

NATHENA

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D2.1 State Of Art

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the state of the art on heat exchangers, their principles of operation, their manufacturing by additive methods, the simulation techniques to characterize their performances as well as the means of testing to validate these performances. Patents and norms related to these subjects are also presented.

2. Summary

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3. Introduction

A heat exchanger is a device that is used to transfer thermal energy (enthalpy) between two or more process fluids. In many heat exchangers, the fluids are separated by a heat transfer surface, and ideally they do not mix or leak. Such exchangers are referred to as direct transfer type, or simply recuperators.

The actual design of heat exchangers is a complicated problem. It involves more than heat-transfer analysis alone. Cost of fabrication and installation, weight, and size play important roles in the selection of the final design from a total cost of ownership point of view. In many cases, although cost is an important consideration, size and carbon footprint often tend to be the dominant factors in choosing a design.

The development of new classes of heat exchangers is ever in progress, both for seeking to reduce the volume of the heat exchanger and to enhance the performances in terms of pressure drop or heat transfer capacity. Clearly, studies in these fields also consider the methods of design, the numerical tools to investigate the performances of a heat exchanger, and also the times that such a tool requires for a reasonable (Bejan A., 2008) (Caputo AC, 2008) (Bejan A, 2011) (Yang J, 2014) (You Y, 2015).

An aircraft for the transport of passengers has often a pleasant cabin environment for a comfortable journey. Heat exchangers are commonly used to cool hydraulics, rammed air, auxiliary power units, gearboxes, and many other components that consist of an aircraft. At high altitudes, the density of air is drastically lower, so it takes more airflow to remove the same amount of heat. Compact heat exchangers are particularly suitable for the aerospace applications due to their less weight, greater compactness, and higher performances due to the improved heat transfer surfaces. In aerospace industries, furthermore, attention is paid on size and weight without compromising on performance aspects.

Despite the impressive progress that has been made during the past decades on development of heat exchangers, there are still serious technical challenges in thermal management of compact devices, mainly due to the growing power density, owing in part to increased performance requirements. This provides the requirement for the development of high performance heat exchangers (Jafari, 2018).

For this purpose, advances in the manufacturing methods that can precisely fabricate fully functional compact and efficient heat transfer devices is important in engineering applications. They should result in the use of less space and material, and allows for higher thermal loads and power densities. In light of this scenario, a significant effort has been carried out towards additive manufacturing (AM) approaches. The benefits of being able to build hollow structures with additive manufacturing may allow higher design complexity that may increase performance, as well as enlarge the application range due to higher strength-to-weight ratios. These complex designs can be made with a favorable surface area, leading to the manufacturing of smart, efficient heat exchangers.

In this report, we reviewed recent advances in heat exchangers dealing with design, simulation, optimization, manufacturing and tests. The organization of this report is as follows.

The first part defines the basics of heat exchanger and some classifications of the existing technologies depending on the operating conditions. The design of heat exchanger, in the second part, relies on theoretical notions linked to physical phenomena, these notions are necessary to understand the fluid behavior and surface heat transfer performance. These phenomena and the related theoretical models are presented. Accordingly, a theoretical design approach is detailed.

Thereafter, a summary of the major heat transfer enhancement techniques is exposed. The fluid distribution improvement and the fouling rate reduction are also synthesized.

The Compact Heat Exchangers part is focused on the existing heat exchanger technologies and some details are given regarding their performances, and manufacturing processes.

The sixth part concerns the utilization additive manufacturing process for heat exchangers. One can find here examples of redesigned heat exchangers using non-usual intensification structures or shapes to overshoot traditional limits in performance, integration, and reliability.

In this part we also consider the new design approaches enabled by the use of numerical simulations. Different approaches are illustrated to present their advantages and limits in the design process. Furthermore, a comparison between the numerical and experimental approaches is investigated.

As annex, the correlations that are quoted in the present document and the thermal and fluidic performances of intensified structures.

4. Heat Exchanger Design

4.1 Introduction

Heat exchangers are units allowing a thermal heat exchange between two fluids at different temperatures. Fluids are usually separated by a solid wall. These devices are used in several industrial processes, transports, electronics or air conditioning. All systems requiring cooling, heating or conservation of a device temperature, use a heat exchanger.

Historically, heat exchangers manufacturers are specialized in one type of heat exchanger. This fact is explained by the tooling used to produce a specific heat exchanger. A plate and fins heat exchanger, for example, need specific tooling to be produced and this tooling is different from those needed to manufacture Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) heat exchanger. New technology like additive manufacturing questions this specialization allowing producing different types of heat exchanger with the same “tool”.

4.2 Flow arrangements

Heat exchangers can be classified in many different ways. Shah and Sekulic (2003) classified them according to transfer process, number of fluids and heat transfer mechanisms. Conventional heat exchangers are further classified according to construction type and flow arrangements. Another arbitrary classification can be made, based on the heat transfer surface area/volume ratio, into compact and noncompact heat exchangers. This classification is made because the type of equipment, fields of applications, and design techniques generally differ. All these classifications are summarized in the following diagram.

As described above, the heat exchangers may be classified according to the fluid-flow path through the heat exchanger. The three basic flow configurations are: counter-flow, cross-flow, parallel-flow:

The main difference between the flow arrangements lies in the temperature distribution along the length of the heat exchanger and the relative amounts of heat transfer under given temperature specifications for specified heat exchanger surfaces. That is, for given flow and specified temperatures, a counter-flow heat exchanger requires minimum area, a parallel-flow heat exchanger requires maximum area, and a cross-flow heat exchanger requires an area in between. Otherwise, counter-current flow allows the largest change in temperature of both fluids and is the most efficient. In co-current flow the streams flow parallel to each other and flow in the same direction. This configuration is less efficient than countercurrent flow but provide more uniform wall temperatures. Cross-flow exhibits a medium efficiency between countercurrent and parallel flow.

A heat exchanger can combine several flow arrangements depending on the fluid paths, the “tube-calandres” heat exchanger on the illustration above gives an example of configuration combining co-current flow, crossflow and counter-current flow.

4.3 Heat exchangers materials

Usually, a heat exchanger material is chosen depending on different parameters such as temperature range or fluid corrosiveness.

Regarding only the temperature parameter, the material selection takes into account two concepts. Firstly, the material conductivity has to be the highest as possible to allow an optimal heat transfer. Secondly, the material needs to provide a good mechanical strength under the working temperature.

That's why for a temperature range from the ambient to 200°C, copper, aluminum and their alloys are usually used. Steel or titanium are used to reach higher temperature. In case of high averaged temperature up to 700°C, stainless steels are used. For higher temperatures, specific steels, silicon carbide and nitride, carbon are the selected option.

4.4 Traditional heat exchanger technologies

The technology selection of a heat exchanger is based on operating parameters (Shah & Sekulic). The two first parameters are operating pressures and temperatures. The heat exchanger during operation must withstand with the stresses due to pressure and temperature difference between the two fluids. The most versatile exchanger for a wide range of operating pressure and temperature is the shell and tube heat exchanger. The next parameter is the cost which is a very important factor of selection. The cost per unit of heat transfer surface area is for example higher for a gasketed plate exchanger than for a shell and tube exchanger. However for a total cost (capital, installation, operation, and maintenance) PHE are less expensive than tube and shell.

Fouling and cleanability are also important design considerations and impact the heat exchanger choice.

Leakage can be taken into account when it is necessary to avoid a potential fluid contamination. Gasketed plate exchangers have for example more leakage probability than a shell and tube.

Fluid type also impact the heat exchanger selection for example plate heat exchanger are generally not used in gas to gas exchanger because they create too much pressure drops.

The following tables and matrix summarize different traditional heat exchangers technologies and help to technology choice depending on the working conditions (nature of fluids, pressure, temperature, etc.).

Table Extracted from Greth data:

<i>Technology</i>	<i>Functions</i>	<i>Fluids</i>	<i>Working Conditions</i>	<i>Technical Data</i>
Continuous Finned Coils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * used as evaporator or condenser for heat pump or refrigerating group * as exchanger for air handling unit, and aero refrigerant unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Air * Refrigerant fluid * Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Temperature : - 50°C/+200°C * Pressure tube side: several tens of bar * Mass Flow : 10 to 1000000 m³/h * Power : 100W up to several tens of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tubes external diameter between ¾ inches up to 5mm - Tube Thickness : 0.5 down to 0.25mm - Fin thickness: 0.12 up to 2mm

			MW	
Micro-channels	* used as evaporator or condenser for heat pump or medium power refrigerating group	* Air * Refrigerant fluid	* Temperature : -50°C/+200°C * Pressure tube side: several tens of bar * Mass Flow : 10 to 10000 m ³ /h * Power : 100W up to several tens of kW	- Tubes width :16 up to 35mm Thickness :1.5mm up to 2mm - Fin thickness:0.1 up to 0.15mm - Fin pitch : 1.5 to 2.5mm
Discontinuous fins and tubes Heat exchanger	* Recuperator for exhausts gases and smoke	* Smokes and exhaust gases * Water * Oil	* Temperature : -50°C/+500°C * Pressure tube side: several tens of bar * Mass Flow : 1000 to 1000000 m ³ /h * Power : tens of kW up to tens of MW	- Tubes in copper, aluminum, steel with an external diameter between 1 to ½ inch - Tube thickness 1 up to 2 mm - Fins : all materials welded or brazed
Plate and gaskets heat exchanger	* Heat exchanger for liquid	* All liquids	* Temperature : -50°C/+200°C * Max pressure: 20 Bars * Mass Flow : 10 to thousands of m ³ /h * Power : several kW up to tens of MW	- Common plate thickness 0.5mm
Brazed Plate heat exchanger	* Heat exchanger for liquid	* All liquid compatible with brazed plate * Multiphase flow	* Temperature : -50°C/+200°C Max pressure: 40 bars * Mass Flow : 10 to hundreds of m ³ /h * Power : several kW up to 1 MW	- Common plate thickness 0.3/0.4mm
Welded plate heat exchanger	* Evaporator and condenser * Thermal recuperator	* All liquids compatible with plates	* Temperature up to 300°C * Pressure < 90 bar	-
Table Source : (Groupement pour la recherche sur les échangeurs thermiques (Greth))				

Table extracted from Compact Heat exchanger, J.E Hesselgreaves:

Type of heat exchanger	Plate-and-frame (Gaskets)	Partially welded plate	Fully welded plate (AlfaRex)	Brazed plate	Platular plate	Compabloc plate
Features						
Compactness (m ² /m ³)	→ 200	→ 200	→ 200	→ 200	200	→ 300
Stream types ¹	liquid-liquid gas-liquid 2-phase	liquid-liquid gas-liquid 2-phase	liquid-liquid gas-liquid 2-phase	liquid-liquid 2-phase	gases liquids 2-phase	liquids
Materials ²	s/s, Ti, Incoloy Hastelloy graphite polymer	s/s Ti Incoloy Hastelloy	s/s Ti Ni alloys	s/s	s/s Hastelloy Ni alloys	s/s Ti, Incoloy
Temperature range (°C)	-35 to +200	-35 to +200	-50 to +350	-195 to +220	→ 700	→ 300
Maximum pressure (bar) ³	25	25	40	30	40	32
Cleaning methods	Mech. ¹⁹	Mech. ^{4,19} Chem. ⁶	Chemical	Chem. ⁵	Mech. ^{12,19}	Mech. ¹⁹
Corrosion resistance	Good ⁷	Good ⁷	Excellent	Good ⁸	Good	Good
Multi-stream capability	Yes ⁹	No	No	No	Yes ¹³	Not usually
Multi-pass capability	Yes	Yes	Yes	No ¹⁰	Yes	Yes

Packinox plate	Spiral	Brazed plate-fin	Diffusion-bonded plate-fin	Printed-circuit	Polymer (e.g. channel plate)	Plate-and-shell	Marbond
→ 300	→ 200	800-1,500	700-800	200-5,000	450	-	→ 10,000
gases liquids 2-phase	liquid-liquid 2-phase	gases liquids 2-phase	gases liquids 2-phase	gases liquids 2-phase	gas-liquid (14)	liquids	gases liquids 2-phase
s/s, Ti Hastelloy Inconel	c/s, s/s, Ti, Incoloy Hastelloy	Al, s/s Ni alloy	Ti s/s	s/s, Ni, Ni alloys Ti	PVDF ²⁰ PP ²¹	s/s, Ti (shell also in c/s) ¹⁵	s/s, Ni, Ni alloys, Ti
-200 to +700	→ 400	Cryogenic to +650	→ 550	-200 to +900	→ 150 ¹⁸	→ 350	-200 to +900
300	25	90	>200	>400	6	70	>400
Mech. ^{16,19}	Mech. ¹⁹	Chemical	Chemical	Chemical	Water wash	Mech. ^{16,19} Chem. ¹⁷	Chemical
Good	Good	Good	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Good	Excellent
Yes ⁹	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not usually	Yes	Yes

Table extracted from Compact Heat exchanger, giving a matrix of choice according to W.M. Kays & A.L. London :

Table 1.0.3 - Comparative Summary of Compact Heat Exchanger Features

Type of Heat Exchanger	Area Density (m ² /m ³) (0)	Stream Types (1)	Materials (3)	Temperature Range (°C)	Maximum Pressure (bar) (2)	Fluid Limitations	Cleaning Methods	Corrosion Resistance (18)	Multi-stream Capability	Multi-pass Capability
Plate and frame (Gasketed)	→200	liquid-liquid gas-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, Incoloy Hastelloy, graphite, polymer	-25 to +175 Special -35 to +200	Normal 25 Special 40	Limited by gasket type. Not normal for gases	Mechanical (14) Chemical	Good (7)	Yes (9)	Yes
Partially welded plate	→200	gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, Incoloy Hastelloy	-35 to +200	25	Few - Some types need clean fluids	Mechanical (4, 14) Chemical (6)	Good (7)	No	Yes
Fully welded plate (AlfaRex)	→200	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, Ni alloys	-50 to +650	40	Few - Some types need clean fluid	Chemical	Excellent	No	Yes
Brazed plate	→200	liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s	Cu braze -195 to +220 Ni braze →400	Cu braze 30 Ni braze 16	Must be compatible with braze	Chemical (5)	Good (8)	No	No (10)
Bavex plate	200 - 300	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ni, Cu, Ti, Special steels	-200 to +900	60	Few	Mechanical (11, 9) Chemical	Good	In principle	Yes
Platular plate	200	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, Hastelloy, Ni alloys	-180 to +700	40	Few	Mechanical (12, 14)	Good	Yes (13)	Yes
Compabloc plate	→300	liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, Incoloy	→300	32	Few	Mechanical (14)	Good	Not usually	Yes
Packinox Plate	→300	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, Hastelloy, Inconel	-200 to +700	300	Few	Mechanical (16, 14)	Good	Yes (9)	Yes
Spiral	→200	gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	c/s, s/s, Ti, Incoloy, Hastelloy	→400 Special →850	30	Few	Mechanical (14)	Good	No	No

Type of Heat Exchanger	Area Density (m ² /m ³) (0)	Stream Types (1)	Materials (3)	Temperature Range (°C)	Maximum Pressure (bar) (2)	Fluid Limitations	Cleaning Methods	Corrosion Resistance (18)	Multi-stream Capability	Multi-pass Capability
Brazed plate-fin	800 - 1,500	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	Al, s/s, Ti Ni alloy	Al -270 to +200 s/s cryogenic to +650	120	Low fouling. Many limitations with Al	Chemical	Good	Yes	Yes
Diffusion-bonded plate-fin	700 - 800	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	Ti, s/s, Ni	→400	200	Low fouling	Chemical	Excellent	Yes	Yes
Printed circuit	200 - 5,000	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ni, Ni alloys Ti	-200 to +900	500	Low fouling	Chemical	Excellent	Yes	Yes
Polymer - compact shell and tube	→275	liquid-liquid	Teflon	→200	11	Few	Water wash	Excellent	No	No
Plate and shell	→200	liquid-liquid	s/s, Ti, (shell also in c/s) (15)	-200 to +900	100	Few	Mechanical (16, 14) Chemical (17)	Good	No	Yes
Shell and tube (19)	→100	gas-gas gas-liquid liquid-liquid two-phase	s/s, Ti, (shell also in c/s), many different materials	-100 to +600	Shell 300 Tubes 1400	Few	Mechanical (16, 14) Chemical (17)	Good	No	Yes

Notes for Table 1.0.3 → = up to, s/s = stainless steel, Ti = titanium, Ni = nickel, Al = aluminium, Cu = copper, c/s = carbon steel
 (0) Area includes the secondary surface (such as fins) (1) Two-phase includes boiling and condensing duties
 (2) The maximum pressure capability is unlikely to occur at the higher operating temperatures, and assumes no pressure/stress-related corrosion. (3) Other special alloys are frequently available
 (4) On gasket side (5) Ensure compatibility with copper braze
 (6) On welded side (7) Function of gasket as well as plate material
 (8) Function of braze as well as plate material (9) Not common
 (10) Not in a single unit (11) On tube side
 (12) Only when flanged access provided, otherwise chemical cleaning (13) Five fluids maximum
 (14) Can be dismantled (15) Shell may be composed of polymeric material
 (16) On shell side (17) On plate or tube side
 (18) Primarily a function of construction materials rather than the exchanger type (19) Not a compact exchanger technology (given for comparison)

The following table extracted from the previous book, allow the choice of the heat exchanger depending on the fluid characteristics such as viscosity, particles and pressure. The table also includes the maintenance and inspection aspect which can be significant points in case of fouling operating conditions.

- Plate heat exchangers and shell and tubes exchangers

HEAT EXCHANGER SELECTION CRITERIA							
Physical Properties	Plate Heat Exchangers				Tubular Heat Exchangers		
	Plate in Frame	Plate and Shell	Welded	Brazed	Double Tube	Quadruple Tube	Multi Tube
Viscosity							
< 10 CP	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
< 1000 Cp	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓
> 1000 Cp	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓
Shear sensitive particulates							
< 1 mm diameter	✓✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
< 10 mm diameter	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
> 10 mm diameter	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓✓	✓	✗
25- 37 mm diameter	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
Insensitive particulates							
< 1 mm diameter	✓✓	✓	✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
< 10 mm diameter	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
> 10 mm diameter	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓✓	✗	✓
> 25-37 mm diameter	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
Fibres							
2 mm	✓✓	✗	✓	✗	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
15 mm	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
Fluid pressures							
< 1200 kPa (low)	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
< 2200 kPa (medium)	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
> 2200 kPa (high)	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓
Fluid temperatures							
< 150°C	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
> 150°C	✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
Flexibility for expansion	✓✓✓	✗	✓✓✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Maintenance	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
Ease of Inspection	✓✓✓	✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
Compactness /floor space	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓	✓	✓
Comparison: - ✓✓✓ = Good selection ✓✓ = Suitable ✓ = Within working range ✗ = Not recommended							
Note: The table above is for general comparison of specific characteristics. It is not to be taken as definitive or absolute. For a specific duty more than one property may be relevant leading to a different selection. For optimum heat exchanger selection readers should refer to their equipment supplier.							

- Plate heat exchangers and spiral exchangers

HEAT EXCHANGER SELECTION CRITERIA							
Physical Properties	Plate Heat Exchangers					Spiral Heat Exchangers	
	Standard	Wide Gap	Double Wall	Twin Wall	Diabon Graphite	Spiral Flow	Cross Flow
Service							
Liquid / Liquid	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓
Gas / Liquid	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓
Gas / Gas	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*
Condensation	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓
Vaporisation	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓ to ✓✓✓*	✓
Nature of Media							
Corrosive	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓	✓
Aggressive	✓	✓	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
Viscous	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓
Heat Sensitive	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓
Hostile Reactions	✓	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓
Fibrous	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✓✓✓	✓
Slurries and Suspensions	✓	✓✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓✓	✓
Fouling	✓	✓✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓
Inspection							
Corrosion	A	A	A	B	A	A	B
Leakage	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Fouling	A	A	A	B	A	A	B
Maintenance							
Mechanical Cleaning	A	A	A	B	A	A	B
Modification	A	A	A	A	A	C	C
Repair	A	A	A	A	A	(A)	(A)
Fluid pressures							
< 1200 kPa (low)	✓✓✓	✗	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓
< 2200 kPa (medium)	✓✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✗	✗
> 2200 kPa (high)	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Fluid temperatures							
< 150°C	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
> 150°C	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
Comparison: - ✓✓✓ = Usually Good selection ✓✓ = Often Good Selection ✓ = Sometimes Good Selection ✗ = Usually unsuitable A = Both Sides B = One side C = No side							
* Depending on operating pressure, gas/vapour density etc.							
Note: The table above is for general comparison of specific characteristics. It is not to be taken as definitive or absolute. For a specific duty more than one property may be relevant leading to a different selection. For optimum heat exchanger selection readers should refer to their equipment supplier.							

The flow regime can also be taken into account to define if extended surfaces are necessary. The following table gives an example of different technology choice depending on the Reynolds number.

Technologies	Liquide		Gaz	
	Bas Reynolds	Haut Reynolds	Bas Reynolds	Haut Reynolds
Rugosité et porosité	Echangeurs à plaques corruguées	x	x	
	Tubes à rugosité de faible amplitude		x	x
	Tubes à rugosité de forte amplitude	x		x
Extension de surface	Plaques à ailettes		x	x
	Tubes à ailettes internes	x	x	
	Tubes à ailettes externes			x

(Shah, 1981) proposed a tree configuration for the heat exchanger technology choice :

Hereunder are provided illustrations of the different types of heat exchangers.

- Tubular heat exchangers (coaxial tubes, shell and tube, coiled tube)

- Plate heat exchangers

- Extended surface heat exchangers (fin tube, thin-sheet)

- Regenerators

4.5 Basic Thermal Design for Heat Exchanger

i) Dimensionless groups

To describe and quantify the occurring phenomena in a heat exchanger, several parameters such as Reynolds number, Nusselt or Colburn factor are used. This part defines these numbers and set correlations binding them.

o Reynolds Number

The Reynolds number, Re , is a dimensionless quantity used in fluids mechanics to predict the flow patterns in different fluid flow situations (Wikipedia, Reynolds Number, 2018). It is the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces within a fluid. Re is given by the following equation:

$$Re = \rho UL / \mu$$

Where ρ is the fluid density (kg/m^3), U is the average stream velocity of the fluid (m/s), L is the characteristic linear dimension (m) depending on the geometry and μ is the fluid dynamic viscosity (Pa.s).

At low Reynolds number, flow regime is qualified as “laminar”. The flow is dominated by viscous forces and is characterized by smooth and constant fluid motion. The pressure loss is minimal but the heat transfer rate is limited by the laminar boundary layer.

At high Reynolds number, the fluid flow is in a “turbulent” regime. Inertial forces dominate viscous forces and induce chaotic eddies, vortices and flow instabilities. At this regime, the heat transfer rate is higher, same as the pressure loss.

Reynolds number can be used to predict the transition from laminar to turbulent flow regime in a heat exchanger, the flow regime impacts heavily the heat transfer performance.

The regime flow transition appear at different Reynolds depending of the geometry. For example, a flow in a pipe is considered laminar when $Re < 2300$ and fully turbulent for a $Re > 10^4$ (White, 2001). On the other side, the turbulent flow is reached for a flat plate only at approximately $Re > 10^6$ (White, 2001).

o Prandtl Number

Prandtl number, noted Pr, is a dimensionless number, defined as the ratio of momentum diffusivity to thermal diffusivity (Wikipedia, Prandtl Number, 2018). Pr number is given by the following equation:

$$Pr = \frac{\text{Viscous Diffusion Rate}}{\text{Thermal Diffusion Rate}} = \frac{\mu/\rho}{\lambda/(C_p\rho)} = C_{p\text{fluid}} \cdot \frac{\mu}{\lambda}$$

Where λ is the thermal conductivity ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), μ is the dynamic viscosity (Pa.s), and is C_p the specific heat of the fluid ($\text{J}/\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}$).

Prandtl number is used notably in Nusselt correlations in which it takes the fluid characteristics into account.

o Nusselt Number

Nusselt number, noted Nu, is a dimensionless number which can be defined as the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer across a boundary. The convection term includes both advection and diffusion phenomenon.

$$Nu = \frac{\text{Convective Heat Transfer}}{\text{Conductive Heat Transfer}} = \frac{h}{k/L} = \frac{hL}{k}$$

Where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient of the flow, L is a characteristic length depending of the geometry, and k is the thermal conductivity of the fluid ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$).

Nusselt number can be used to evaluate the heat transfer coefficient during the pre-sizing part. Several correlations can be used to evaluate Nu number. Correlations are defined using experiments or numerical simulations. Usually these correlations bind Nusselt number to Reynolds and Prandtl

numbers and help to quickly predict the heat transfer coefficient of a geometry depending on the fluid characteristics and velocity. Some examples of these correlations are given below:

Nusselt Correlation for a flat plate in laminar flow:

$$Nu = 0.332 Re_x^{\frac{1}{2}} Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \text{ for } Pr > 0.6$$

Nusselt Correlation in turbulent pipe flow:

$$Nu = \frac{\left(\frac{0.79 \ln(Re - 1.64)^{-2}}{8}\right) (Re - 1000) Pr}{1 + 12.77 \left(\frac{0.79 \ln(Re - 1.64)^{-2}}{8}\right)^{0.5} \left(Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1\right)}$$

More correlations are available in the ANNEX - CORRELATIONS.

o Colburn Factor

Colburn factor is a non-dimensional parameter used in convective heat transfer analysis

$$j = St \cdot Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{Nu}{Re Pr^{1/3}}$$

Where St is the Stanton number and Pr the Prandtl number.

o Friction Factor

The friction factor can be used to quantify the heat exchanger pressure drops.

$$f = \frac{\Delta P D_h}{4L \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho U_0^2\right)}$$

More correlations are available for friction factors in ANNEX - CORRELATIONS section.

o Stanton Number

Stanton number, noted St, is a dimensionless number use to measure the ratio of heat transferred into a fluid to the thermal capacity of the fluid. It characterizes heat transfer in forced convection flows (Wikipedia, Stanton Number, 2018).

$$St = \frac{h}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot U}$$

Where h is the convection heat transfer coefficient ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$), ρ is the density (kg/m^3), C_p the specific heat ($J/Kg \cdot K$), and U the fluid velocity (m/s).

ii) Thermal characterization & Overall heat transfer coefficient K

For a given situation, a heat exchanger is defined in a stationary state by its thermal power, noted P (W), and its overall heat exchange coefficient, noted K ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$). The thermal power is the power exchanged between the two fluids. The heat exchange coefficient link the thermal power to the logarithmic fluid temperature difference, ΔTLM (K), and the heat exchange effective area, S (m^2). (Hugo, 2012)

$$P = K.S.\Delta TLM \text{ with } \Delta TLM = \frac{\theta_a - \theta_b}{\ln\left(\frac{\theta_a}{\theta_b}\right)}$$

Where θ_a the difference of temperature between the hot and cold fluid from the “a” side and θ_b the temperature difference from the side “b”.

The thermal power P can be determined experimentally with a balance on each fluid enthalpy.

$$P = \dot{m}_a C_{pa} \theta_a = \dot{m}_b C_{pb} \theta_b$$

Where \dot{m} is the fluid mass flow rate (Kg/s), and C_p is the specific heat capacity at a constant pressure (J/Kg.K).

In this theory, the balance consider that all the power lost by one fluid is recovered by the other. In reality, a part of the heat is lost outside the heat exchanger.

The overall heat exchange coefficient, K, is compounded of several terms: the heat exchange coefficient of the first fluid and the effective area of exchange of the first fluid side, the thermal resistance of the solid structure and a thermal contact resistance, and finally the heat exchange coefficient of the second fluid and its effective area.

$$\frac{1}{KS} = \frac{1}{h_{f1}S_{f1}} + R_{conduction} + R_{contact} + \frac{1}{h_{f2}S_{f2}}$$

The efficiency of a heat exchanger, noted ϵ , is usually defined as the thermal power exchanged divided by the maximal power exchangeable, P_{max} . P_{max} being the power exchanged by the fluid with the smaller flow rate heat capacity considering the case in which this fluid reach the outlet at the inlet temperature of the second fluid.

$$\epsilon = \frac{P}{P_{max}} = \frac{P}{(\dot{m}C_p)_{min} (T_{a in} - T_{b in})}$$

The efficiency is given in the literature as a function of NTU number and of the flow configuration (Hugo, 2012). The following correlation is an example of this correlation for a heat exchanger in counter-flow:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1 - \exp(-NTU(1 - C_r))}{1 - C_r \exp(-NTU(1 - c_r))} \text{ if } C_r < 1$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{NTU}{1+NTU} \text{ if } C_r = 1 \text{ (Same fluid, same flow rate)}$$

We will details the use of NTU number in the next sections.

For classics heat exchangers, a lot of abacuses exist giving correlations with flow regime and studied geometries. However, in the case of innovative heat exchangers, abacuses don't exist. In this case, it is necessary to determine for each configuration the evolution of the heat exchange coefficient depending of the flow conditions. These are usually describe with the Colburn factor, j, as a function of the Reynolds number. Stanton and Prandlt number are also used. All these numbers are details in the dimensionless group section.

iii) Design Methodology

This part contains classical pre-sizing methodologies and abacuses. The NTU method will be presented.

o Log-Mean Temperature Difference Method

When temperatures are known, the heat transfer coefficient can be determined by using the logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD). (Kay & Nedderman, 1985)

Assuming the heat exchanger has two sides called A and B where the fluids enter or exit the heat exchanger, LMTD can be written as:

$$LMTD = \frac{\Delta T_A - \Delta T_B}{\ln \Delta T_A - \ln \Delta T_B}$$

Where ΔT is the temperature difference between the two fluids on the side A or B. Heat transfer coefficient K can then be written as a function of the power exchange P (W), the heat transfer area (m^2) S , and LMTD.

$$P = K \cdot S \cdot LMTD$$

o NTU Method

The Number of Transfer Units (NTU) method is a methodology to calculate the heat transfer rate in heat exchangers. (Incropera & DeWitt, 1990) (Incropera F., DeWitt, Bergman, & Lavine, 2006)

The first step is to define the effectiveness ϵ of the heat exchanger. The effectiveness is the ratio of the actual heat transfer rate and the maximum possible heat transfer rate:

$$\epsilon = \frac{q}{q_{max}}$$

Where $q = C_h(T_{h,i} - T_{h,o}) = C_c(T_{c,o} - T_{c,i})$ is the actual heat transfer rate (W) and C is the heat capacity rate (W/K).

For a particular case if ϵ is known or chosen, and the inlet conditions and streams are known, the amount of heat that will be transferred can be written as: $q = \epsilon C_{min}(T_{h,i} - T_{c,i})$

For any heat exchangers ϵ can be written as a function of NTU and the heat capacity ratio

$$C_r = C_{min}/C_{max}$$

The number of heat transfer units, NTU, can be used to find the necessary heat transfer coefficient K to reach a specific efficiency, relation between K and NTU is given by the formula:

$$NTU = \frac{KS}{C_{min}}$$

Where K is the overall heat transfer coefficient and S the heat transfer area.

Now K is defined as a function of NTU, and the effectiveness has been determined, relations between these parameters are needed to calculate K . Depending on the flow configuration, different correlations of effectiveness as a function of NTU can be used.

NTU correlation can be found in the ANNEX - CORRELATIONS part.

4.6 Heat Exchanger pressure drops & pumping power

A heat exchanger is defined by a pressure loss for each fluid. This pressure drop term is divided in two terms: minor losses and friction losses.

The singular pressure drop coincide to shrinking and expansion of the cross sectional area along the fluid path in the heat exchanger. These changes in the cross sectional area induce acceleration (convergent) and deceleration (divergent) of the fluid that create pressure loss.. Correlations for singular pressure drop in pipes can be easily found and used for ducts before the manifold or ducts inside the heat exchanger core.

The second type of pressure loss, the regular pressure drop, is proportional to the heat exchanger area. The origin of this phenomenon being the friction of the fluid on heat exchanger's walls. This type of pressure loss occur at all stages of the heat exchanger and is particularly important in the core of the heat exchanger where the developed area reaches a maximum.

According to (Hesselgreaves, Law, & Reay, 2016), the pressure drop thought a core can be given in term of friction factor:

$$\Delta P = \frac{1}{2} \rho u^2 \frac{4L}{d_h} f$$

Comparing two surface 1 and 2 with a given pressure drop can be done using friction factors:

$$\frac{A_{c,1}^2}{A_{c,2}^2} = \frac{f_1 L_1 d_{h,2}}{f_2 L_2 d_{h,1}}$$

If the thermal performance is not considered, the flow areas for two surfaces with similar friction factors are the same if the ratios L/d_h are the same.

The pressure drop strongly depends of the structures used for heat transfer enhancement, in this case correlation for friction factors can be founded in ANNEX - CORRELATIONS part.

For complex design, simulation or experimentation is needed to evaluate the pressure drop across the structure.

For gas-gas or liquid-gas applications, the pumping power have a direct impact on the efficiency.

Using the pressure drop relationship cited previously, the pumping power is given by \dot{W}_p

$$\dot{W}_p = \frac{\dot{m} \Delta P}{\rho} = \frac{2 f \dot{m}^3 L}{\rho^2 A_c^2 d_h}$$

The pumping power can be compared using:

$$\frac{\dot{W}_{p1}}{\dot{W}_{p2}} = \frac{\left(\frac{f}{j}\right)_1}{\left(\frac{f}{j}\right)_2} \left(\frac{A_{c,2}}{A_{c,1}}\right)^2$$

4.7 Surface basic heat transfer and flow friction characteristics / effect of surface roughness on heat transfer coefficient

i) *Physic principles*

To understand surface basic heat transfer it is necessary to understand all the notions link to the thermal and flow phenomenon.

This part introduces some physical heat exchange principles. Heat transfer takes place when a body has a heterogeneous temperature distribution. Heat transfer can take different forms like conduction, convection and radiation. These three heat transfer principles will be explained in the next subsections. Subtle notions ensuing from this principles will be detailed (boundary layer, etc).

o **Conduction**

Thermal conduction is the heat transfer part due to microscopic collisions of particles in a body. Conduction takes place in solid, fluid (liquids or gazes) until the system reaches a thermal equilibrium (no temperature differences).

Power transferred by conduction at stationary state is given by the Fourier equation:

$$\phi = -\lambda \cdot \nabla T \rightarrow \Phi = \frac{\lambda S}{e} \cdot \Delta T = \frac{\Delta T}{R_{th}}$$

Where λ ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$) is the thermal conductivity of a material, ∇T (K/m) is the temperature gradient, ϕ (W/m^2) is the heat flux density, Φ (W) the heat flux (also called the heat transfer rate), S (m^2) is the heat exchange surface, ΔT (K) the temperature difference, and R_{th} ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$).

o **Convection**

Convection is the part of heat transfer due to molecules movement in fluids like gases or liquids. Convection is due to two phenomenon: diffusion (example: movement of molecules from a high density zone to a low density zone) and advection (movement of molecules by bulk motion).

The power transferred by a fluid in convection to a solid is given by the following equation:

$$P = K S \Delta T$$

Where K ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$) is a heat transfer coefficient depending of the fluid characteristics and of flow conditions, S the surface (m^2) of contact between the fluid and the solid, ΔT (K) the temperature difference between the fluid and the solid.

Two major convection mechanisms can be identified: forced and natural convection.

- Natural convection

Natural convection, also called free convection, is induced by fluid temperature difference and appear only under gravity effect. The temperature difference causes a heterogeneous density distribution in the fluid that create a fluid motion that matches Archimedes' principle.

A simple example of this phenomenon is water convection in a pan that can be observe during cooking. The temperature difference between the bottom and the top of liquid creates density difference and start convection.

Natural convection is described by Rayleigh number. In heat exchanger, natural convection can take place in dead zone.

- Forced convection

In forced convection, fluid movements results from pumps or fan mechanical work. It is typically used to increase the rate of heat exchange by increasing fluid speed (advection phenomenon increases).

At low speed, flow are dominated by viscous forces, the flow is smooth. The regime is qualified of "laminar". As speed increases, excessive kinetic energy of the fluid flow overcome the damping effect of the fluid's viscosity, the fluid dynamic is characterized by chaotic changes in pressure and velocity: the regime is qualified of "turbulent".

The fluid flow is characterized by two distinct regions, a thin fluid layer (the boundary layer) in which velocity gradients and shear stresses are large and a region outside the boundary layer in which velocity gradients and shear stresses are negligible.. The fluid velocity is null at the wall when the velocity far from the wall is equal to the non-chaotic flow maximum speed U_0 . It means that a speed profile is visible this profile becomes closer to a constant as the fluid viscosity increase. The boundary layer internal velocity profile depends on its laminar or turbulent nature.

The heat transfer rate increases when the boundary layer is in a turbulent state. Indeed, the turbulent state increases the mixing, this decreases the fluid temperature close to the wall granting a better temperature difference ΔT .

o Radiation

Radiation is the last heat transfer bias. It cover energy transmission under electromagnetic waves (photons) forms. In the case of a blackbody, radiation is defined by the Stephan equation:

$$\Phi(W) = \sigma ST^4$$

Where $\sigma(W.m^{-2}.K^{-4})$ is the Stephan-Boltzmann constant, T(K) the temperature of the emitting body, and S (m^2) the surface of emission.

Thermal radiation are principally take into account in heat sink design. In the case of two fluids heat exchanger, energy transmission by thermal radiation is neglected with respect to convection and conduction phenomena.

ii) *Intensification techniques and friction factor*

In this section, we will discuss of the channels and inserts shapes used to enhance heat transfer in air heat exchanger. A synthesis of helpful correlations from literature and link with the presented structures will be retrievable in the ANNEX - CORRELATIONS section. Comparison will be established.

Heat transfer intensifications gather all technics used to increase the thermal power of a heat exchanger for a given device volume. Several ways to enhance heat transfer in air-air heat exchanger are possible like surface condition modification, surface extension, inserts generating vorticity and turbulence, fluid mixer, surface pattern, etc. (Hugo, 2012)

The heat transfer will be increased by increasing the effective heat transfer area, mixing the flow or reducing the boundary layer thickness, without creating too much pressure loss.

o Corrugations / Twisted Geometries

Corrugated surfaces are already well-known and used in industrial heat exchangers. Corrugated surfaces are surface with ripples. These ripples increase the heat transfer by increasing flow mixing, this augmentation depend on the corrugations parameters like the wave pitch and the wave frequency and depends on the application. Using corrugations increase the available heat transfer area for a given heat exchanger size. Corrugated surfaces can be used on plate or tubes geometries with various degrees of complexity.

A wide choice of corrugation pattern exists (over 60 patterns worldwide). The following figure illustrate some patterns.

These patterns can be alternated to create tortuous flow passages with interruptions increasing the heat transfer rate. Alternate corrugations patterns can also play a preventing role by decreasing fouling resistance with shear stress and turbulence enhancement. Plates are designated as hard or soft depending of the turbulence intensity generated.

An illustration of complex shape can be observed in the study of (Kareem, Jaafar, & Lazim). They focus on the heat transfer enhancement induced by a two-start spirally corrugated tubes compared to a normal tube showed that the spiral corrugation can improve the heat transfer significantly at low and medium Reynolds number. At these Re , the heat transfer enhancement range is 21.7% - 60.5% for a low pressure drop increase (20-36%). However for higher Reynolds number the pressure loss is increased much greater than the heat transfer.

Grooved tubes

(Bilen, Cetin, Gul, & Balta, 2008) studied the heat transfer and friction characteristics of a fully developed turbulent air flow in different grooved tubes (Re range 10,000 to 38,000). Three types of grooved tubes were tested (circular, rectangular, trapezoidal) as shown below:

The geometric shapes of the grooved tube, dimensions in mm (a) circular, (b) rectangular and (c) trapezoidal grooves.

Grooved tubes are widely used in modern heat exchanger, they are known for being effective to enhance heat transfer. In these studies grooved tubes are compared to a smooth tube geometry. The following graphic plotting Nusselt as a function of Reynolds number illustrate a significant increase of heat transfer performance for grooved geometries. The circular grooved appear to be the most effective compared to the rectangular and trapezoidal shape.

Variation of Nusselt number with Reynolds number for smooth and different grooved tubes.

The maximum heat transfer enhancement is granted by the circular groove with 63% of enhancement, while the heat transfer augmentation is 58% and 47% for trapezoidal and rectangular groove respectively compared to a smooth tube. Comparing the rectangular and trapezoidal shape to circular groove geometry, it appears that the higher transfer rate of the circular one is due to more flow mixing and disturbance. The grooved tube also offers more heat transfer area and provide periodic redevelopment of boundary layers. The thermal boundary layer for grooved flow are thinner compared to a smooth pipe.

The evolution of the friction factor with the Reynolds number is illustrated by the graphic below:

Variation of friction factor with Reynolds number for smooth and different grooved tubes.

The friction factor for grooved pipes present a similar value meaning friction factor is independent of Reynolds number, while the smooth tube show a decreasing friction factor value with Re augmentation.

The following graphic compare the performance for a given pumping power between the grooved pipe and other geometries in literature, grooved pipes appearing as a very efficient geometry compared to traditional inserts and a good potential candidate for high Reynolds air flow.

Comparison of thermal performance in the grooved pipe with the results in the literature.

(Maradiya, Vahder, & Agarwal, 2017) review several type of twisted inserts and geometry in the literature. Geometrical parameters like the width, length, twist ratio, and twist direction affect significantly the heat transfer. The inserts requiring an additional pumping power, the good selection of an insert is important to have a significant impact on the performance. The study emphasizes that the roughness gives in many cases better performance than the twisted tape like in the case of flow with large Prandtl number. In all case enhancement is due to reduction in flow cross section area, the increase in turbulence intensity, and the increase in tangential flow. The twisted direction have also to be taken into account, counter swirl performing better than co-swirl for multiple twisted tapes. The role of inserts stay more significant for laminar regime than for turbulent, however wire coil inserts can be used to enhance heat transfer in turbulent flow. The combination of twisted tape inserts and wire coil grants better heat transfer performance for all regime. Perforations appear to be an efficient way to save material and reduce obstruction.

It is bring to light that it is better to use a full length tape rather than regularly spaced tape.

They give an exhaustive review of the impact of a lot of inserts parameters such as:

- Twisted tape dimensions
- Effect of twist ratio :

- Effect of helical inserts
- Effect of modified twisted tape
- Effects of wings and winglet twisted tape
- Effects of wire coil insert
- Effects of perforations and of surface characteristics
- Use of rib and groove to reduce viscous sublayer
- Effect of corrugation and vortex generator

The study give a recap of the different technics in the following table. The insert can be compare using the TPF (Thermal Performance factor) which is the ratio of the relative effect of change in heat transfer rate to change in friction factor.

Author	Modification	Parameter	Re	TPF	Nu/Nu ₀	f/f ₀	Fluid type	Image
Eiamsa-ard et al. (2009)	Short length twisted tape Short length twisted tape Short length twisted tape	Twist ratio -4, Tape length ratio - 0.39-1	5000 10000 20000	0.98 0.95 0.91	1.30 1.24 1.16	2.31 2.23 2.1	Air	
Eiamsa and Promvongse (2010)	Alternate clockwise and counterclockwise Alternate clockwise and counterclockwise Alternate clockwise and counterclockwise	Twist ratio - 3-5, Twist angle - 30°-90°	5000 10000 20000	1.35 1.26 1.18	2.52 2.18 1.8	6.62 5.26 3.58	Water	
Rahimi et al. (2009)	Jagged twisted tape Jagged twisted tape	Width - 15 mm, Pitch length- 5 cm, Twist ratio - 2.94, Thickness-1 mm	5000 10000	1.17 1.09	2.22 1.93	6.86 5.61	Water	
Shabanian et al. (2011)	Butterfly twisted tape Butterfly twisted tape	Thickness- 0.5 mm, Holding rod diameter- 1.9 mm, Angle-45°-135°, Pitch length-6cm	5000 10000	1.60 1.53	4.74 3.73	26.6 14.8	Water	
Eiamsa-ard et al. (2013a)	Twin Delta winged tape Twin Delta winged tape	Twist ratio-3, Wing tip angle-20°-60°, Wing declination angle-15°	5000 10000	1.24 1.12	2.54 2.10	8.78 6.64	Water	
Eiamsa-ard et al. (2010a)	Delta winglet twisted tape Delta winglet twisted tape Delta winglet twisted tape	Twist ratio-3-5, Depth of wing cut ratio-0.11-0.32	5000 10000 20000	1.22 1.18 1.15	2.24 2.08 1.94	6.3 5.65 4.83	Water	
Promvongse et al. (2014)	Twisted tape with winglet vortex generator Twisted tape with winglet vortex generator Twisted tape with winglet vortex generator	Twist ratio-4&5, Attack angle of winglet-30°, R _g - 0.1-0.2, R _p -2-5	5000 10000 20000	1.56 1.48 1.38	3.16 2.95 2.83	8.47 9.33 9.85	Air	
Wongcharee and Eiamsa-ard (2011)	Twisted tapes with alternate axes and triangular wing Twisted tapes with alternate axes and triangular wing Twisted tapes with alternate axes and triangular wing	Twist ratio-4, Wing cord ratio-0.1-0.3	5000 10000 20000	1.42 1.25 1.13	2.87 2.34 1.96	8.4 6.7 5.6	Water	
Eiamsa and Wongcharee (2013)	Counter double twisted tape Counter double twisted tape Counter double twisted tape	Twist ratio-3-5, Width-4mm	5000 10000 20000	2.02 1.76 1.50	4.7 4.05 3.45	12.7 12.5 12.5	Water	

(continued on next page)

Summary of important techniques and their TPF (continued)

Author	Modification	Parameter	Re	TPF	Nu/Nu ₀	f/f ₀	Fluid type	Image
Bhuiya et al. (2013b)	Triple twisted tape Triple twisted tape Triple twisted tape	Twist ratio-1.92-6.79	5000 10000 20000	1.44 1.40 1.33	2.85 2.51 2.2	7.5 5.83 4.6	Air	
Skullong et al. (2016a)	Staggered winglet perforated tape Staggered winglet perforated tape Staggered winglet perforated tape	Winglet inclination angle-30° Winglet blockage ratio-0.1-0.3 Winglet pitch ratio-0.5-1.5	5000 10000 20000	1.7 1.58 1.48	4.2 4.1 4.0	15 18 20.5	Air	
Yadav and Bhagoria (2014)	Triangular sectioned rib as roughness on absorber plate Triangular sectioned rib as roughness on absorber plate Triangular sectioned rib as roughness on absorber plate	Relative roughness pitch-7.14-35.71, Relative roughness height-0.021-0.042	5000 10000 20000	2.05 2.07 1.98	3.05 3.2 3.08	3.36 3.69 3.83	Air	
Gawande et al. (2015)	Right angle triangular rib as roughness on absorber surface Right angle triangular rib as roughness on absorber surface Right angle triangular rib as roughness on absorber surface	Relative roughness pitch-7.14-35.71, Relative roughness height-0.021-0.042	5000 10000 20000	1.99 2.01 1.98	3.07 2.96 2.93	3.68 3.23 3.38	Air	
Rao et al. (2015)	Surfaces with spherical and tear drop dimples Surfaces with spherical and tear drop dimples Surfaces with spherical and tear drop dimples	Depth to diameter ratio-0.2	5000 10000 20000	1.48 1.51 1.53	1.65 1.8 1.9	1.4 1.68 1.92	Air	
Salameh et al. (2016)	Perforated rib Perforated rib Perforated rib	Pitch ratio-10, Rib height to hydraulic diameter ratio-0.1	5000 10000 20000	2.8 2.45 1.9	4.8 4.4 3.6	5 5.9 6.8	Air	
Caliskan (2014)	Punched triangular vortex generator Punched triangular vortex generator Punched triangular vortex generator	Attack angle-15°-75° Winglet height to channel height ratio-0.6	5000 10000 20000	2.7 2.48 2.2	1.95 2.1 2.21	0.38 0.6 1	Air	
Tang et al. (2015)	Twisted tri-lobed inner tube Twisted tri-lobed inner tube	Twist pitch length-200	10000 20000	1.11 1.04	1.19 1.09	1.22 1.15	Water	

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o Surface extension

• Fins

Fins usually consist in folded/stamped steel sheet which are implemented in a heat exchanger by welding or brazing. They offer a high surface and a low pressure drop for a given volume due to their low frontal area and turbulence generation rate.

Fins height in heat exchanger are determined and limited using the fin efficiency. Indeed depending on the flux and the fluid temperature, fins have a maximum useful length beyond which the developed surface do not participate to the heat exchange anymore.

To define the maximum length x_{max} , a 1D approximation can be used. In this particular case the temperature of the fin can be calculate as the function of its length:

$$\theta(x) = (\theta_{base} - \theta_{fluid}) \exp(-mx) \text{ with } m \text{ the fin paramater } m^2 = \frac{hp}{ks}$$

Where h is the heat transfer coefficient, s the fin section, p the fin perimeter.

x_{max} is reached when θ is equal to θ_{fluid} , or the targeted temperature depending of the wanted efficiency.

This relation can also be used to approximate the best fin pin length.

Correlation for continuous fins can be found in the ANNEX-CORRELATION part.

Sometimes it is necessary to increase fins potential for heat exchange as if the fin surface modifications usually increase pressure drop. To do this fins can be deformed or perforated resulting in higher flow mixing.

Corrugated fin geometries for plate fin exchangers: (a) Plain triangle fin. (b) Plain rectangular fin. (c) Wavy fin. (d) Offset strip fin. (e) Multilouver fin. (f) Perforated fin. (Courtesy of Delphi Harrison Systems Lockport, NY)

- Offset Strip Fins (OSF) geometries

OSF geometries use a fin pitch with an offset to provide compact channels with high heat transfer area. The offset increase the turbulence of the flow with the detachment of the flow boundary layer.

This type of fin use one principle: the offset increase the number of leading edge where the heat transfer is higher. A second effect of the offset is the flow mixing which participate to improve the heat transfer effectiveness.

The flow behavior in offset strip geometries has been studied by Xi & al., 1991, they visualize the flow inside offset strip fin. It was observed that for $Re < 50$ the flow is laminar, no swirls appear in the fin wake. For Re between 50 and 100, instabilities appear in the wake of the primary rows of fins, this instabilities facilitate the formation of swirls and recirculation zone on the next rows.

For $Re > 100$, the mixing increases, swirls can be observed since first rows. After a few row, an important mixing occurs.

They found that increase the thickness of the fin can improve heat transfer. In effect, the modification of the thickness has impact on the physic phenomenon in the flow (cf. boundary layer in the convection part of physic principles).

Dejong & Jacobi, 1997, using an analogy between Sherwood and Nusselt number, showed that on each fins, the heat transfer reach a maximum close to the reattachment point.

Correlations for OSF geometries can be found in the ANNEX - CORRELATIONS part.

- Wavy fins

A common example of deformation is wavy fins. Wavy fins are fins deformed to fit a wave profile. Wave frequency, pitch and symmetry impact the heat transfer ability of the structure and should be adapted to the fluid characteristics and flow regime. Wavy fins induces flow direction variations to mix the fluid and increase the heat transfer. For a same length a wavy fin grants a greater heat transfer area compared to a classic longitudinal fin.

For a given Reynolds, increasing the fin pitch F_p lead to a better air mixing increasing heat transfer. However, it increases the pressure loss. (Junqi, Jiangping, Zhijiu, Yimin, & Wenfeng, 2006)

(Khaled, 2014) compared different types of wavy fins with different symmetric axis using finite difference method. It appears that F type wavy fins allow more heat transfer rate when short fins and large surface-wave frequency are necessary. The Type A fins are optimal when long fins and large

surface waves frequency are needed. Type E have the best heat transfer rate when long fins and small surface frequency are considered.

The wavy fins B & D have the same performance and have a larger fin efficiency than the others types of wavy fins.

The wavy frequency will be adapted depending on the pressure drop.

Correlations for wavy fins can be found in the ANNEX - CORRELATIONS part.

- Louvered fins

(Lyman, 2000) explained that louvers act as small flat plates aligned parallel to the flow. Louvered fins enhance heat transfer by providing multiple flat plate leading edges with their associated high values of heat-transfer coefficient (Kuppan). The louvers degree used to provide the best heat transfer depend

on the geometry and Reynolds number. The slit fins are rotated 20° to 60° relative to the airflow direction. Louvered fin strip length are usually 6-8mm.

The flow around louvered fins is similar to the OSF geometry flow, with boundary layer detachment and swirl. The angle of the louvered fin and the flow impact strongly on the heat exchanger performance. Depending on the flow and of the fin angle, the fluid flow will follow more or less the path imposed by louvers.

At low Reynolds, the streamlines will be parallels to the fins whereas for high Reynolds streamlines show lower offsets.

Compared to unlouvered surfaces, louvered fins can increase the heat transfer by a factor 2 or 3. The Reynolds number operating range for louvered fins is 100 up to 5000 depending on the geometry. The very effective heat transfer surfaces, the light weight and low pumping power for a given heat transfer make these technology very suitable for aerospace application.

(Ryu, Yook, & Lee) used the Suga-Aoki equation to find an optimal design of a corrugated louvered fin.

$$\left(\frac{F_p}{L_p}\right)_{opti} = \frac{2M + 1}{2} \tan\theta$$

To reach a better result they proposed an improved version of this equation adding Reynolds number (velocity term implementation) for $0 \leq Re_{L_p} \leq 500$. This correlation estimates the optimal model with a 3.08% error.

$$\left(\frac{F_p}{L_p}\right)_{opti} = \frac{(2M + 1)}{2} \left(1.9944 - \frac{5.0419}{\ln(Re_{L_p})} \right) \tan\theta$$

For louvered fin the hydraulic diameter is defined as $D_h = \frac{4 A_c L}{A_0}$ where A_c is the minimal passage section crossing the louvers and A_0 the total heat transfer area.

Several correlation give the Colburn and friction factor coefficient, they are available in the ANNEX-CORRELATION part.

- Fins with angle

The (SAFRAN, 2016) illustrates another example of non-continuous fin with non-usual fin shape using an angle to reduce pressure drop by 15%. The angle is defined to reduce flow recirculation behind the fin and to facilitate the 3D printing process of the fin (angle of 45°). The fin section can takes different shapes.

- Perforated fins

Perforated fins are used in the distributor sections of exchangers and also for boiling application. Perforations allow the flow to migrate laterally without the pressure drop penalty encountered with OSF configurations. The interruptions created by these perforations give a mild increase of the performance per unit area. Shah (1975) has shown that the heat transfer enhancement is modest, and occurs for Reynolds number greater than 2000. J.E Hesselgreaves in Compact Heat Exchangers, explains that a reasonable assumption to use it that for the same j factor than plain fin of same nominal dimensions, the friction factor is 20% higher.

- Pins

Pins are a particular case of fins, characterized in that the pins are short length fins of various shape (cylindrical, dropform, elliptical, etc). They are used in heat exchanger to expand the heat transfer area, and augment the heat transfer coefficient by increasing the flow mixing (turbulences generation).

(Yadav & Pandey, 2016) showed that under forced convection pins shapes have a significant impact on the heat transfer. It appears that elliptical and kite pin fins (cf. fin shape c & d) grant the best heat transfer performance.

(Bhenia, SoodPhakdee, & Watebe Copeland) numerically compared different arrangements and shapes for heat transfer enhancement in a forced laminar flow. They demonstrate that a staggered arrangement is preferable for heat transfer performance.

Comparing different shapes of pins in staggered arrangement they found that circular pins are more interesting than elliptical. This result seems at first glance in opposition to the study presented before. In fact, it is link to the constant parameters used for the test. The next study will explain it.

(Sahiti, 2006) thesis presented a performance comparison of different shapes done by numerical simulation. Sahiti used a specific criteria condition to ensure a true performance comparison. Sahiti distinguished two different setup to compare shape in staggered configuration. In FCC configuration, the following parameters are conserved: hydraulic diameter, same coverage ratio, same pin length. In SCC configuration, the conserved parameters are the blockage area, the distance between pins and pin length.

With these criteria, it can be observed that for a given surface and define coverage ratio, circular fin are the best solution for low Reynolds whereas at higher Reynolds the drop shape pins outperform circular one (similar to (Yadav & Pandey, 2016)).

On the other hand, with a fixed distance between pins, elliptical pins appear to be the best solution for all range of Reynolds (similar to (Bhenia, SoodPhakdee, & Watebe Copeland)).

Pin fin array Nusselt number as a function of Reynolds number for FCC, staggered arrangement.

Pin fin array Nusselt number as a function of Reynolds number for SCC, staggered arrangement.

In the case of heat exchanger, it seems more appropriate to choose pin fins depending of the desired effective conductivity, this match with a same coverage ratio. The choice between fins will consequently be done with FCC criteria depending of the Re number calculated in the heat exchanger flow path.

- Vortex Generators

Vortex generators (VG) are heat transfer enhancer used in combination with others extension surfaces devices like pins.

Unlike fins or pins, the first purpose of Longitudinal Vortex Generators (LVG) is not to increase heat exchange available surface, but to enhance heat transfer by modifying flow regime and condition. LVG increases heat transfer using two ways. They started up flow rotation that provide a flow mixing and more appropriate fluid temperature next to heat exchanger walls preventing temperature stratification in the flow path. The mixing created by rotation reduces boundary layer thickness and the turbulent flow can be directed to a specific zone, a thinner boundary layer increase heat transfer performance.

The efficiency of vortex generators depend both of vortex intensity and persistency and is highly dependent to Reynolds number. A common way to define the attack angle of vortex generators is done by observing temperature gradient and velocity streamlines angle. A diminution of this angle resulting in a better heat transfer performance.

Used in combination with pin and with a good arrangement, vortex generators and especially longitudinal vortex generators (LVGs) can increase the heat transfer and reduce some local pressure loss phenomenon. Indeed, LVGs like every flow obstacles create pressure drop, but with an appropriate arrangement around pins called “CFU approach” VG have a double effect on the flow. In CFU configuration, LVG do not only reduce boundary layer thickness by creating mixing but also delay the boundary layer separation around the front (picot upstream of LVGs) pin reducing dead zone size behind pins. The reduction of fluid recirculation induce a lower pressure drop. At the same time the convergent created by the winglet arrangement create a jet impingement on the next pin increasing heat transfer on its attack angle. (He & Zang)

An illustration of this phenomenon is given on the following figure:

It has been demonstrated that a staggered arrangement for pins with LVGs result in better heat transfer performance compared to inline arrangement. (Torii, Kawak, & Nishino, 2002)

Refs.	Geometry	Reynolds Number / (1000)	Overall Heat Transfer Enhancement*	Pressure Drop Penalty
[4]	Cube protuberances and delta-winglets	61	76% Cube 42% Counter-rot. 15% Co-rotating	Unknown
[5]	Full scale plate-fin heat exchanger	0.3-2.2	50%	20-30%
[6]	Flat plate with rectangular winglets	30-300	100%	Unknown
[7]	Rectangular channel with delta wing, delta winglets, and rectangular winglets.	1.36-2.27	20-60% (Delta wing)	Unknown
[8,9]	Rectangular channel with delta winglet pair			
	No hole under wing	0.5	34%	79%
	Hole under wing	0.5	10%	48%
[10,11]	Parallel plates with delta winglet pair	1.0-4.0	84%	Unknown
[12-14]	Rectangular channel:			
	Delta Wings	1.0-2.0	50%	45%
	Delta Winglet Pair	5.6	77%	Unknown
	Multiple pairs - inline	4.6	60%	145%
	Multiple pairs - staggered	4.6	52%	129%
[15-18]	Rectangular channel with one tube delta winglet pair downstream of tube.	5.0	20%	-10% (lower ΔP)
[19-21]	Three tube rows:			
	Inline round	0.6-3.0	55-65%	20-44%
	Staggered round		9%	3%
	Flat tubes		100%	100%

* Typical or maximum overall heat transfer enhancement unless otherwise noted.

[19-21] refers to a tube row arrangement, with delta-winglets in wake zone of tubes. (Gentry & Jacobi, 1995)

Patterned surfaces

Pattern surfaces consist in removal or addition of material to the heat exchange area to create small structures modifying the texture of surface. The pattern surface change flow behavior close to the wall, breaking the boundary layer to increase the heat transfer.

(Yenare, Kundlik, & Mali) studied oval and circular dimple patterned surface and compare them to a plain plate. They demonstrate that dimple increases the heat transfer compare to a plain plate. Moreover the oval dimple plate grants a better heat transfer enhancement than the circular and plain plate. However the friction factor is higher with oval dimple plate due to more swirl flow.

Nusselt number enhancement being higher than friction factor enhancement it appears that circular or oval dimple plate use is justified for a laminar flow.

(Gazi I., Mounir ., & Philip M., 2001) studied the impact of dimples and protrusions on walls, and the interaction of these structures when they are on opposite walls. They explain that the dimples and protrusions have several advantages allowing a high heat transfer augmentation for a low pressure drop increase, an easy manufacturing and do not increase significantly the structure weight. Their study cites several previous studies showing that this type of structure can increase the heat transfer up to 150%, in some cases the heat transfer enhancement can reach up to 2.5 times the smooth surface rate value whereas the pressure drop created is half of the value of conventional turbulators.

Cited documents explain that the heat transfer and pressure loss has a low dependency to Re and channel height.

Testing several arrangements, (Gazi I., Mounir ., & Philip M., 2001) show that in the case of opposite walls protrusion a better heat transfer enhancement is obtained in the case of misaligned protrusions and dimples. Dimples and protrusions arrangement have a higher Reynolds dependency than dimple-smooth surface arrangement. From this study they conclude that using protrusions is advantageous only when a relatively low pressure drop and friction factor magnitude is not needed.

(Hwang, Kwon, & Cho) observed the heat transfer coefficients and friction factors on dimple-protrusion geometries at different scales. Locally, it appears that the high heat transfer regions appear on the front part of protrusion and on the rear part of dimple. For a double-side dimple-protrusion patterned wall, interaction of coherent vortices enhances highly the heat transfer coefficient. Taking average values, the Nusselt ratio is higher in the lower Reynolds numbers due to stronger vortices. Patterned surface is efficient at low Re number, the induced vortices increasing the heat transfer. At higher Re , the performance factor decreases sharply.

(Moon, O'Connell, & Sharma) studied experimentally the impact of a one-side convex patterned surface in a rectangular channel. They observed that the heat transfer enhancement is significantly higher in the region immediately upstream of convexities whereas the heat transfer enhancement is lowest in the regions beneath and immediately downstream of convexities. The heat transfer enhancement difference between different clearance gaps is small except when the ratio between clearance gap under concavities and convexity diameter is equal to 0, in this case the rectangular channel with a smooth wall on one side and convexities on the other thermally performed better for $Re < 20\,000$.

(Zheng, Peng, Shan, Liu, & Liu, 2015) studied numerically the effect of rib on heat transfer in a tube heat exchanger. Two types of ribs were used P-type ribs and V-type ribs.

Structure and configurations of the ribbed tube: (a) V-type; (b) P-type.

They concluded that rib arrangements have perceptible effects on the flow. The V-type shape induced multiple vortices when the P type shape create a single vortex.

Tangential velocity vectors and streamlines in the outlet of the test section of the P-type ribbed tube for $Re = 10,170$: (a) tangential velocity vectors; (b) streamlines.

Tangential velocity vectors and streamlines in the outlet of the test section of the V-type ribbed tube for $Re = 10,170$: (a) tangential velocity vectors; (b) streamlines.

It appears that the V-type ribbed tubes give a higher heat transfer with a 57-67% higher Nusselt than the P type ribbed tube respectively. However the friction factor is also 86-94% higher for the V-type geometry compared to P type. The V-type shape with its multiple vortex is a more effective pattern for heat transfer compared to the single vortex induced by P-type ribbed tube.

(Eiamsa-ard & Changcharoen, 2011) compared numerically several ribs shape in channels with airflow (Re range 10,000 to 30,000). A k-omega SST turbulent model is used. Nusselt number, the friction factor and a thermal enhancement factor are used to compare the different ribbed structures.

The thermal enhancement factor is defined as $TEF = \frac{Nu}{\left(\frac{f}{f_{smooth}}\right)^{1/3}}$

1 Schematic of two-dimensional rib-roughness channel and configuration of various-shaped ribs.

Effect of the rib shape on thermal enhancement factor.

The results indicate the concave-concave rib shape give the highest Nusselt and friction factor, by suppressing flow separation bubble in the corner of the rig and creating a large recirculation zone with high turbulence intensity. However it is efficient only if pressure drop and pumping power are not a major concern. The convex-concave shape provides the lowest friction factor but a moderate Nusselt number. Due to its low friction factor, the convex concave surface offers the highest thermal enhancement factor (TEF=1.19 at Re=10,000).

Cellular metals

- Lattices structures

Lattices structures are architecturally structured material that formed a mesh and are compounded of the repetition of a geometric element periodically in space. The pattern can be deformed as a function of its position. This type of structures is characterized by a high porosity usually over 90%. The meshes are qualified of conformal when the mesh follow a part curve, and non-conformal when the mesh doesn't follow part curve. Lattices structures are well-known for their good ratio performance/weight. (Structure lattice). Lattices can take several shapes, a few of them can be seen in the pictures below:

Lattices structures allow high specific surfaces with common specific surfaces of $600\text{m}^2/\text{m}^3$ for a 5mm side unit. They present a good compromise between the heat transfer and the induced pressure drop. (Structures lattices par voie de fonderie)

(Son, Weibel, Kumaresan, & Garimella) explained that structured porous materials have a great potential as extended surfaces in heat exchange applications that also need load-bearing capability. Lattices frame present a high strength to weight ratio. In this study, tetrahedral lattices are studied in a laminar flow regime (Re range from 150 to 1000) with five samples of different porosities (75 up to 98%). The behavior of Nusselt and friction factors depending of porosity and flow regime are described. The graphics below show the important impact of the porosity on friction factor and heat transfer rate.

It is also possible to observed the area goodness factor which illustrate the ratio between heat transfer ability and pressure drop. It appears that the ratio stay relatively stable when Re increase, meaning that

the heat transfer and the pressure drop increase with a similar rate. It is observable that the ratio j/f slightly decreases with the porosity drop.

(Kumar, Manogharan, & Cormier) study the effect of lattices orientation of hexagonal periodic cellular structures on heat transfer and pressure drop. A finite element method was used. It was found the same structure can grant different performance in term of pressure drop and heat transfer depending on its orientation. It induces that the orientation of a cellular structure is a significant parameter which may be taken into account to extract the greatest performance depending on the application.

Table 1 Data for different orientation of Hexagonal periodic cellular structure (α, β, γ is the angle in x, y and z plane respectively)

Trial Num	Orientation (α, β, γ)	Avg. Vel. ($m s^{-1}$)	Outlet Temp. ($^{\circ}C$)	Temp Increase ($^{\circ}C$)	Static Press. (Pa)	Press. Drop (Pa)	Heat Flux ($W m^{-2}$)	Nusselt Number	Reynolds Number	Friction Factor
1	(0,0,0)	5.275	35.254	15.254	101350	25	3.277	3.508	1558.575	0.175
2	(30,0,0)	5.341	32.987	12.787	101355	30	2.763	2.962	1324.802	0.172
3	(45,0,0)	5.349	37.685	17.485	101355	30	4.987	3.404	1155.105	0.149
4	(0,45,0)	5.382	40.121	19.921	101344	19	5.846	3.875	1285.952	0.103
5	(0,30,0)	5.363	38.359	18.159	101352	27	5.650	5.198	1621.539	0.187
6	(30,30,0)	5.382	37.488	17.288	101356	31	6.711	4.952	1242.449	0.163
7	(30,45,0)	5.152	39.288	19.088	101360	35	6.357	3.806	1065.308	0.179
8	(45,30,0)	5.341	36.169	15.969	101355	30	5.987	4.168	1074.468	0.139
9	(45,45,0)	5.417	37.849	17.649	101361	36	5.689	3.083	937.486	0.140
10	(45,45,45)	5.321	35.786	15.586	101354	29	5.773	4.072	1058.621	0.134
11	(45,45,30)	5.319	35.782	15.582	101354	29	5.687	3.394	894.947	0.113
12	(45,30,30)	5.346	36.387	16.187	101356	31	5.471	3.249	930.063	0.124
13	(30,30,30)	5.339	35.869	15.669	101357	32	5.677	3.869	1031.584	0.143
14	(30,45,30)	5.3414	36.327	16.127	101355	30	5.184	3.308	994.645	0.129
15	(45,30,45)	5.4312	37.861	17.661	101363	38	5.431	2.968	948.519	0.148

The two following graphs and the above table show that if the major concern is the heat transfer whereas the pressure drop is considered as a minor one, the orientation 5 will grant the best performance. However if the pressure drop is the major concern the 4th orientation will grant the lower pressure drop without being the less efficient in term of heat transfer efficiency.

Friction factor versus lattice orientation

Nusselt number versus lattice orientation

(Yan, Zhang, & Lu, 2015) studied single phase (air) forced convective heat transfer of a new lightweight X type lattices and compare its performance with other lattices types. Their X type lattices are produced with a metal sheet which is pressed, allowing the use of a traditional fabrication process.

Sandwich panels with (a) tetrahedral core (also called "lattice-frame material" (LFM)), (b) pyramidal core, (c) Kagome core and (d) wire-woven bulk Kagome (WBK) core.

They observed that with an identical conductivity of the material, and with a fixed porosity, a significant heat transfer enhancement (up to 170% and 100%) can be reached by the X type lattice compared to lattice frame material (LFM) or Kagome respectively.

The form of the lattice of X type grants a highly tortuous spiral primary flow and 3 types of secondary flows (2 cross flow and 1 vortex pair). This flow mixing allow up to 90% and 20% higher area averaged Nusselt number than for LFM. Moreover higher core surface area density is obtained with X type lattices for a given porosity. However the complex flow mixing between global primary flow and secondary flow increase the pressure drop penalties of 3.2 to 3.6 times compared to LFM and Kagome respectively.

For a fixed pumping power, higher heat transfer and thermal efficiency are reached compared to the two others studied structures.

The European Patent Office - EP 2775244 B1, entitled Micro-lattice cross-flow heat exchangers for aircraft, illustrate the use of lattices structure for an aircraft precooler. This heat exchanger is a part of the cabin cooling system and cool the air coming from the aircraft engine. The heat exchanger first fluid path go through hollow X type lattices and the second fluid path flow around lattices. The lattices structures are subject to flexion and pressure load.

- Woven textile

(Lu, Xu, & Wen) explained that metal textile are three-dimensional analogue of metallic screen meshes which have already been extensively used in fields such as aerospace, air conditioning system, etc. They are characterized by a large values of area density and are especially effective to dissipate heat in a limited design space. The construction of woven screens may be design to ensure multiple tasks combining for example load support and heat dissipation. Layers of woven screens are bonded together to build woven textile structures. Woven textiles fabrication employ brazing and soldering.

The following pictures show different textile use in heat exchangers:

The following table regroup several samples and allow to observe common porosity and surface area which can be found on heat exchanger:

Test sample	Material	Wire diameter/mm	Aperture/mm	Porosity	Surface area density/(m ² /m ³)	Open area ratio
S-1 & D-1	Copper	0.8	2.36	0.795	994	0.557,7
S-2 & D-2	Copper	1.0	2.13	0.737	1,004	0.463,1
S-3 & D-3	Copper	1.2	1.98	0.683	988	0.387,6
S-4 & D-4	Copper	0.8	1.30	0.680	1,496	0.383,2
S-6 & D-5	Stainless steel	0.9	2.275	0.769	989	0.513,4
S-7 & D-6	Stainless steel	0.56	1.98	0.822	1,237	0.607,6
S-8 & D-7	Stainless steel	0.56	1.557	0.785	1,470	0.540,9

Correlations to calculate the properties of woven textile depending on wire parameter and configuration are available in the ANNEX-CORRELATION part.

(Tian, Lu, & al., 2006) studied a cross flow heat exchange using both air and water as coolant. Samples were built as sandwich panels with textile cores bonded to solid faces. The overall pressure drop and heat transfer performance of copper and stainless steel textile based lattices structures were investigated. They observed that at high Reynolds numbers the friction factor based on unit pore size depends mainly of the open ratio area. Heat transfer depends on conduction through solid ligaments and forced convection applied to the coolant. It was found that the performance of diamond oriented structures was superior to square oriented structures for a similar porosity and surface area density.

For a fixed Reynolds number, two key parameters control heat transfer: porosity and surface area density. At a given porosity, the heat transfer increases with the increase of surface area density, however for a fix surface area density an optimal porosity can be found to reach the maximum heat dissipation rate. Thermally the textile structures perform as well as stochastic open-cells metal foams due to high surface area density, however the needed pumping power is lower with textile structures.

iii) Surfaces comparison

The goodness factor comparison allows to compare two different surfaces. The following method compares the thermal performance of two surfaces on a friction power basis. The heat transfer coefficient noted α and the friction power P are written as functions of f , j , Re and D_h .

$$\alpha = C_p \eta \Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{j R_{e D_h}}{D_h}$$

$$\frac{P}{A} = \frac{\eta^3}{2\rho^2} \frac{f R_{e D_h}^3}{D_h^3}$$

The thermal performance of two surfaces can be compared by plotting $j R_{e D_h} D_h$ versus $f (R_{e D_h} / D_h^3)$ which compare the transfer coefficient for equal friction power per unit of surface area and for an equal thermal effectiveness. (Goodness factor comparisons)

Colburn and friction factors can be used for a surface comparison purposes, however it can be more interesting to combine pressure drop and thermal comparison. (Hesselgreaves, Law, & Reay, 2016) proposed a comparison parameter, called “operating parameter” P_0 , obtained with the derived form of the core mass velocity equation (London 1983), this derived form is used to reach the following relationships:

$$\frac{A_{c,1}}{A_{c,2}} = \left[\frac{f_1 j_2}{f_2 j_1} \right]^{0.5} = \left(\frac{j_2}{f_2} \right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{f_1}{j_1} \right)^{0.5}$$

The form of this equation describe j/f ratio as the flow area goodness factor (London, 1964).

The cross sectional area for a side, $C_{s,1}$ is dependent of A_c and of the porosity σ .

$$\frac{C_{s,1}}{C_{s,2}} = \frac{A_{c,1} \sigma_2}{A_{c,2} \sigma_1} = \frac{\left(\frac{j_2}{f_2} \right)^{1/2} \sigma_2}{\left(\frac{j_1}{f_1} \right)^{1/2} \sigma_1}$$

Volume of each side of the heat exchanger is also added by $V=C_s L$ and the material content is given by $V_m = V(1 - \sigma)$:

$$\frac{V_{m_1}}{V_{m_2}} = \frac{V_1(1 - \sigma_1)}{V_2(1 - \sigma_2)} = \frac{\left(\frac{j_2}{f_2} \right)^{1/2} d_{h_1} \sigma_2 (1 - \sigma_1)}{\left(\frac{j_1}{f_1} \right)^{1/2} d_{h_2} \sigma_1 (1 - \sigma_2)}$$

A ratio of operating Reynolds number with which j is a strong function and j/f a weak function for most surfaces can be used as a comparison tool. The ratio of Reynolds number for both surfaces can be re-expressed as a criterion for equivalence of operating points and can result in an alternative form of the mass velocity equation. The operating parameter P_0 can be extract from this law.

$$\frac{Re_1}{d_{h_1} \left(\frac{j}{f} \right)_1^{1/2}} = \frac{Re_2}{d_{h_2} \left(\frac{j}{f} \right)_2^{1/2}} \rightarrow \frac{Re}{d_h \left(\frac{j}{f} \right)^{1/2}} = \frac{1}{\eta} \left(\frac{2\rho\Delta P}{P_r^3 N} \right)^{1/2} = P_0$$

With this parameter (Hesselgreaves, Law, & Reay, 2016) extracted the following graphical comparison:

- Face area parameter for a selection of surfaces.

The face parameter area reflects the relatively low spread arising from the low variation of f/j .

- Volume parameter for a selection of surfaces.

The volume parameter P_v , illustrate the advantage of low hydraulic diameter, especially at low operating parameter. Of note is the clear winner of the triangular duct surface, which has a linear relationship because of the fully developed laminar flow.

- Volume parameter for a selection of surfaces for $D_h=1.5\text{mm}$

When the surfaces are compared at a 1.5mm hydraulic diameter it appears the lowest performers (highest volume) are now the continuous duct surfaces, which are the most compact in tested form. The surfaces enabling enhancement by interruption of the boundary layer are grouped together with offset strip fin showing the highest performance. The reason being that OSF has the shortest restart length and a fin enough thin to avoid a dominating form drag. The graphic makes clear that for compactness solution boundary layer interruption by restart (like with OSF) or by secondary flow (wavy fin, dimpled surface) are the most appropriate.

Another way to compare structures is to study directly the friction factor and Nusselt as a function of the Reynolds number.

The following graphics illustrate the difference of behavior and allow to categorize the structures depending on the flow regime. For example it appears packed bed are efficient for heat transfer but induce high friction factor for all regime, limiting their use to low Reynolds applications when pressure drop is not a priority. At the opposite side, empty channel allow low friction factor but slight heat transfer ability, they will be appropriate when pressure drop is a major concern and for high Reynolds applications. Between them, foams also called lattices structures, appear as an intermediary solution.

Friction factor and heat transfer (behind Nusselt number) can be combined on one graph by plotting $Nu/f^{1/3}$ as a function of Reynolds rather than friction and Nu factor separately.

(Gugulothu) purposed a table for a fast comparison of different inserts dedicated to heat transfer enhancement which have been studied by scientists in the literature.

S. No	Author	Publication Year (Country)	Augmentation	Reynolds Number	Nusselt Number	Friction Factor	Enhancement of heat transfer	Pressure Drop	
1	Smith Eiamsaard and Pongjet Promvongse	2005 (Thailand)	Helical tapes insert with rod	2300 to 8800	145%		5% to 10% (without rod)	30% (without rod)	
			Helical tapes insert without rod		165%				
			Helical tapes insert without rod	s=0.5	5%		145%	45%	
				s=1.0	10%		140%	52%	
				s=1.5	17%		133%	58%	
				s=2.0	21%		129%	62%	
			Full length helical tape with rod		160%				
Full length helical tape without rod	150%								
Regularly spaced helical tape	145%								
2	Smith Eiamsaard et al	2006 (Thailand)	Full length twisted tape with twist ratio	y=6	179%				
				y=8	143%				
			Twisted tape with free space length	s=0.0	179%				15%
				s=1.0	160%				
				s=2.0	142%				
s=3.0	121%	39%							
				81%					

3	Pongjet Promvongse and Smith Eiamsaard	2007 (Thailand)	Converging nozzle	8000 to 18,000	236%		
			Diverging nozzle		344%		
			Diverging nozzle	PR=2.0	310%-360%		10-20%
				PR=4.0	296%	25%	5-13%
			PR=7.0	240%	60%	3-9%	
4	Smith Eiamsaard et al	2007 (Thailand)	Helical Tape with core rod	2000 to 12,000	230%	50% (with core rod)	25% to 60% (with core rod)
			Helical Tape without core rod		340%	4.9 times	
5	Smith Eiamsaard et al	2008 (Thailand)	Backward Louvered Strip Inserts	6000 to 42,000	263%	233%	1.17 to 1.98
			Forward Louvered Strip Inserts		284%	413%	1.11 to 1.8
			Backward Louvered Strip Inserts	$\theta=15^\circ$		1.55 times	1.33 times
				$\theta=25^\circ$		2.0 times	1.97 times
				$\theta=30^\circ$		2.33 times	2.64 times
			Forward Louvered Strip Inserts	$\theta=15^\circ$		2.8 times	1.5 times
$\theta=25^\circ$		3.25 times		2.19 times			
$\theta=30^\circ$		4.13 times		2.84 times			
6	Ibrahim EZ	2011 (Egypt)	Helical screw tape inserts	5.7×10^2 to 1.31×10^3	3.2%	2.8%	
7	Shabanian S R et al	2011 (Iran)	Butterfly twisted tape	$\alpha=45^\circ$		15.5 times	
				$\alpha=90^\circ$		18.3 times	
				$\alpha=135^\circ$		11.5 times	
			Classic twisted tape	Y=1.76		6.38	
				Y=2.35		5.48	
				Y=2.94		4.66	
			Jagged twisted tape	Y=3.53		3.84	
				Y=1.76		10.65%	
				Y=2.35		20.57%	
				Y=2.94		30.19%	
			Y=3.53		34.41%		
8	Mohammed HA et al	2013 (Malaysia)	Forward louvered strip	10,000 to 50,000	4.1 times		350% to 400%
			Back word louvered strip				367% to 411%
9	Naga Sarada S et al	2013 (India)	Louvered Square leaf insert 30° backward		32.72%	80.39%	Ratio=0.79
			Louvered Square leaf insert 60° backward		81.31%	143.4%	Ratio=1.34
			Louvered Square leaf insert 90° backward		128.39%	441.3%	Ratio=1.30
			Louvered Square leaf insert 30° forward		30.03%	116.4%	Ratio=1.02
			Louvered Square leaf insert 60° forward		121%	369.1%	Ratio=1.32
10	Naga Sarada S	2014 (India)	Cylindrical pin	7000 to 15,000		280.3%	55.5% 1.99 times

	et al		Curved leaf			17.5%	49.8%	
			Triangular insert			660.7%	1.42 times	
11	Naga Sarada S et al	2014 (India)	Rectangular bar with Diverging conical strip	8000 to 15,000		54.45% Ratio=1.54	31.32% Ratio=1.66	1.34
			Rectangular bar with Converging conical strip			68.53% Ratio=1.68	204.29% Ratio=3.04	1.16
			Rectangular bar with Alternate Converging, Diverging conical strips			58.72% Ratio=1.58	66.03% Ratio=1.31	1.40
12	Naga Sarada S et al	2014 (India)	Rectangular bar with Diverging conical strip	8000 to 19000		54.45% Ratio=1.54	31.32% Ratio=1.31	1.40
			Rectangular bar with Converging conical strip			68.53% Ratio=1.68	204.29% Ratio=3.04	1.16
			Rectangular bar with Alternate Converging, Diverging conical strips			58.72% Ratio=1.58	66.03% Ratio=1.66	1.34
			Rectangular bar with holes and Diverging conical strip			64.46% Ratio=1.64	246.18% Ratio=3.47	1.08
			Rectangular bar with holes and Converging conical strip			72.77% Ratio=1.72	322.92% Ratio=4.22	1.06
			Rectangular bar with hole and Alternate Converging, Diverging conical strips			77.92% Ratio=1.77	279.45% Ratio=3.79	1.14
13	Ahmed M.A	2015 (Iraq)	Straight Channel	Nanofluid: SiO ₂ 400 to 4000				
			Sinusoidal Channel					7.1%
			Trapezoidal Channel					7.4%

From these publications, it appears that various type of intensifications structures exist with different advantages and application range. Plains fins offer a high heat transfer surface for a low flow blockage resulting in a low pressure drop making them particularly adapted when pressure drop is the major concern. In the case of a laminar flow or low turbulence flow, the plain fins can be replaced by various other structures to enhance the heat transfer with turbulence intensification. This intensification is obtained by two different methods: the rupture of the boundary layer by interruption, or by generating secondary flow, with the possibility to combine the two methods. If fins type structures are appropriate when pressure drop is a major concern, lattices and wire type structures offer a solution for intermediary flow conditions. They bring a mechanical support as a secondary function of the heat transfer intensification.

Patterned surface and vortex generators appear clearly to be efficient only for laminar flow when their turbulence intensification role develop its full potential. This reduces significantly their field of application.

The use of grooved surface in combination with fin/tube type geometry should be explore for enhancing heat transfer without increasing significantly pressure loss.

iv) *Roughness impact on heat exchange*

The surface roughness can be induced by the production process (for example additive manufacturing), or be artificially created from a smooth surface. Roughness impact on heat exchange and pressure drop cannot be neglected in all cases. The following articles investigate its impact under different flow conditions.

Forced air heat transfer enhancement has been extensively explored and many augmentation techniques have been already proposed, including plane fins, pin fins, dimpled surfaces, surfaces with arrays of protrusions, metal foams, and artificial surface roughness. The artificial surface roughness means here any surface patterning with enough regularity and purposely designed in order to enhance heat transfer. For instance, in such a category, we may include ribs (Tanda, 2004) and, more recently, (shark-skin-like) scale roughened surfaces (Chang et al. 2008). The resulting heat transfer enhancement of the scale roughened surface is surprisingly good compared to rib roughened and dimpled surfaces (Zhou et al. 2012). This proves that there is still room for improving the optimal design of artificial surface roughness.

(Kandlikar, Joshi, & Tian, 2001) studied effect of channel roughness on heat transfer and pressure drop using water at low Reynolds number inside tubes. They observed that heat transfer and pressure drop show a dependence to roughness only for a diameter under 0.62 mm. Tubes with diameter above 1.067 with e/d (grain size over diameter ratio) equal or lower to 0.3 may be considered as smooth tubes.

(Mikielewicz & Wajs, 2012) compared a commercial plate heat exchanger (water flow) to the same exchanger but with a modified heat transfer surface (higher roughness). The initial roughness was $Ra=0.46\text{mm}$ and $Rz=3.34\text{mm}$ and the modified surface had a $Ra=2.8\text{mm}$ roughness with $Rz=15.9\text{mm}$. The same flow and thermal conditions were used in both cases. They observed that a larger roughness of the heat transfer surface leads to an increase of the heat transfer coefficient of the cooling water side by 30 to 35% and simultaneously increases the flow resistance up to 30%. On the heating water side, the heat transfer coefficient was increased by 25% for a flow resistance increased by 22%.

(Kuppan) explained that for a turbulent flow in a tube a low-velocity flow region known as the laminar sublayer is located immediately adjacent to the wall. Most of the thermal resistance occurs in this low-velocity region. Any roughness that disturbs the laminar sublayer enhances the heat transfer. For fully developed flow in a smooth tube, the dimensionless laminar sublayer thickness is given by:

$$y^* = \frac{y\sqrt{Gc\tau/\rho}}{\nu} = 5$$

Using the shear stress τ for a smooth tube the ratio of laminar sublayer thickness y to tube diameter d is given by:

$$\frac{y}{d} = 25Re^{-0.875}$$

Knowing the laminar sublayer thickness y it is possible to know if the roughness will have an impact on it.

Surface roughness heat transfer enhancement is effective in turbulent flow when it is difficult to increase the heat transfer without increasing too much the pressure drop. For laminar flow applications, small-scale surface is not effective, and twisted tape inserts or internally finned tubes are preferable.

(Maradiya, Vahder, & Agarwal, 2017) review illustrated that in large Prandtl number flow, roughness performs better in heat enhancement than some inserts. The maximum heat transfer occurs for a roughness height of three times the viscous sublayer thickness. An artificial corrugated rough surface can be used to improve significantly the heat transfer. The roughness breaks and destabilizes the thermal boundary layer.

(Kirsh & Thole) studied on additive manufactured wavy microchannel bring to light that the roughness effects can strongly modify the flow behavior observed by simulation.

(Ventola L., 2014) used Additive Manufacturing (direct metal laser sintering) to fabricate flat and finned surfaces with different surface roughness and analyzed them for heat transfer performance.

Experiments were conducted and convective heat transfer data was reported in terms of Nusselt number. Model of Turbulent flow over the rough surface was developed and compared with experimental results. For flat rough surfaces, a peak of convective heat transfer enhancement of 73% (63% on average) was observed, while, for rough (single) finned surfaces, a peak enhancement of 40% (35% on average) was observed. According to these authors, the observed heat transfer enhancement values could not be explained by the increases of the effective roughness surface area, which was found to be always much smaller. Even though it is known to be a quite old problem, there is no universally accepted theory that can accurately describe turbulent flows in the presence of complex multi-scale roughness (Jiménez, 2004). Based on the research work of (Gioia G., 2006), authors elaborated a novel model which was found to be in excellent agreement with the experimental data. Such a finding looks promising towards a systematic theory of turbulent flows over rough walls, particularly with regards to convective heat transfer (Ventola L., 2014).

(Ventola L., 2014) Following the idea by (Gioia G., 2006), proposed that heat transfer close to the wall is dominated by eddies with size depending on the roughness dimensions and the viscous (Kolmogórov) length scale.

Turbulent flows over rough walls represent a long-standing problem (since 1930s, at the latest), although a lot of work has been already carried out. However, looking at the published literature, the main conclusion is that turbulent structure close to rough walls is far from being fully understood (Jiménez, 2004). Even in classical textbooks (Schlichting, 2000), it was already pointed out that the number of parameters describing roughness is extraordinarily large owing to the great diversity of geometric forms. It has been suggested that the details of the rough wall may influence the flow across the whole boundary layer, but some care must be taken to sort those claims and their significance in truly understanding wall turbulence (Jiménez, 2004). Modern theories do not provide much more than taxonomic classification into wide categories (Jiménez, 2004), i.e. k-roughness and d-roughness, depending on the existence of significant stagnation on the rough surface. Even when some quantitative parameters seem to be relevant for characterizing wall roughness, as in the case of the equivalent grain size of the Nikuradse's sand (Schlichting, 2000), typically, it is only a convenient way of characterizing the drag increment due to the roughness and, hence, its effects on turbulent flows. In some scientific communities, a few parameters which are conceptually very different, e.g. frontal solidity and plane solidity, are used interchangeably. Many of the suggested correlations are restricted to surfaces with simple geometry, and cannot easily cope with irregular surfaces (Jiménez, 2004). In general, extensive experimental work is currently ongoing to visualize the actual vortices under turbulent boundary layers at rough walls. Only recently, a pioneering paper by (Gioia G., 2006) succeeded in explaining the classical Nikuradse's experiment results and in recovering the empirical scaling laws of Blasius and Strickler (on the basis of another classical result, namely the

phenomenological theory of Kolmogórov). The basic idea was to estimate the size of the eddies that dominate the momentum transfer close to the wall by a combination of the size of the roughness elements and the viscous length scale. We found this quite enlightening, and thus decided to further extend the idea of Gioia et al. (focusing though on convective heat transfer), in order to explain the previous experimental data.

The surface roughness has a significant impact on both heat transfer and pressure loss. Surface roughness appears to be more desirable in the case of high Reynolds application when the use of heat transfer intensifications structures begin to impact significantly the pressure. To benefit of this roughness it will be necessary to ensure it is sized properly depending on the laminar sublayer thickness.

4.8 Flow maldistribution & Header Design

Several studies have numerically or theoretically compared different shapes and design of flow header to reduce flow maldistribution. Depending on its seriousness, the maldistribution impacts the heat transfer capacity, operating control and could possibly induce mechanical damage. In some cases the maldistribution have only a slight effect on the heat exchanger performance, while in other cases it can result in a significant loss in performance. (Mueller & Chiou, 2007).

i) Global view of flow maldistribution

Geometric flow maldistribution results of a non-ideal design. (Shah & Sekulic) classified flow non-uniformities of this type into three groups: gross flow maldistribution (inlet face of the heat exchanger), passage to passage flow maldistribution (non-uniform flow in neighboring flow passages), manifold-induced flow maldistribution due to inlet outlet header design.

Gross flow maldistribution is a non-uniform flow occurring at the macroscopic level due to a poor header design or a blockage of some flow passages during manufacturing. This class of flow maldistribution causes a significant increase in the exchanger pressure drop and some reduction in heat transfer rate.

Passage to passage flow maldistribution has a high susceptible occurrence in compact heat exchangers with uninterrupted flow passages, principally because neighboring passages are geometrically never identical, due to imperfect manufacturing processes. The different size and shape passages exhibit different flow resistances resulting in a non-uniform flow in the heat exchanger core, the flow seeks a path of least resistance. This phenomenon usually leads to a slight reduction of pressure drop while the heat transfer drop can be significant. The influence is particularly important at low Reynolds. Fouling or brazing can increase this flow maldistribution.

Manifold-induced maldistribution was not detailed by (Shah & Sekulic) and will be treated by the Header design and maldistribution part.

(Nielsen, Engelbrecht, Christensen, Jensen, Smith, & Bahl) study the effect of the maldistribution on the performance of microchannel parallel plate heat exchanger. The study presents a numerical method to quantify the heat transfer degradation associated with non-uniform flow channels thickness. Simulation brought to light that large decreases in heat transfer performance can occur in case of non-uniform flow channels spacing. The model was validated by a flat plate heat exchanger.

ii) Header design and maldistribution

A good header design reduces flow maldistribution in heat exchangers, the following articles will detail and compare different headers solutions to provide an optimal header design and reduce pressure drop and maldistribution.

(Kalidasan & Ravikumar) used CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamic) to lead a numerical comparison of circular, square, rectangular and triangular shape header for a compact heat exchanger using a nine parallels tubes configuration. A numerical analysis was done on flow uniformity for several Reynolds, varying different parameters such as header cross section, area ratio and flow rate. It was conclude that among the 4 shapes, the flow maldistribution was the highest for a circular cross sectional header and the lowest for a triangular cross sectional header. In all configuration increasing the flow rate induce an increase flow maldistribution.

(Wang, Yang, Tsai, & Chen, 2011) studied different inlet header inserts to optimize the flow distribution in a parallel flow heat exchanger.

Among the different inserts we can distinguish trapezoidal insert, multistep, inclined and baffle tubes.

It appears that between all inserts the most efficient was the baffle tube (picture in bottom right). The baffle tube uses tubes of variable diameter to adapt flow distribution.

The first 2 tubes have decreasing diameter, next tubes have the same lower diameter. The tubes with higher flow resistance guide more flow to the first and second tube. This organization grants a homogenous average flow ratio for all tubes. No vortex is generated at the inlet header with this baffle tube design. The pressure drop increase is evaluated as insignificant compared to the other headers.

(Dharaiya, Radhakrishnan, & Kandlikar) compared tapered header to a circular header. Authors found that the tapered header efficiently reduces maldistribution phenomenon. The decreasing pressure profile generated by the tapered header improves the flow distribution which becomes more uniform.

: Maldistribution plot for straight Z-type flow in circular cross-section header ($D_H = 0.7\text{mm}$).

: Maldistribution plot for straight flow in a tapered cross-section header ($D_H = 0.7\text{mm}$).

(K. Shah & Sekulic) proposed theoretical profile for an oblique header depending on the flow configuration (counter flow headers, parallel flow headers and free discharge headers). They indicate that the best option to reduce pressure drop is the counter flow header.

Oblique-flow headers: (a) parallelflow; (b) counterflow; (c) free discharge header. (From London et al., 1966.)

Theoretical Shape, Pressure Profiles, and Pressure Drops of Oblique-Flow Headers

Header Type	Theoretical Model ^a	Pressure Drop
Paralleflow header	Inlet header pressure $\frac{p_i - p(X^*)}{H_i} = \frac{\pi^2}{4} (X^*)^2 \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_o} \left(\frac{z_i}{y_o}\right)^2$	Inlet: $\frac{\Delta p_i}{H_i} = 1 + \frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{H_o}{H_i}$
	Inlet header profile ^b $\frac{z}{y_o} = \frac{1 - X^*}{\left[\frac{\pi^2}{4} (\rho_i/\rho_o) (X^*)^2 + (y_o/z_i)^2\right]^{1/2}}$	Outlet: $\frac{\Delta p_o}{H_i} = 0.645 \frac{H_o}{H_i}$
Counterflow header ^c	Inlet header pressure $\frac{p(X^*) - p_i}{H_i} = \frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_o} \frac{z_i}{y_o} [1 - (1 - X^*)^2]$	Total: $\frac{\Delta p_i}{H_i} = 1 + 1.467 \frac{H_o}{H_i}$
	Inlet header profile ^b $\frac{z}{y_o} = \frac{1 - X^*}{\left\{ (y_o/z_i)^2 - \frac{\pi^2}{4} (\rho_i/\rho_o) [1 - (1 - X^*)^2] \right\}^{1/2}}$	Inlet: $\frac{\Delta p_i}{H_i} = \frac{1}{3}$
Free discharge header	Inlet header profile $\frac{z}{z_i} = 1 - X^*$	Outlet ^d : $\frac{\Delta p_o}{H_i} = 0.645 \frac{H_o}{H_i}$
		Total: $\frac{\Delta p_i}{H_i} = 0.595$
		Inlet: $\frac{\Delta p_i}{H_i} = 1$
		Total: $\frac{\Delta p_i}{H_i} = 1$

$$H_i = \left(\frac{\rho v_m^2}{2g_c}\right)_i \quad H_o = \left(\frac{\rho v_m^2}{2g_c}\right)_o \quad X^* = \frac{x}{L}$$

Source: Data from London et al. (1968).

^a The geometry of header designs is presented in Fig. 12.11. Subscripts *i* and *o* denote the entrance of the inlet header and the exit of the outlet header.

^b The outlet header is a box header (required for a minimum inlet header loss for counterflow configuration and imposed for paralleflow configuration).

^c For the paralleflow header, the inlet header dimension *z_i* can be either larger or smaller than the outlet dimension *y_o*; for counterflow, *z_i* must be $(2/\pi)y_o\sqrt{\rho_i/\rho_o}$ to assure the matching pressure profile needed for uniform flow distribution and for minimum header loss. The outlet header is also considered to be a box header.

^d $H_o/H_i = 4/\pi^2$ for a counterflow header.

(Zhang, Tian, & Guo, 2013) used CFD to optimize a plate and fin heat exchanger header to reduce flow maldistribution and to improve the heat transfer performance. A CFD model under FLUENT software was used.

The problem with a conventional header is that the fluid speed are lower on the sides of the header, the classic header was optimized first with a plane perforated plate then using a curving perforated plate. The plate uses three different holes diameters symmetrically arranged. Two Reynolds (1000 and 1500) were tested. The perforated plate grants a better performance than the classic header with a more uniform profile. The use of a curved plate instead of a plane plate strengthens the uniformity of the distribution. The uniformity of the flow granted by the optimized header is illustrated by the graphic below.

For this study, experimental results were in good agreement with CFD results.

(Zhang, Mehendale, Tian, & Li, 2015) studied different inlet angles to improve flow distribution in a plate and fin heat exchanger and the impact of a complementary cavity. The distributor schematic can be seen below (it is the same type of geometry that the (Zhang, Tian, & Guo, 2013) study):

At the difference of the conventional distributor, the improved distributor is perforated with a 10% distribution allowing flow to move through the passages. The effect of the distributor angle is significant and reached an optimum for 45° angle in their study.

The use of a complementary cavity improves the heat exchanger performances, the parameter h/H was the primary parameter modifying flow distribution. The optimal value for this ratio was about 0.2. The

auxiliary cavity allows the fluid to be redistributed in the distributor due to the different pressure drops between the fluid passages.

Velocity distribution in lateral direction for different conventional distributors.

Velocity distribution in lateral direction for different improved distributors.

(Raul, Bhasm, & Maurya, 2015) studied four header types of plate fin heat exchanger: a conventional header is described on the following figure with no baffles, and a modified header with single or double baffle with a varying arrangement. The study was done for three Reynolds numbers (60000, 50000, 40000).

a

b

Schematic drawing of header configurations (a) Conventional header (b) Modified header

The baffles are made of several holes with diameters increasing with the distance to the baffle center. This diameter variation balances the flow speed which is naturally higher at the center due to the header shape. Two patterns are used an inline pattern and a staggered pattern.

Baffle plate arrangement used in inlet header configuration a) Inline arrangement [3] b) staggered arrangement [3] c) second baffle plate.

The figure below illustrates that in the conventional header the high velocity of at the center of the part result in a non-uniform flow distribution. The use of 2 baffles and the modification of the header (figure c and d) strongly affect the flow distribution and allow a uniform flow along the header length.

velocity contours of all header configurations. (a) Conventional baffle plate (b) header with single baffle plate (c) modified header with double baffle plate (inline arrangement) (d) modified header with double baffle plate (staggered arrangement)

The study concludes that the use of modified header with double baffle plate grants a uniform flow that improve the effectiveness of the heat exchanger. This type of header can be used for design heat exchanger with effective performance.

(Kumar, Atluri, Hargunani, & Wasewar, 2007) studied numerically the optimization of the shape of a plate and fin heat exchanger distributor to optimize the flow distribution. The numerical study was done on the Fluent CFD software.

Geometry of the conventional header.

Geometry of the modified header.

The CFD simulation showed that the conventional header give a poor flow distribution. The modified header change in shape reduces considerably the flow maldistribution. This can be observed on the graphic below illustrating the non-uniformity of the flow in the channels following the header. The high flow velocity difference between the central channels and the side channels appearing on the conventional header is strongly reduced with the more adapted shape of the modified header.

Comparison of flow nonuniformities in conventional and modified headers.

The modified header in this flow conditions ($Re=2100$) reduces by 70.71% the flow non-uniformity. The good header shape can also nullify the reverse flow phenomenon than can be observed on conventional header.

(Habib, Ben-Mansour, Said, Al-Qahtani, Al-Bagawi, & Al-Mansour, 2008) studied the effect of maldistribution in air-cooled heat exchangers using numerical simulations. Different geometrics parameters were studied such as the number of nozzles, their locations, nozzle geometry and diameter, the use of a second header, and the inlet velocity. The results showed that reducing the nozzle diameter increase the flow maldistribution. Increasing the number of nozzles has a significant influence on the flow maldistribution, this parameter seems to be the most effective to reduce it, like it is illustrated by the static pressure graphic below.

Distribution of the static pressure in the header ($x = 50$ mm) of the air-cooled heat exchanger of different values of number of nozzles.

The changes in nozzle diameter or geometry have only a slight impact on maldistribution. It was found that the inlet velocity has a negligible influence on the maldistribution. The use of a second header between the nozzle and the current header grants a smoother transition that improves the uniformity of the flow (it can be compared to the use of double baffle configuration of the (Raul, Bhasm, & Maurya, 2015)).

Distribution of the static pressure in the header ($x = 50$ mm) of the air-cooled heat exchanger at different number of holes in the second header.

Literature also proposed constructal design for heat exchanger fluid flow distribution. (Fan, Boichot, Goldin, & Luo, 2008) studied an example of constructal design component. They investigated the quality of this distribution architecture alternatively as a collector or as a distributor for a heat exchanger. The study used both experiments and CFD simulations.

It was brought into the light that a constructal fluid component used as collector guarantee a more uniform distribution compared with its use as a distributor case. In the picture below, it is clear that the flow distribution in the output channels of the constructal distributor do not show a uniform distribution when the constructal architecture is use to make a distributor (left). At the opposite side the constructal component functioning as a fluid collector can approach more uniform and stable flow distribution (right).

The flow direction in the constructal component affect strongly on the final distribution quality. Experiments and CFD simulation confirms that constructal component do not stop maldistribution in the distributor case.

However the more uniform and stable flow distribution guaranteed by the integration of a constructal collector can enhance overall heat transfer coefficient of the heat exchanger from 45.2% to 29.2% under various Re conditions. The complexity of the constructal component causes high pressure drops restraining the use of this design to low applications Reynolds.

Numerical method to improve the maldistribution are also available, please see the CFD-Numerics topological optimization of a manifold in the Numerical simulation dedicated chapter.

The maldistribution publications presented above illustrate the complexity of the maldistribution problem. From these publications some solutions emerge, the first publications with shape comparison seem to promote circular and tapered header, their simple parametrization and the different theoretical profiles given by literature make them good candidate for a first design approach. The use of baffles to ensure flow uniformity in distributor appears as one of the most efficient solution to establish in a short length a flow uniformity. However there is a lack of information on pressure loss due to these baffles. It is probable that the pressure drop increase heavily with the flow speed, the baffle inducing brutal change in cross sectional area and in flow direction. These elements can make them unappropriated for high Reynolds flow.

The constructal design do not appear to be a valid option, the flow not being uniform and the constructal shape creating severe pressure drop for high Reynolds.

Finally, numerical methods give the possibility to design complex shape distributors fitting a given problem. Numerical methods appear to be an effective way to reach an optimal trade-off between pressure loss, flow uniformity and a low volume/weight distributor.

4.9 Fouling

i) Fouling Mechanisms and Factors

(Kuppan) explained that fouling consist in particles deposits on heat transfer surfaces. These deposits reduce heat transfer. Indeed, the particles layer increases the total conductive thermal resistance between the two fluids. The fouling layers on each fluid side act as thermal resistance (colored on the next equation) that can be added to the initial thermal resistance of the heat exchanger and the two fluid convective resistances.

$$R_T = \frac{1}{h_1 A_1} + \frac{R_1}{A_1} + \frac{\Delta T}{k_{HX} A_{HX}} + \frac{R_0}{A_0} + \frac{1}{h_0 A_0}$$

Deposits also increase the pressure drop by degrading the surface condition. Deposits increase the frictional resistance to flow and can block flow passages reducing the flow section.

Fouling may create a localized environment augmenting corrosion phenomenon. The modification of heat transfer rate, will also reduce the system thermal efficiency.

There are six fouling mechanisms:

- Particles fouling
- Scaling fouling
- Corrosion fouling
- Icing fouling
- Biological fouling
- Chemicals fouling (due to chemicals reactions)

In the case of air-air heat exchanger, fouling phenomenon will probably be related to the 4 first points cited. Condensation and evaporation phenomenon can result in limestone deposit and corrosion.

During the halt of the system in freezing conditions, heat exchanger icing can appear depending on the working condition of the heat exchanger.

It is important to understand that multiple fluid factors can promote fouling phenomenon. These fluids factors will enhance the different fouling mechanisms. As the fluid temperature rises fouling phenomenon usually becomes more present due to scaling tendencies, higher corrosion rate and chemicals alterations of fluids.

Hydrodynamic effects due to fluid velocity and shear stress impact fouling. The presence of low speed flow zone will favor the particles deposit. To reduce sedimentation and accumulations of particles it is necessary to maintain a uniform velocity inside the heat exchanger structure.

Materials used to manufacture the heat exchanger influence the sensitivity to fouling, the material will induce corrosion fouling. Choose an adapted material to reduce corrosion phenomenon will reduce the fouling. Finally, it seems obvious to remind that every impurities entering the flow increase fouling by depositing on the fouling layer or acting as a catalyst for other substances.

ii) Fouling Kinetics and Stages

To predict fouling process, it is necessary to observe fouling kinetics. It appears that the fouling kinetic is influenced by the deposit nature, notably because of re-entrainment phenomenon of the fouling layer and its ageing. The working conditions of the heat exchanger (halt of the system, mass flow and temperature variations) will also modify the fouling kinetic.

Three kinetics can be distinguished. The first kinetic is principally observed on soft deposit. It takes place when the deposition velocity is higher than the re-entrainment speed. To evaluate the fouling thermal resistance created by this kind of kinetic, the asymptotic value of this fouling kinetic is used corresponding to an equal deposition and re-entrainment speed. KERN and SEATON (1959) shew that the fouling resistance evolved with the following tendency $R_f(t) = R_f^* \cdot \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{t_c}\right)\right)$ where R_f^* is the asymptotic fouling resistance and t_c the time when the resistance reaches its asymptotic value in the case of a linear evolution.

The second fouling kinetic is a linear growth with no re-entrainment. This kinetic is observed for scaling fouling (limestone deposit). On this kind of kinetic, the fouling thermal resistance increase until the flow path is completely obstructed.

The third and last fouling kinetic present a fouling thermal resistance increasing without reaching asymptotic value. This evolution can be highlight in particular cases such as particles deposit in a gaseous flow.

All these kinetics are the result of multiple stages. The first stage of fouling is called “initiation” phase, it is the time required to observe the deposit formation on a clean surface. This stage is difficult if not impossible to detect. Indeed, no pressure drop increase or efficiency loss are perceptible.

The second step corresponds to the particles transport on the wall by mechanical (inertial impact on the wall) or/and diffusive (turbulence, Brownian movement) forces.

The third phase consists to the adhesion of particles to the wall due to adhesion forces such as Van der Waals, electrostatics forces, capillary forces, inertial or cohesion forces. Factors like roughness, arrangement of the existing deposit) will enhance the adhesion phenomenon.

This phase can be followed by a re-entrainment stage which occurs when the equilibrium between wall shear stress and cohesion forces is broken.

At the same time, the ageing of the deposit will modify its chemical and crystal structure allowing an easier re-entrainment.

An approximation of the fouling resistance can be found using tabulate value of thermal fouling resistance depending of the working fluid and of the heat exchanger geometry. The following values give an example for a finned heat exchanger surfaces:

<i>Fluid</i>	<i>Fouling resistance (10⁻⁴ m².K/W)</i>	<i>Flow velocity (m/s)</i>
Natural gas	0,9 - 5,3	30 - 40
Propane	1,8 - 5,3	25 - 30
Butane	1,8 - 5,3	18 - 24
Clean turbine gas	1,8	15 - 21
Moderately clean turbine gas	2,7 - 5	
Light oil	3,6 - 7	
Diesel oil	5,3	
Heavy oil	5,3 - 12,4	
Crude oil	7,0 - 27	
Coal	8,9 - 88,5	

Résistance d'encrassement (10⁻⁴ m².K/W) pour les gaz de combustion à travers des surfaces ailetées

iii) Numerical Modelling and Characterization

The numerical modelling can be used to study the fouling in a specific heat exchanger and help to design it.

(Lindberg) investigated a method to simulate particles fouling entering an engine compartment with its cooling heat exchanger on an usual CFD software. This method can be extended to any air/air heat exchanger. To model the fouling, the study replaces the heat exchanger by a porous media. When the simulation of the flow field is converged the fluid solver is frozen, particles are released and tracked in post processing. Particles are released in a steady state Lagrangian framework.

To make the behavior of particles in porous media matching the behavior of these particles in real heat exchanger, the study used and implemented a body force acting on particles.

The study conclude that the method works to determine a relative amount of particles entering the engine compartment and can be used to test the behavior of different size of particles for a given case.

(H., Groll, Weibel, & Garimella) proposed a model to predict the fouling in heat exchanger particularly in HVAC heat exchanger of fin/wavy fins type. HVAC being air/air heat exchanger but with low working temperature conditions. The model presented in their study can be at least partially used to do numerical modelling of heat exchanger fouling. Their model take into account different fouling factor and evaluate sequentially the amount of particle deposition due to each factors until the heat exchanger be finally blocked.

iv) Technics for Fouling Diminution

Some heat exchangers geometrie are known to be fouling resistant enabling a lower cleaning rate, notably coiled heat exchanger which have a constant wall shear stress and no weak zone. Plate heat exchanger with wide ducts is particularly adapted for fouling.

Some heat exchangers like scraped surface heat exchanger contain moving part to clean the surface during operation.

However if high compactness is needed that required complex surfaces which are sensitive to fouling another solution is to use a pre-heat exchanger anti-fouling system or to design the heat exchanger core in a way that keep fouling rate as low as possible.

Pre-heat exchanger anti-fouling system consists to clean the air before it enters the heat exchanger using separator, these systems use centrifugal forces and inertia of particles to concentrate particles in a portion of the flow which is eliminated. Two solutions example are presented below:

- Centrifugal separator

The patent (Corporation) showed an example of a separator system using centrifugal forces to clean air. This system is positioned between the air duct and the beginning of the heat exchanger. Several helicoid inserts divert the major part of the particles on the offset part of the tube. This air charged in particles goes into a specific zone where it can be eliminated. The clean air at the center of the duct is directed to the heat exchanger.

Fig. 2

- Inertial Separator

The patent (Honeywell) gives an example of a louvered inertial separator using plurality of louvers to change flow direction for a first part of the flow. A second part of the flow passes through a central portion without changing direction. First air flow containing less particles than the second part of the air flow (heavy particles can't change direction because of their inertia) is sent to the heat exchanger core. The clean air deflected from its initial direction represents 90% of the initial flow.

An example of technical data used to set the separator:

- Technical details given by the patent :
 1. Louver angle from 10 to 90 degrees
 2. Louver spacing from 0.5 to 5mm
 3. Louver length 5 up to 40 mm
 4. Louver thickness from 0.5 to 2 mm
- These data match with the following air flow characteristics :
 1. Mass flow from 0.5 to 3 kg/s
 2. Air speed from 5 to 50m/s

If it is impossible to remove particles before the heat exchanger core, it is always possible to design the heat exchanger to reduce fouling rate.

(Abd-Elhady, Rindt, Wijers, & van Steenhoven, 2004) showed that for a certain gas speed called the limiting fouling speed, the particulate fouling ceases. This gas flow speed limit can be compared to a critical flow velocity required to roll a spherical particle resting on a flat surface and subjected to a shear flow. Depending on particle size distribution in gas flow fine particles deposited can be removed by large depositing particle. To prevent fouling the flow speed have to be larger than the critical flow velocity that corresponds to the particle size most likely to stick first and remain in the heat exchanger.

(Thonon, Grandgeorge, & Jallut) observed the fouling kinetic on corrugated plate heat exchangers and particularly the impact of the corrugation angle. This study was conducted experimentally with water and CaCO_3 particle. It appears that the asymptotic fouling resistance is lower in the case of high corrugation angle. For the water example, the asymptotic fouling resistance is 6 times lower for 60° degree angle compared to 30° corrugation angle.

It was noticed that the asymptotic fouling resistance is inversely proportional to the velocity squared.

(London & Kays, 1998) also gave solutions depending on the fouling type :

For crystallization or precipitation fouling, like water, calcium or magnesium type deposition on the surface, only chemicals additives or mechanical methods can be used.

For deposit fouling, the solution is to use high velocities like explained in the (Abd-Elhady, Rindt, Wijers, & van Steenhoven, 2004) and to reduce dead spot.

For corrosion fouling, a good choice of the initial heat exchanger materials is the most appropriate way to prevent fouling.

It has been seen from this part that the fouling has to be considered as an integral part of the design process. To reduce this phenomenon, two obvious solutions are shown. The first one use a cleaning system before the heat exchanger core at the price of an additional pressure drop, the second one consist to design the heat exchanger to match specific internal speed and avoid recirculation and dead zones. The CFD simulation, by providing a global view of the flow behavior inside the exchanger, can be considered as a useful tool to converge towards a fouling tolerant design.

4.10 Icing

i) Icing Mechanisms

Icing process part will define the icing process, its effects and identify the causes of this phenomenon.

According to the article (Verma, 2002), when moist air passes over cold heat exchanger surfaces with surface temperatures below dew point, the moisture in the air begins to condense. Also, if the surface temperature is below freezing point, frost starts to form. Frost growth causes the performance of heat exchanger to decline, firstly as frost accumulation blocks the air flow passage causing an increase in the air-side pressure drop and a consequent decrease in the airflow rate. Secondly, the capacity of heat exchangers is also detrimentally affected by the insulating effect of frost. Eventually, the heat exchangers need be defrosted to maintain adequate performance. However, the defrosting process itself causes an additional penalty of energy consumption.

During the process of frost deposition on a cold surface several stages of frost formation may be distinguished according to the article (Hayashi, 1977). The three periods describing the formation of a frost layer are provided hereunder:

- The crystal growth period
- The frost layer growth period
- The frost layer full growth period

The first corresponds to the first formation of ice crystals on the cryosurface, which basically form parallel columns or needles growing in one dimension. In the frost layer growth period they start interbranching which leads to a meshed more uniform frost layer. The surface temperature of the frost gradually increases with increased frost thickness due to a rising thermal resistance. When the triple point temperature is reached the frost surface begins to melt, water soaks into the frost and decreases its thermal resistance, which again leads to additional frost deposition and under continuous melting and freezing eventually to a dense and tight layer. This stage is referred to as the full growth period. In the following model only the frost layer growth period will be considered. The authors of the article classified four types of frost crystal structure with respect to the cryosurface temperature and the water concentration difference between bulk flow and surface. Generally, higher cryosurface temperatures and lower concentration gradients lead to denser and more homogeneous frost layers. In the same study the frost type was found to have a strong influence on frost properties like density and thermal conductivity.

The prediction of frost layer thickness and its thermal behavior largely depends on frost properties such as density, thermal conductivity and the effective diffusion coefficient of water vapor in the air filled porous medium. The diversity of possible frost structures as indicated above clearly shows that an accurate determination of those properties for a wide range of operating conditions and heat exchanger types may be a difficult task. The wide range of empirical correlations and theoretical

models that have been established sometimes are mostly applicable only in a very limited operating range. A literature review of empirical correlations for frost properties and frost layer thickness can be found.

ii) Technics for Icing Diminution

In this section, technics to prevent or reduce icing in heat exchangers are presented.

The patent US2013140004A1 presents a system consisting in adding a separator for separating ice particles from the cold air flowing through the cold air flowpath. This separator includes a porous wall through which a majority of cold air entering the separator passes. The system includes an ice particle discharge opening permitting a minority of the cold air entering the separator to carry ice particles separated from the majority of cold air through the opening.

Others systems are described in the patents US20150308731A1 and US4246963. In the first, the conduits of the heat exchanger are heated and defrosted by an electrical current flow. The drainage of the condensed water is supported by openings. In the second system, manifolds direct a relatively hot fluid through the inlet of the cold fluid circuit.

Finally, patents US9033030B2 and US20160122024A1 describe anti-icing systems based on geometrical features. The first uses a specific channels repartition to adapt the flow speed in the different parts of the heat exchanger. The velocity modification seeks to modify the temperature distribution to minimize the cold spots susceptible to frost.

The second is based on a specific channels arrangement to prevent icing. The heat exchanger has two alternate layers. In the first layers one channel contains the hot fluid. In the second layer two channels contain the cold fluid. One of the channels has a lower number of fins to prevent icing.

4.11 Thermal Expansion of Heat Exchangers

i) Thermal Expansion Definition

According to (Barron, 1998), the dimensions of most substances increase when they are heated at constant pressure. This is the phenomenon properly called thermal expansion. However, it is not uncommon for substances to contract on heating. Furthermore, some solids suffer distortion of shape on heating, and may expand in some directions and contract in others. There is nothing anomalous in such behavior, and it is convenient to generalize the term thermal expansion to cover all changes of dimension with temperature.

For common metallic materials, an increase in temperature causes an increase of the volume of the structure. This process results from heat's ability to increase a material's kinetic energy.

Within solids, molecules are typically located in close proximity to one another, contributing to the defined shape of the structure. As the temperature rises, molecules begin to vibrate at a more rapid speed and push away from one another. This increased separation between the individual atoms causes the solid to expand, thus increasing the volume of the structure.

With this volumetric enlargement, the elements of a solid undergo greater levels of stress. Thermal stresses can have a significant effect on a structure's strength and stability, potentially causing cracks or breaks within certain components. Such failures compromise the overall design of the structure, which can lead to possible weakening and deformation.

Thermal expansion critical problems can occur when a structure composed of different elements with different thermal expansion coefficient is subjected to high temperature ranges. The resulting differential elongations can cause high residual stresses in the structure. Residual stress in welding is just one example. In welding, a bond is formed between metal parts by melting their surfaces and placing them together so they are joined when the materials solidify again. As the assembled structure cools down, some areas of the welding tend to contract more than other areas due to differing thermal expansion coefficients. This causes residual stresses within the area of the weld.

ii) Technics for Thermal Expansion Diminution

In this section, technics to prevent or reduce thermal expansion effects in heat exchangers are presented.

Patents US20130299134A1 and US6474408B1 provide mechanical solutions based on the use of seals between an inner core and an outer core. These seals allow differential thermal expansions of the heat exchangers elements.

A close technic is described in the patent KR20180016252A where heat exchangers are divided into two distinct assemblies. Each assembly contains thermally conductive structures framed by two tanks. The tanks of the two parts are interconnected by a system that can absorb thermal expansion. This coupling allows the translation of one assembly of the heat exchanger relative to the other.

Another technic is described in the patent US20160377350A1 for plate fin heat exchangers. It consists in including in the heat exchangers zones with non-continuous fins. The discontinuity reduces constraints. The fins have 3 degrees of freedom and they can be interpreted as the fin possibility to take a sinusoidal shape.

5. Traditional Compact Heat Exchangers

5.1 Compact Heat Exchangers Definition

According to (Kuppan) heat exchangers are considered as compact when their area per unit volume, called density or surface compactness, is equal or higher than $700 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ for gases and $400 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ for liquids such as liquid-to-gas type exchangers (Theodore L. Bergman, 2011). Flow passages associated with compact heat exchangers are typically small ($D_h \leq 5\text{mm}$), D_h is the magnitude of the hydraulic diameter and the flow is often laminar (Theodore L. Bergman, 2011). A compact heat exchanger can use a compact surface for one or more fluids sides. Compact heat exchangers usually provide a higher thermal effectiveness than non-compact heat exchanger like shell and tubes.

Their compactness allows low weight and easier transport combined to a better temperature control. However the compactness increases the heat exchanger susceptibility to fouling.

In accordance with the classification presented in Compact Heat exchanger of J.E Hesselgreaves, 3 types of heat exchangers are considered as compact heat exchangers:

- Plate and fin heat exchangers (brazed or diffusion bounded plate fin)
- Printed circuit heat exchanger (PCHE)
- Marbond

The following graphic gives a global vision of the utilization range of PCHE and FPHE heat exchangers.

5.2 Plate and Fin Heat Exchangers

Plate and fins heat exchangers are a matrix of flat plates and corrugated fins in a sandwich construction. Plate and fin exchangers have various geometries, in order to compensate for the high thermal resistance, particularly if one of the fluids is a gas. This type of exchanger is corrugated with triangular fins, rectangular fins, wavy fins, offset strip fins (OSF), louvered fins or perforated fins. Brazed aluminum plate fin heat exchangers possess some specific characteristics: the heat transfer area per unit volume is very high. Compare to a shell and tubes, the area is over five times greater. Area densities go from 850 to 1500 m²/m³. A single heat exchanger can incorporate several different process streams and the plate-fin construction allows these to enter/exit the HX at intermediate points along heat exchanger length.

It is possible to work with very close temperature approaches between streams (1°C to 3°C).

High thermal efficiency allows compact, low-weight structures. The fin thicknesses range from 0.05 to 0.25mm and fins height range from 2 to 25mm. Typical fin densities go from 120 to 700 fins/m. Some applications with 2100 fins/m exist. The temperature limitation depends strongly of the construction material (-270°C to 650°C). Aluminum brazed can operate up to 120 bar when stainless steel brazed HX are limited to 50 bar.

Plate fin heat exchangers are made by the stacking of corrugated sheets separated by planar sheets and closed on the sides by lateral bars. The separation sheet usually has a clad alloy that will melt at a lower temperature than the parent aluminum during brazing to bond the various components. The exchanger can be made of several cores welded together.

5.3 Printed Circuit Heat Exchangers

Printed circuit heat exchangers are highly compact, corrosion resistant heat exchangers and capable of operate at pressures of several hundred bar and temperature range from cryogenic to several hundred degrees Celsius. The standard manufacturing process involves chemical milling of the the fluid flow

into the plates. This allows great flexibility in thermal/ hydraulic design as complex new plate patterns require only minimal re-tooling costs.

Stacks of etched plates are diffusion bounded together to form a compact, strong, all-metal heat exchanger core.

The thermal capacity of the exchanger is built to the required level by welding together diffusion bonded blocs to form the heat exchanger core. Nozzle and headers are then welded to the core.

Due to its construction, the printed circuit heat exchanger is able to reach 200 bar as routine, with values range from 300 up to 500 bar.

The all welded construction allows operating temperatures from -200°C to $+900^{\circ}\text{C}$. Heat transfer area can reach $2500\text{m}^2/\text{m}^3$.

Printed circuit heat exchanger cores are typically 5 to 10 times smaller than shell and tube exchanger for the same performance.

(Zohuri, 2017) presents an analysis of the performance variation with the width of the exchanger with respect to pressure drop. Width of the heat exchanger was varied while all other parameters were kept constant. An increase of the heat exchanger width increases the free flow area resulting in a velocity decrease. The pressure drop across the HX varies proportionality to the square of the flow speed. Similarly, he indicates that increasing stack and height of the heat exchanger will lead to an increase of the heat exchanger area which subsequently increases the pressure drop.

The diameter of the channels should be at least two times the thickness of the plates.

5.4 Marbond Heat Exchangers

Marbond heat exchangers are formed of slotted flat plates (plates chemically etched through). The plates are diffusion-bonded together. Unlike PCHE which is several times thinner, the plates are stacked to create a single substream enabling very low hydraulic diameters that depends on the slots width and of the plate thickness. The porosity is typically of 0.6-0.7. This type of construction allows very versatile surface forms and allows Marbond heat exchanger to present forms very similar to those of plate and fin or PCHE surface.

The choice of material is only limited by their diffusion bonded ability.

6. Additive Layer Manufacturing & Heat Exchangers

6.1 3D Printing Capabilities for Heat Exchanger

Currently, the manufacturing of heat exchangers entail a long and expensive progression of subtractive (cutting and punching) and conjunctive (brazing) processes. In addition, the brazing process usually requires a complex arrangement of fixtures that involves significant labor and time.

(Gobetz, Rowen, Dickman, Meinert, & Martukanitz, 2016) explained that at the opposite of brazing, the additive manufacturing combines the ability to realize planar structures as well as complex one to create internal fluid channels on heat exchangers. The ability to design complex surfaces allows reaching increased performance. Moreover the range of applications is extended due to higher strength to weight ratios.

Aluminum and stainless steel are common materials that can be used for additive manufacturing. Copper can also be used however it is not considered as viable for aerospace applications.

With additive manufacturing, one can come up with new complex geometries with improved heat transfer coefficient and surface areas. Parts fabricated by an Additive manufacturing processes, like Selective Laser Melting and Selective Laser Sintering, have the following improvement as compared to existing manufacturing techniques such as extrusion, forging, brazing, casting, bonding, machining or combination of these:

- Channel diameter of less than 1mm can be manufactured (Wong et al. 2009).

- Surface roughness can be controlled which may increase heat transfer through increase heat transfer coefficient.
- Intricate 3-D geometries for better mixing of fluid can be designed and manufactured.
- Complex surfaces with improved heat transfer rate and reduced pressure drop can be designed and manufactured

The benefits of being able to build hollow structures with additive manufacturing may allow higher design complexity that may increase performance, as well as enlarge the application range due to higher strength-to-weight ratios. These complex designs can be made with a favorable surface area, leading to the manufacturing of smart, efficient heat exchangers.

“Additive Manufacturing (AM) is a tremendous opportunity, but it requires engineers to develop a set of skills to support it, processes are required before and after; that is the biggest hurdle for the adoption of AM” (Thomas-Seale et al. 2018).

6.2 3D Printing Limits for Heat Exchanger

(Gobetz, Rowen, Dickman, Meinert, & Martukanitz, 2016) detailed several drawbacks of additive manufacturing of heat exchangers. One of them is an important rough as-built surface which can impact fluid flow. Surface roughness reached with laser based powder bed fusion is ranged between 12.5 μm Ra to 500 μm . This roughness can impose the use of honing to achieve better surface finish for internal channels.

The necessity of support structures can be circumvented by maintaining a minimal 40 degrees angle with the horizontal but imposes design constraints.

Another characteristic is the ability for additive manufacturing to create thin walled structures. The walls thickness depends on several parameters, a 200 μm may be created keeping the structural integrity.

But more generally, (Thomas-Seale et al., 2018) have identified the current barriers to the progression of AM for end-use products from an industrial perspective:

- Cost-benefit analysis is highly application specific and incorporates an element of uncertainty, compounded by the lack of well-rounded AM knowledge filtering into industry.
- Design for AM necessitates that designers have a new perspective, requiring increased creativity, underpinned by AM specific knowledge and experience.
- Software for AM is currently severely fragmented in industry and research. The process requires streamlining through the design, optimisation and build preparation processes to create software that is tailored to DfAM yet platform independent.
- The lack of materials available for AM either inhibits the manufacture of certain parts or requires them to be redesigned for different materials. Industrial application requires a parameter dependent operational window for materials to speed up the translation of concept through the end product.
 - Bed size and the speed of AM are limitations for mass manufacture.
 - In-process monitoring systems are crucial to ensuring good quality statistics. In the long-term, industry requires closed loop systems which compensate for in-build fluctuations.
 - Quality control is predominately dictated by in-house specifications and requires more guidance from overarching standards finite element analysis can no longer support the validation of designs for AM, where the mechanical properties are highly dependent on the processing parameters.

Thermomechanical modelling can aid design, but it is time and computationally intensive. Currently the most robust method of statistically quantifying the mechanical properties, in the presence of uncertainties in the build process, is material equivalence.

- Line of sight difficulties for inspection and finishing are a key focus in both research and industry. Where internal features can be finished by mechanical, magnetic, electrical or chemical techniques, surface quality quantification is still limited by deficiencies in imaging resolution.

6.3 Example of 3D Printing Use

The European Patent Office - EP 3312538 A1 illustrates the use additive manufacturing to produce a heat exchanger. The use of additive manufacturing allows overcoming some of the limitations of traditional fabrication methods for heat exchangers. The performance capabilities of conventional heat exchangers can be limited by minimum tube diameters that can be reliably manufactured using standard processes. The additive manufacturing is here used to reduce the tube diameters by up to an order of magnitude compared to those found in conventional designs. The resulting fin tubes can compete in terms of performances capabilities with compact plate-fin designs.

The Canadian patent application CA 2991813 gives an example of a compact heat exchanger for high performance application in automotive realized in additive manufacturing.

Design optimization of heat transfer and fluidic devices by using additive manufacturing

(Nikhil) cites in the bibliography innovative shapes for fins. Until now, geometries based on drop shapes prismatic arrays and cellular metal foams (lattices) were strongly limited by the manufacturing limitations. Additive manufacturing allows complex shape designs. The study cited by (Nikhil) analyses profiles for pin fin designs using additive manufacturing for their production, 4 profiles are compared in terms of heat transfer coefficient and pressure drop.

a) Pinfin-Al6061; b) Diamond-Al6061; c) V-Al6061; d) V-Al6061

Plot of heat transfer coefficient at different mass flow rate

Plot of pressure drop at different mass flow rate

It appears that two geometries that can't be manufactured by conventional machining had better heat transfer rate. This improvement was linked with a better flow migration and a boundary layer growth that was limited leading to higher transfer rate.

Parametric investigation of a non-constant cross sectional area air to air heat exchanger

(Cardenas) proposes an innovative heat exchanger geometry for air-air heat exchanger that can't be manufactured by traditional manufacture process but can be produced using new technics as additive manufacturing. The objective of the study was to reach a design that simultaneously maximizes the exergy efficiency and minimizes the cost. The first approach used in the study consists in maximizing efficiency for a minimum cost by using a design with a non-constant cross-sectional area. The cross sectional area is based on a honeycomb pattern. High pressure pipes are placed to ensure a HP pipe is surrounded by six LP pipes.

A mathematical model and algorithm was developed to generate an optimum design in terms of cost per unit of exergy transfer, depending on temperature range, etc. It is explained that the main contributor of additive manufacturing cost is the material cost. Considering this the reduction of the effective volume is an efficient way to reduce HX cost. The final obtained geometry allows a significant volume reduction per unit of exergy transferred. A segment of HX was designed and

optimized to reach a volume of steel of 84.846cm^3 per kW of exergy transferred at 99% efficiency. The study brings to light the fact that the volume per kW of exergy transferred increases in a quadratic proportion with the characteristic dimensions of the heat exchanger (distance between centers of HP pipes), this observation being probably true for other types of heat exchangers.

Design and Evaluation of an Additively Manufactured Aircraft Heat Exchanger

The study (Saltzman & al.) evaluates the effect of the manufacturing process for heat exchangers.

Heat exchangers have been used for years with conventional design. They have been optimized for cost reduction, weight save, and performance improvement. However, some application such as military and aerospace are still looking for higher performance. The additive manufacturing allows to have a new way of design freedom and may improve some key point for a new performance gap. These heat exchangers are used for fuel air cooler, air conditioning, electronic cooling, engine oil cooler or hydraulic system. All of these can be optimize using the latest technologies.

The authors describe shortly the manufacturing process, and the layer per layer building (Laser beam manufacturing)

The limit of the conventional process, and the freedom of the additive manufacturing may be a serious option to deliver compact, and high-performance parts.

The aim of this work was to evaluate the differences between additive manufacturing, and conventional heat exchanger.

The conventional one has been scanned by tomography.

As the conventional heat exchanger is design to be manufactured with the standard manufacturing process, some tiny modifications need to be done to match with additive manufacturing constraint.

The study does not consider the possibility of topological optimization. This kind of design can reduce the weight of the part by adding just the necessary material.

The test has been performed with aluminum. The exact aluminum composition of the conventional heat exchanger is not written on this study, but the additive one is AlSi10Mg. It has been built on a EOS M280 with a building time of 160.hours. Adjustment has been made on the machine (recoating blade in silicone) to avoid the forces during the coating. Normal parameters have been used.

Before removing the part from the plate, a heat treatment of 300 °C during 2 hours was made. This improved a bit the thermal conductivity (173W/m-K)

Here is a picture of the 4 heat exchangers:

Fig. 11. Summary and naming convention of all four heat exchangers tested.

After the tomography the CAD design has been modified to match with the additive manufacturing process. Angles have been increased to avoid the roof effect.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the baseline oil cooler (left) and CAD model used for the AM build (right), indicating changes to the manifold walls.

About 20% of the air side fins was cracked on the additive manufacturing heat exchanger. None of these cracks was severe enough to scrap the part.

The AM roughness was higher than the conventional one. This was expected, and the roughness was kept this way so it could impact the results.

The AM heat exchanger is 34% heavier than the conventional because of the design modification. This could be a lot lighter if it was a real aircraft application.

Test:

Every heat exchanger has been tested in the same condition, with the same material. The water was heated up to 70°C by four. The water pump manages a maximum of 0.35KG/s.

The water temperature, and flow rate is the same for all test.

Fig. 12. Heat exchanger performance rating test rig.

Pressure drop:

The conventional manufacture heat exchanger is sold on the market. There is available value, so they could compare, and check the test accuracy.

The results show that all the additive manufactured parts have the higher drop pressure. So, the roughness of the channels of AM heat exchangers increases the pressure drop drastically.

Fig. 16. Water-side pressure drop versus water mass flow rate for the baseline traditional and additive oil coolers.

Heat transfer:

The measurement shows that with almost the same design, the AM heat exchanger is more efficient (around 4%), and around 10% for the highest flow rate. But for a given flow rate, the pressure drop is twice the value of the traditional heat exchanger. (see previous curve)

Fig. 17. Comparing heat rejection for the traditional and additively manufactured oil coolers.

Conclusion:

Both AM heat exchangers are better cooler than conventional ones. The surface roughness is probably the main reason of this gap. These surfaces increases give more contact areas and increase the heat transfer. The additive manufacturing heat exchanger has a big potential. The results show better heat transfer without any changers, or optimization.

The design freedom offers by this process gives more possibilities to improve the flow so the heat transfer can be better. It is believed that the performance can be increased with more compact and

lighter design. This is keys point to aeronautic industry, for better plane efficiency, and more ecological aircraft.

Redesigning a Heat Exchanger Using Additive Manufacturing Methods

(Badamo, Jackson, & Lutton, 2016) illustrate the use of additive manufacturing to redesign a heat exchanger from Lockheed Martin aircraft to provide more heat transfer keeping the same heat exchanger volume that the original. To achieve this goal, the solution was to use hexagon lattice structure to increase the surface area, and to build the heat exchanger with aluminum. The hexagon surface triples the surface while keeping a good airflow.

(Unison to Additively Manufacture Air-Air Heat Exchangers for Cessna Denali Aircraft, 2017) used additive manufacturing for aircraft heat exchangers. Unison developed an air-air heat exchanger for Cessna Denali single-engine turboprop. The additive heat exchanger increases reliability by eliminating the use of brazed joints. The second amelioration comes from the design allowed by additive manufacturing, the heat exchanger offering a lower volume and weight.

An investigation of a multi-layered oscillating heat pipe additively manufactured from Ti-6Al-4V powder

In the document (Ibrahim, 2016), the authors describe a multilayered 50.80x38.10x15.75 mm Oscillating Heat Pipe (OHP) built on a ProX 100 machine using Ti-6Al-4V powder (ASTM B347 Grade 5, 15-45 μm).

An Oscillating Heat Pipe consists of capillary pipes organized in a serpentine-way through a heat source and a heat-sink. The part of the OHP in contact with the heat source is called “evaporator” and the part in contact with the heat sink is the “condenser” (see figure below).

Schematic view of an OHP with liquid and vapor distribution

When the temperature difference is sufficient, the liquid coolant evaporates in several portions of the evaporator section and expands unevenly. This is the “start-up” of the OHP; the heating builds up an oscillating vapor pressure on the liquid volumes and drives the coolant in an oscillatory motion.

An effective working range for an OHP can be expressed with the Bond Number:

$$Bo = \frac{r_h^2 \Delta\rho_{lg} g}{\sigma} \leq Bo_c$$

With $\Delta\rho_{lg}$ the pressure difference between the gas and liquid phase of the coolant, r_h is the channel radius, σ the liquid-to-vapor surface tension. Bo_c is the critical Bond number for operating an OHP and ranges between 0.8 and 1.

The OHPs are sensible to the orientation since gravity will influence the fluid motion.

Multi-layered OHPs with interconnected channels prove to be challenging to produce using traditional manufacturing methods (more than 2 layers). Moreover, the geometry and shape of OHP channels are also heavily constrained.

The OHP build is made of 4 interconnected layers build vertically upward (the channels were perpendicular to the baseplate). The un-melted powder was removed by drilling 9 holes and injecting pressurized air (see figure below).

Top left - 3D printed OHP. Bottom left - CAD transparent view. Right - Dimensioned drawings (mm).

After experimental tests and measurements with water and cleaned by vacuuming the liquid, the channel surface quality was investigated using neutron imagery. It was highlighted the presence of remnant volume of coolant unevenly along the channels (see figure below).

Neutron radiograph of the OHP exhibiting the trapped water remnants.

This highlights the impact of the rugosity of sintered channels on the wicking (evacuation) and the wetting of the liquid coolant.

Also, the roughened surface (compared to traditional OHP) “can decrease the start-up power threshold of the OHP (due to boiling enhancements and secondary capillary action) while decreasing its power limit (since pressure balancing within the evaporator becomes easier to obtain during operation)”.

Very small unrestrained powder debris are also observed (likely small satellites that have been “teared off” by the liquid motion), which impact beneficially the heat transfer as they improve micro-to-nanoscale convection by mixing with the coolant.

The authors conclude on the “utility of L-PBF for fabricating minichannel devices. A means for de-powdering the internal channel structure must be integrated at the design phase.” Also, the rugosity of the internal channels due to sintered powder improves the wicking capability of the liquid coolant. This improves the capillary pumping the OHP thus reducing its start-up threshold and gravity (orientation) dependence.

The utilization of selective laser melting technology on heat transfer devices for thermal energy conversion applications: A review

In the document (Jafari, 2018), the authors dress a global review of the capabilities of selective melting manufacturing technologies in the field of thermal management, namely in the production and usage of heat exchangers, heat pipes, heat sinks.

They sorted the studies in two HX technologies: single phase and two phases.

- Single phase heat exchangers

The authors reviewed many design and technology for single phase heat exchangers, such as fins, micro-channels, pitot tube...

Fins-like design has been extensively studied as fins greatly enhance the heat transfer coefficient of a heat-sink, but this is counterbalanced by a significant pressure drop. The contribution of SLM technology is mainly on the liberty it offers to design and produce fins of various and complex geometry, leading to significant improvements on the heat transfer but still at the price of a pressure drop. The figure below shows different design built using SLM machine.

Heat-sinks built using SLM technology; a) classic pin fins, b) diamond-shaped fins, c) V-shaped fins, d) Lattice structure.

The figure below presents a non-exhaustive comparison summary of heat-exchangers built using SLM technology and their baseline.

Heat transfer	pressure drop	Baseline	Investigated	References
+39%	-18%		finless tube micro channel [123]	
+21%	-		rounded rectangular HS [118]	
+35%	-		Airfoil HS [118]	
+32%	-		Pitot tube HX [43]	
(a) +11.2%, (b) +11.5%, (c) +12.8%, (d) -19.1%	(a) +1.6%, (b) -66%, (c) -15%, (d) -28%		Variable pin fin HS [133]	
+40%	-		twisted tube HX [127]	

Comparison between heat-exchangers built on SLM machine and their baseline.

The authors conclude that the research effort has been focused on investigating novel designs made possible using SLM technology to improve thermal performance. They suggest that further developments should be conducted to improve compactness and thermal efficiency in the hope to maximize the thermal performance and minimize the cost.

- Two-phases HX/HS

Two-phase propose an improvement on thermal management. The authors have mainly focused their review on heat-pipes, as they are a heavily used passive two-phase device.

Heat-pipes make use of porous media to enhance evaporation and boiling phenomena and to be able to pump fluid by capillarity.

The authors point out the difficulty in manufacturing porous media or wick structure using traditional means. SLM process allows easily making sintered-powder porous structure of various shapes but also to design porous structure filled with small unit cells (see the two figures below for examples of sintered wick structures and unit cells).

Porous media made from sintered powder using SLM.

Cell topology	Material/application	Manufactured part

Different unit cell topology used to produce porous structure in SLM.

In summary, the authors point out the growing interest in making innovative complex porous media structure using SLM technology. This technology allows fabricating porous structures that are impossible to make otherwise.

Several studies have been carried out to evaluate the mechanical properties of porous structure with different materials and unit cells. They point out the influence of numerous parameters such as build orientation, heat treatment, cell topologies...

The authors also point out that none of the studies reviewed demonstrate the acceptance of porous media made with SLM in heat-exchange applications.

Concerning heat-pipes, the authors conclude that SLM has proved to be a suitable manufacturing technology. They cite several studies that successfully build different type of heat-pipes (pulsating heat-pipes, loop heat-pipes, capillary heat-pipes among others) with innovative designs allowed by SLM technology leading to improved thermal performance.

In conclusion, the authors have reviewed numerous papers on heat-exchangers/heat-sinks produced using additive manufacturing. Through these studies, it has been shown that SLM technology provides unique features and liberty to improve efficiency of heat-exchangers/heat-sinks.

The authors also point out the interest of copper in SLM technology for heat exchangers/heat sinks. Further studies are needed in this specific field as copper exhibits several challenges to be used in additive manufacturing (laser absorption, heat conduction among others).

Despite the qualities provided by SLM technology, in the authors' opinion, further studies are needed on the matter of surface roughness. It has been shown that surface roughness improves heat transfer but at the price of a pressure drop.

The authors also point out the lack of studies on improving compactness of heat-exchangers using additive-manufacturing.

Design And Process Considerations For Effective Additive Manufacturing Of Heat Exchangers

The document (Handler, 2017) provides information about additively manufactured heat transfer equipment, such as heat pipes and heat sinks, in particular the benefits and challenged associated to the power bed fusion (PBF) process.

The most commonly claimed advantage of PBF is the ability to create complex structures at one manufacturing step, whereas the current heat exchanger manufactured with conventional process require to be assembled with various joining method, which can cause thermal resistance and heat transfer reduction. This thermal resistance becomes from the remaining small gaps between the surfaces after joining.

Among the different additive manufacturing process, PBF has the advantage to enable small layers, fin details and reduced supports.

Surface roughness

One particularity of PBF is the roughness of the manufactured surfaces. Whereas it can be a disadvantage for some applications, it turns out to be a positive factor for heat transfer by causing local turbulence and providing more surface area. However, it has the drawback to increase pressure drop.

The roughness is mainly dominated by the material and process parameters: hatching distance, thickness of the layers, direction of the build, scan velocity and power of the heat source, and size of the particles.

Figure 1. SEM image of a PBF/Ti-6Al-4V mini-channel adjacent to a machined surface.

Calignano et al. (Calignano M. A., 2013) investigated the effects of different SLS process parameters on the surface roughness of AlSi10Mg, and they used the Taguchi method to determine an ideal set of parameters for the best surface roughness $R_a=15.68 \mu\text{m}$

The geometrical orientation has a substantial influence on the surface roughness. Pakkanen et al. (Pakkanen, 2016) studied this phenomenon using SLM to produce variations of tubing 10 mm thick out of AlSi10Mg and Ti-6Al-4V. The tubes were produced at various angles and all the R_a values were included in $20\mu\text{m} \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$.

Other parameters can influence the roughness:

- Jamshidinia et al. (Jamshidinia, 2015) showed that heat accumulation resulted in lower roughness
- Wang et al. (Wang M. X., 2016) showed that the surface roughness on the top and bottom surfaces of an inclined wall increase sharply when the angle exceeds 45° for both surfaces

Porous Structures

Porous materials like metal foams or sintered parts are often used in heat pipes as wicking structures but their high degree of randomness does not optimize their effectiveness. PBF allows manufacturing porous structures with optimized designs. The cellular lattice structures are beneficial in increasing heat transfer due to their high surface area and continuous nature.

Heat sinks

Wong et al. used SLM to produce heat sink arrays of Al 6061 and some SS 316L with different geometries to compare their associated heat transfer and pressure drop during crossflow of air through the arrays.

When the different geometries were compared, the cylindrical pins and the “V-shaped” array performed roughly the same at equal Reynolds numbers, and the diamond-shaped pins produced significantly higher heat transfer at much lower Reynolds numbers, while the elliptical pins produced the lowest heat transfer.

Figure 2. Lattice-structured heat sink fabricated via L-PBF [34]. *Used with permission.*

However, the lattice structure had significantly lower heat transfer even though it had a larger surface area. This was due in part to the fact that the lattice was designed to have channels that allow air flow with little interaction with the lattice structure, and this reduces heat transfer.

When the pressure drops were compared, the elliptical pins produced the lowest pressure drops, the cylindrical pins produced the highest, and the pressure drops for the rectangular pins and lattice structure were about the same.

Pressure Loss and Heat Transfer Performance for Additively and Conventionally Manufactured Pin Fin Arrays

This paper, (Kirsh T. , Pressure Loss and Heat Transfer Performance for Additively and Conventionally Manufactured Pin Fin Arrays, 2017), deals with the pin fin heat exchangers, which are widely used in cooling of electronics and turbine airfoil, in order to compare their performances between the conventional (data from the literature) and the SLM additive manufactured versions.

The figure below defines the geometrical configuration of the pins array:

Fig. 1. Pin fin spacing nomenclature.

The literature shows that:

- Decreasing X/D and S/D increased the heat transfer, but yielded a corresponding penalty in pressure drop
- S/D had a stronger influence on friction factor than did X/D
- An increase in Reynolds number generated higher heat transfer
- An increase heat transfer performance with narrow pin fin channels, where wall effects were influential, compared to a conventional, wide pin fin array
- An increase in convective heat transfer due to rough pin surfaces as compared to the smooth surfaces, which is a characteristic of the additive manufacturing.

The literature reports also that the surface finish of AM parts is influenced by the process parameters, such as laser scan speed, hatch distance, laser energy density and layer thickness:

- An increase of the laser energy density which smooths the part surface and mitigates the stair-stepping effect seen on inclined upward facing surfaces
- Laser power as especially influential in the surface roughness of downward facing surfaces, whereas for upward facing surfaces, the laser power had minimal impact on surface roughness
- Smaller layer thicknesses will improve surface finish.

Pin fin arrays in Inconel 718 with four different spacing were manufactured and tested over a range of Reynolds numbers. As pin density increased, a corresponding increase in the roughness in the channel was seen due to the higher levels of heat accumulation during the build, which causes more loose powder particles to adhere to the interior channel surfaces. An increase in friction factor of 20–40% (for a tighter spanwise spacing) and 60% (for a wider spanwise spacing) is observed over smooth arrays with the same spanwise spacing.

Fig. 2. Test coupon build direction, with support structures. Flow direction is into the page, normal to the flanges.

Table 1
Test matrix.

S/D	X/D	Added surface area relative to open duct (%)
2.0	2.6	50
4.0	2.6	43
1.5	2.6	58
2.0	1.3	85

The heat transfer of the L-PBF coupons far exceeded that of a smooth channel. At a close spanwise spacing, the L-PBF coupon outperformed other smooth arrays with the same spacing, especially at higher Reynolds number. With a wider spanwise spacing, however, the difference between the L-PBF and smooth arrays was small.

This study has found that roughness levels and pin shape are intrinsically tied to the pin spacing in the array and prove equally influential in the performance of the array.

6.4 Optimized Designs of Heat Exchangers for Additive Layer Manufacturing

The Additive Layer Manufacturing (ALM) technology, as seen before, allows a multitude of new possibilities in terms of design. The design of heat exchangers, less constrained for reasons of manufacturability thanks to this technology, can be now more suitable to the problems of the exchanges of heat to try to optimize them.

The University of Maryland's Center for Environmental Energy Engineering (CEEE) designed a new kind of air-to-refrigerant heat exchanger compatible for 3D printing in order to be more effective. This new design is based on an innovative shape for tubes in order to reach an optimal air-side thermal resistance and minimize the size and weight of the heat exchanger:

This new kind of tubes, combined with the possibility of integrating functions, allowed the CEEE to design and print a one part heat exchanger more efficient, more compact, lighter and requiring less maintenance than a conventional one. On the picture below, the original heat exchanger is on the left, the optimized one is on the right.

Another example of the capabilities of 3D printing which allow optimizing the internal structure and skin thicknesses is provided hereunder:

This heat exchanger was designed by AUTODESK and provides very interesting performance while being lighter and stronger. Inside each of the tear drop shaped tubes are struts (known as turbulators) which increase the internal surface area and disrupt the flow of the fluid to maximize heat transfer and thus cooling. The outside form is also designed to maximize cooling by increasing the external surface area via the inclusion of external cooling fins. The heat exchanger is built from a large number of repeated sub-elements. Each sub-element has been optimized so that the final design can be formed into almost any shape which means it can be designed to fit into the space available.

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In this other example, lattice structure is integrated in the design of the heat exchanger. This kind of new 3D printable design allows improving heat efficiency by increasing the exchange surfaces while increasing the mechanical strength. This heat exchanger was designed by Swansea University and Renishaw.

For the automotive 3D printed heat exchanger provided below, HiETA technologies and Renishaw designed a very innovative one part concept. Traditionally, heat exchangers are often made up from thin sheets of material that are welded or brazed together. The complexity of the designs makes production both challenging and time-consuming, while the material used for the welding and brazing process adds to the overall weight of the part. Thanks to additive manufacturing technology, this kind of heat exchanger is around 40% lighter and smaller by volume than anything equivalent.

Other 3D printed heat exchangers are provided below. Shape varieties are almost limitless.

3D SYSTEMS:

PROGRESSIVE:

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APWORKS:

MATERIALISE:

7. Numerical Simulations (CFD, STRUCTURE, ALM)

7.1 Introduction

Numerical simulations are needed to predict the fluidic, thermal, mechanical and electromagnetic behavior of a studied system. Numerical simulations, based on finite element method, are very useful to simulate innovative concepts without the need of physical tests. In the development phase of a product, the number of tests is then reduced and therefore the cost also.

The finite element method, based on the resolution of systems composed of algebraic partial differential equations, leads to an approximated solution of the simulated problem. This approximation is due to the precision of the discretization of the analyzed space (the mesh) but also to all hypotheses taken for the analyses (initial state, boundary conditions, loadings ...).

A heat exchanger is confronted with multiple mechanical and thermal stresses. These mechanical stresses can be of different natures:

- Fluid pressure
- Imposed deformation
- Vibration
- Interface forces

Thermal stresses are due to the temperatures of the fluids circulating in the heat exchanger, which can be extremely cold or hot, with large variations.

To characterize the behavior of a heat exchanger, several kinds of analyses have to be performed in order to take into account thermal and mechanical solicitations.

7.2 Heat Transfer and Fluid Flow Simulation

i) Computational Fluid Dynamics

According to (Computational Fluid Dynamics) article, computational fluid dynamics is defined as the use of numerical analysis and data structures to solve and analyze problem involving fluid flow and by extension heat transfer.

In the Fluid Power industry CFD has proven to be an essential tool to the design engineer. Together with Additive Manufacturing (3D Printing, AM) design, it has enabled a high rate of both complex design iterations, and validation in meeting performance targets.

(Ismail, Ranganayakulu, & Shah, 2009) study illustrates the multiple possibilities offered by the CFD to optimize a heat exchanger. The present study shows several levels of CFD use to improve heat exchanger performance: at the intensification structure scale, the CFD simulation was used to generate Colburn and friction factor as a function of Reynolds for three types of offset fins and sixteen types of wavy fins allowing a direct comparison of the different structures.

At a bigger scale, the data find in literature on maldistribution and header design were tested using the CFD enabling the comparison of flow uniformity and pressure drop for different header designs. Finally at the heat exchanger scale, three plate and fin heat exchangers were modeled and compared.

(Pianko-Oprych & Jaworski) article also illustrates the use of CFD for heat exchanger design and comparison. They compared two plate heat exchanger geometries studying the impact of geometric characteristics.

The computation allows them to examine the velocity, temperature and pressure distributions along the heat exchanger. CFD results were compared to experimental results and show a good agreement.

Comparing two heat exchanger configurations they were able to identify that the second one allows obtaining lower outlet temperature for the hot fluid which means a better heat transfer. They were able to compare pressure drop in each case. They brought to light that the 3D CFD is a useful tool to analyze, design and optimize heat exchanger designs and allows minimizing flow maldistribution.

This point of view is confirmed by (Kalidasan & Ravikumar) & (Zhang, Tian, & Guo, 2013) studies which both illustrate the use of CFD to design solution for flow maldistribution in heat exchanger. The two studies showed successfully that CFD allows first to visualize the location of the problem of flow distribution and to lead parametrical study to define the best solution. It is also important to observe that maldistribution results coming from the CFD are in agreement with experiments.

Several of the different correlations coming from literature and which are displayed in this report were obtained by CFD calculation and validated by experimental studies. It illustrates the ability of CFD to enable comparison between different structures samples to select the best geometry without the need of prototyping cost.

NOGRID gives an example of tool to make CFD simulation for heat exchanger. They illustrate their program ability with a shell-and-tube heat exchanger numerical study. The software particularity is to propose a meshless CFD tool when the major CFD programs like FLUENT and Siemens STARCCM+ require the user to mesh its CAD geometry for calculation purposes.

CFD appears as a useful tool to optimize a heat exchanger. The possibility to visualize temperature, velocity, and heat transfer fields (etc...) everywhere in the modeled domain allow to precisely understand phenomenon occurring in a geometry. With this information it becomes possible to analyze the interactions between design parameters and flow or heat transfer behavior to define precisely the best set of parameters for a given case. Each scale of the heat exchanger can be optimized and compared without the need of prototyping cost.

ii) Topological Optimization

According to (Haertel), topology optimization aim at improving a structure using a desired objective, stiffness or temperature while matching a given set of constraints like an amount of material or a maximum pressure drop. While size optimization and shape optimizations are limited with a set of optimization outcomes because of design assumptions have to made, the topology optimization does not need initial design parametrization. This property helps save development time and allows to identify unintuitive and unanticipated optimized designs.

Topology optimization defines the way in which constituent parts are interrelated or arranged.

(Christian, Manuel, & Lin) gave a global view of the use of topological optimization to create automated design process to solve thermal problem. These kinds of methods can be used to create high performance heat dissipating devices for example. (Christian, Manuel, & Lin) explain that different methods for topology optimization exist. The principal differences between methods depend on how the design variable is parameterized and controlled. Some methods are based on the definition of design variables directly on a finite element domain, others use a specific function used to interpret the generated structure.

The methods can define the structures as a 0-1 design meaning material is or is not affected to a location when some methods can provide densities affecting values between 0 and 1 depending on the location.

Methods can be distinguished: homogenization method uses macroscopic properties of several microstructures and defines the optimal combination of these structures on a domain to form the global structure. At the opposite side the hard kill methods gradually remove elements (material) to design the domain, these kind of model are based on genetic algorithms. A third method is the boundary variation method for which the structural boundaries are implicitly defined as the contour line of a field, this field is a function of a design variable. The last type is the density based methods which are an extension of homogenization methods. The principal difference consists in the use of a single design variable usually the density rather than a set of microstructure. Other variables like thermal conductivity and elastic modulus are then defined as a function of the design variable.

In the case of thermal problem, topological optimization uses a conductivity matrix as a function of a design variable ρ . Gradients are then used to update the topology optimization process.

Examples of the use of topological optimization for the design process are given, two of several examples are cited below:

Koga & al. made a topology optimized water-cooled heat exchanger using finite element method.

Yaji & al. used a boundary variation method to obtain the optimal design of a coupled thermos-fluidic problem.

(Haertel & Nellis, 2016) applied density based topology to the optimization of an air side surface of a condenser in a laminar regime. The model tries to optimize the conductance of the heat exchanger for a given pressure drop and air-side temperature. The model varies the conductivity of the cells to obtain the optimum design.

The program can also evaluate the best geometry for different channel heights (first following picture) or for a fixed conductivity (second picture), etc.

The results were compared to an equivalent finned surface and a significant performance improvement was obtained. This kind of optimization is qualified of mature for fully developed flow.

The same kind of work can be find in (Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering Department Liege University) presentation which gives an example of topology optimization taking both thermal and mechanical performance into account. The topology optimization can be used to improve thermo-mechanical properties and reduces local and residual stresses with respect of manufacturing constraints.

(Haertel, Lei, Alexandersen, Engelbrecht, Lazarov, & Sigmund, 2017) used a density based topology optimization for heat exchangers and heatsinks. For their work, they illustrate an example of 3D topology optimization done for a natural convection heatsink.

(Haertel) thesis gives an example of topology optimization of a cross flow air-air heat exchanger considering heat transfer in both fluids. An interface identification method was used to represent the solid heat exchanger material that separates both fluids. The selected heat exchanger model was a shell and tube heat exchanger. To reduce the computational load, only a small part of the heat exchanger is considered.

The simulation objective is to maximize heat transfer between the two fluids with a constraint of maximum temperature difference between the inlet temperature of the first fluid and the velocity weighted average temperature of the secondary fluid. The optimization result is given below:

The fluid 1 route is represented in blue and the fluid 2 inside the tubes in red. The yellow represents the solid interface between fluids. The fluid 1 and 2 velocity and temperature field are shown. These results demonstrate the applicability of topology optimization model to heat exchanger especially cross flow heat exchanger. However some drawbacks are presented, the model used in this study considered two fluids with the same conductivity, and this type of optimization requires an heavy computational power. For some heat exchanger examples given in the thesis 2000 to 4000 CPU for 1 day to 1 week were used.

Topological method can also be used for flow distribution. An example is SmartOptim of CFD-Numerics, which is an automated module to improve distribution design. The program iteratively designs the shape of the manifold to reduce the pressure drop. In their example, a complex shape distribution is optimized and the pressure drop is reduced by 32%. The program kept the flow uniformity of the inlet.

SmartOptim optimise le parcours du fluide en modifiant la géométrie

SmartOptim optimise le parcours du fluide en modifiant la géométrie

SmartOptim

Réduction de 32% de la perte de charge

Uniformité d'alimentation de l'échangeur conservée

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xbkDgmEEenok>

(Tawk, Ghannam, & Nemen) presentation explains the use of topological optimization and the models behind it to improve heat exchangers. They also brought to light the limits of topology optimization. The high number of variable in formulations limits the number of design cells which induce limited CFD calculation accuracy, limited optimal structures and limited size of optimization domains. The convergence of the method presents a high sensitivity to numerical parameters, like penalization parameter, filter radius of sensibility and design parameters, step size for method of moving asymptotes and weight of fluid continuity function.

It appears that topology based method allows producing innovative shape and complex heat transfer surfaces for a given problem, however the heavy computational cost (time and resources) and the models limits make it difficult to use at the heat exchanger scale.

iii) Genetic Algorithms & Artificial Neural Networks

Genetic algorithms are based on Darwin law natural selection. A genetic algorithm generates high quality solutions applying bio inspired operators such as mutation, crossover and selection. (Genetic algorithm)

(Hajabdollahi, Tahani, & Fard) used a CFD and a genetic algorithm to do an multi-objectives optimization of a compact heat exchanger of plate and fin type, using triangular fins. The objectives were to maximize the heat transfer and simultaneously minimize the pressure drop across the heat exchanger core. Pressure drop and effectiveness were two objective functions. The design parameters were the fin characteristics, like the fin pitch, height and the heat exchanger geometry (stream length). To evaluate friction factor and Colburn factor six different fin pitches and fin lengths were modeled

for various Reynolds number using CFD. An artificial neural network was then used to predict f and j for any Reynolds, fin pitch and fin length. The results were then validated using literature.

The multi-objective problem of this study consisted to simultaneously optimize several objectives with inequality or equality constraints.

A set of Pareto optimal points is shown below. There is a conflict between the two objectives, and the algorithm generates several optimum designs.

The algorithm makes clearly appear that effectiveness and pressure drop objectives can't have their optimum value reached simultaneously for one solution. Each point of the Pareto frontier has the potential to be the optimum design because of the two opposite objectives. The final selection need a decision making process. The point C being the intermediary solution between the both optimum can be selected as the desirable final solution.

(Xie, Sunden, & Wang, 2007) optimize a plate and fin type compact heat exchanger using a genetic algorithm. A minimum volume and the total annual cost were chosen as objective for the algorithm. Pressure drop constraints are also used. The procedure was based on the epsilon-NTU method.

With the pressure drop constraints, the optimized heat exchanger was 30% lower and the annual cost was reduced by 15%. Without taking pressure drop consideration, the algorithm optimized the heat exchanger to reduce the volume by 49% and the annual cost by 16%. The study demonstrates that the genetic algorithm allows automated search of a multiple criteria optimized solution. The method can be extended to other types of heat exchangers using for example perforated fins, slotted fins or louvered fins.

(Yaici & Entchev) study illustrates the combination of CFD and artificial neural networks (ANN) to make an alternative method for flow and heat transfer modelling in the case of plate-fin-tube heat exchangers. 3D CFD is used to develop an ANN model which is able to predict flow characteristics for different Reynolds. The characteristics were reported as Colburn and friction factors. The predicted performance of fins and tubes heat exchangers with this method grants a better accuracy than the literature correlation to design fin and tubes HX.

(Conor, 2017) thesis gives an example of the heat transfer intensification structure optimization on a heatsink. The study defines a fluidic domain and two power maps (symmetric and non-symmetric) which will influence the optimization. An initial geometry is created layer by layer using power vector

and a probability based on the normalized value of the power for each bit and is then analyzed on a CFD tool.

A genetic algorithm is then used to optimize the heatsink geometry. The solution performance is ranked by entropy generation rate and around a 20 samples memory is used. An optimization loop generates geometry. The entropy generation rate of this geometry is evaluated and if the structure performs better it replaces the old one in the memory.

The algorithm work results in a decrease entropy generation by 25% and 21% compared to a similar finned heatsink for the two power maps. The associated thermal resistance decreases of 27% and 22% respectively. However pressure drops were increased by 487 and 453%, each due to entropy generation rate as guiding parameter.

These kinds of algorithms appear to be particularly adapted in the case of heat exchanger design which needs to take into account a significant number of parameters with large range variation. This method appears to be enough developed to extract automatically an optimal design for a complex

object like a heat exchanger as if several objectives are given. However it is necessary to be careful to the objective parameter definition to ensure the algorithm will tend to an efficient optimization result.

iv) Adjoint Solvers

(Wang, Nagisetty, Montanari, & Hill, 2015) illustrate the use of an adjoint solver to optimize automatically the fin parameters of a fin heat exchanger using FLUENT CFD software. The heat load and the drag force are combined in a function using a Reynolds analogy approach. The solver varies fin parameters and has to simultaneously optimize the heat transfer and reduce the drag until the optimum parameters are found.

Geometric parameter variations with optimization iterations

Compared to the initial design, the objective was improved by 50%. The study concludes that the adjoint solver is able to efficiently evaluate the sensitivity of an objective function and predict changes in observables.

(Kirsh & Thole) study the optimization of wavy fins channels using an adjoint solver. The study was led on two wavy micro-channels configurations of constant wavelengths ($\lambda = 0.1L$ and $\lambda = 0.4L$) which are then produced with additive manufacturing and tested. Three objectives functions were used: the first one focuses on minimizing the pressure loss, the second one maximizes heat transfer and the last one maximizes heat transfer to pressure drop ratio. Each function results in a different optimized geometry. The channel length also impacts strongly the final geometry. With the minimum pressure requirement, the channel walls of $0.1L$ case were modified by the adjoint solver to decrease the flow separation in the baseline region, whereas for the second wavelength $0.4L$ the optimizer work to reduce the vortices in the baseline. To maximize the heat transfer, the optimizer modified the wall shapes to enhance the formation of vertical structures for both wavelength cases.

Experimentally it was observed that the objective to minimize pressure loss was not achieved for either wavelength, the roughness due to the AM process dominates the flow structure more than walls shape. However for the heat transfer optimization without pressure drop consideration, the wall shapes

succeed in enhancing vertical structures. The pressure drop penalty was higher than heat transfer benefit.

The objective to maximize heat transfer/pressure drop ratio gives the best results. For the same friction factor augmentation than the baseline 0.1L channel, the 0.1L optimized channel have a 15% increase in heat transfer.

(Min, 2017) illustrates the use of adjoint solver to optimize geometry in a given volume with a maximum domain shape constraint. The study optimizes ducts for HVAC in car. The solver has to fit the ducts inside the confined space and optimize the flow simultaneously reducing pressure drop and improving flow uniformity. The solver avoids labor-intensive trial and error method to optimize the geometry, the optimization requiring lot of parameters variations. In the presented case, the duct was fitted inside the given domain and the pressure drop was reduced by 75% with a flow uniformity improved by 45% at outlet. The work required 50 iterations from the software. The following picture illustrates the boundary surface and the optimized geometry inside.

v) Porous Based Simulation Model

(Ramadurai) illustrates the use of porous media approach by Altran Technologies to simulate porous media, inter alia in micro channels coolers, without the need of direct modeling for thousands of microholes. Direct simulation of complex geometries is too time consuming and cumbersome. The porous media approach consists in using average volumetric properties and an equivalent continuum to simulate the real part. It is based on the concept of representative elementary volume. This volume is selected to avoid properties fluctuations and has to be small enough to render spatial dependency of the properties.

Porous media models are simulated under Fluent using physical velocity for fluid flows computation while the heat transfer model for energy transport in the porous media can be a Local Thermal Equilibrium or a Non Local Thermal Equilibrium model. The difference being that the first thermal model considers that the fluid and solid are at the same temperature in the porous media. In the second model, a heat exchange takes place between the porous media and fluid flow. The author concludes that CFD simulation of flow and Heat transfer through complex geometries can be simplified with

porous modeling approach without having compromises on the accuracy of the simulation. The time took by simulation cycle is lower and improves the design time and time to market.

(Urquiza, Lee, Peterson, & Greif, 2013) introduced an EPM (effective porous media) method to study thermal, hydraulic and mechanical behavior of printed circuit heat exchangers (PCHE) using transient state. They explained that simplified steady state stress analyses underpredicted the peak stresses that occur during thermal hydraulic transient.

The effective permeability is determined with a local volume average, and the use of correlation. The pressure drop determination due to friction of the flow is done with a Fanning friction factor. Heat transfer properties such as convection coefficient come from geometry specific correlation whereas surface area and effective thermal conductivity are calculated with CAD and FEA software.

With the different properties, the code solves mass, energy balance and Darcy equations. The steady state temperature is obtained after iterating between hydraulic and thermal analyses. The program structural analysis is based on structural properties such as Poisson ratios, elastic moduli, and shear moduli that are affected to their zone in the PCHE composite plate model. One advantage of this approach is to allow fast computation and the capture of geometry effects with significantly reduced computational effort. The EPM lower cost in computational resources makes the user able to study PCHE containing features too small to be discretized individually and ran into a transient simulation.

It appears in both publications that the porous based method is efficient for the simulation of complex surface using a scale change, the reduction in computation time and resources are significant. According to the studies, as the porous model uses average properties, the given results are in agreement with experiments. All these elements make this method interesting for heat exchanger simulation.

vi) Deviation Between CFD Model and Experimentation

(Pavel, Jan, & Karel, 2015) compared results coming from three numerical simulations done on Ansys Fluent to experimental results. Their study was done for a compact heat exchanger and combines flow and heat transfer. The flow was simulated using a k- ϵ model for the turbulence. They observed that the prediction was overestimated. The estimated heat transfer rates had a 13 up to 18% overestimation compared with the measured total values. Commonly, higher flow rates with the same temperature boundary conditions gave lower overestimation. They speculate that the difference was created by the turbulence model, k- ϵ model is a model for high-turbulence simulation, however the gap between two fins is relatively small and the flow is locally forced to laminar, this regime approximation can be a source of deviation.

(Minkowycz, Sparrow, Abraham, & Gorman) book cites several investigations that make comparison between CFD and experimental value.

Ismail and Velraj investigate friction factor (f) and Colburn factor for offset and wavy fins. Air is used in their study as the working fluid and the CFD methodology is validated with available literature and experimental results of f and j correlations. CFD results of offset fins are compared to in-house experimental results as well as to correlations for literature. For offset fins, it is noted that j estimation is in good agreement, whereas f correlation needs a multiplication factor of 1.6 for design considerations.

Pelletier et al. investigate the simulation of a brazed plate heat exchanger (BPHE) to define heat transfer characteristics with FLUENT CFD simulation. They use a $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model. The fluid used for the simulation was water with constant properties. It was observed a simulation deviation of 45 % from the experimental values for a constant wall temperature boundary condition and 58% for a constant heat flux boundary condition. Between $k-\omega$ SST and $k-\epsilon$ model, the first one predicts pressure drop value more accurately. $k-\omega$ SST model predicts results 10 to 13% lower than experimental values.

Jain and al. study a chevron plate heat exchanger. The angle of the chevron plate is 60° . For the hot channel, a periodic boundary condition is used. A $k-\epsilon$ model is used, the numerical friction factor was underpredicted by 10% and the numerical Nusselt is underpredicted by 13%.

O'Halloran and Jokar compared the simulation of a BPHE (with FLUENT commercial CFD tool) to experimental data. Several chevron angles were used with various velocities and temperatures for boundary conditions. The turbulence model was $k-\omega$ SST. It was found that the maximum deviation was 20%.

Patil & al. investigate usage of CFD to optimize design parameters. Simulation results deviate from experimental results by 2%.

(Diani, Bodla, Rosetto, & Garimella, 2015) compared the pressure drop and the heat transfer resulting from experiments and simulation on metal foam structures. The commercial CFD software ANSYS Fluent was used for the simulation part. They observed that the numerical analysis predicts pressure gradients very well with a mean relative and absolute deviation of minus 3.8% and 5.4%. For heat transfer coefficient, they compared the computed coefficients to those predicted by an empirical correlation from the literature. This correlation was derived from experimental measurements performed on a variety of metal foams. The numerical heat transfer coefficient agrees well with the experimental/empirical values.

These studies gave various deviation results. As it is impossible to find a common average deviation in this studies, the different publications highlight the importance of model selection (turbulence model, etc...) to reach results as close as possible from the experiments. A first approach to evaluate the deviation could be to test for a given simulated case, the results sensitivity to different models.

vii) Mesh Adaptation

As seen before, the finite element method is a must in the numerical resolution of partial differential equations. These equations have many applications in the modeling of natural phenomena, particularly in physics, mechanical, chemistry and biology, and it is interesting to obtain a precise numerical approximation of their solution. According to the document "Adaptation de maillages en parallèle" from Christian Tye Gingras (Gingras, 2014), one of the problems of this method is when a good accuracy is needed. The regular mesh has to be very precise and leads to large size of systems to solve. Indeed, the accuracy depends on the mesh used by the finite element method. Typically, the finer is the mesh, the more accurate are the results, but the more expensive the calculations. For example, for some equations, such as Navier-Stokes equations, a standard computer may take several days to complete calculations with an acceptable level of error. In this kind of situation, the mesh adaptation, used in conjunction with the finite element method, makes it possible to control the error on the approximate solution while limiting the size of the problem. Nevertheless, adaptation itself has a significant cost in computing time.

The mesh adaptation consists in refining locally the mesh, only in “interesting” areas. For example, in a thermo-fluidic analysis, it is particularly essential to characterize the fluid flow near the boundary layer in a heat exchanger. The figure below, extracted from the document « Génération et adaptation de maillage volume-couche limite dynamique pour les écoulements turbulents autour de géométries complexes » from Laure Billon (Billon, 2018), shows an iterative process to generate an adaptive mesh near a boundary layer:

Another example: a mesh refinement around an object which can represent a fin of a heat exchanger for example:

7.3 Thermo-Mechanical Simulation

To perform thermo-mechanical analyses, several programs are available. Most common editors are MSC SOFTWARE, ALTAIR, ANSYS, DASSAULT SYSTEMES. Each one has its own calculation code to implement the finite element method.

Each of these programs is able to perform linear and nonlinear analyses in static or dynamic conditions. Mechanical behavior of a system can be simulated taking into account all kind of loading: force, pressure, acceleration, temperature, displacement, vibration, impact... All kind of material can be used for analyses: metal, plastic, composite, wood...

These finite element analyses allow predicting the stress repartition in the studied system, its deformations and displacements, its modal behavior (natural frequencies), its frequency response, its stability... Pressure and thermal stress calculations are performed to determine the thicknesses of critical parts in the heat exchangers, such as the fin, plate, tube, shell, etc. A proper selection of the material and the method of bonding (such as brazing, soldering, welding, or tension winding) fins to plates or tubes is made depending on the operating temperatures, pressures, types of fluids used, fouling and corrosion potential, design life, and so on.

Hereunder a picture extracted from the thesis “Comportement Statique et Dynamique d'une Structure Periodique 3D d'un Echangeur Aeronautique : Etude Experimentale, Modelisation et Simulations Numeriques” by J. Rishmany (Rishmany, 2007) and illustrating a mechanical analysis of a compact heat exchanger pattern. This picture represents a tension simulation with (a) imposed displacements, (b) imposed force and (c) displacements and force combined.

Another application of thermo-mechanical analysis is the study of fatigue phenomenon in a system. Fatigue means the damage of a part under the effect of repeated efforts. This is a phenomenon distinct from wear. While the part is designed to withstand given forces, the repeated application of weaker forces can cause it to break.

Fatigue is a process that, under the action of time-varying stresses or deformations, modifies the local properties of a material. These can lead to the formation of cracks and possibly the breaking of the structure. The fatigue is characterized in particular by a range of stress variation which can be well below the elastic limit of the material. The main stages of fatigue failure of a part or assembly are crack initiation (if defects are not already present in the material), crack propagation and final failure.

The Wohler curve (or SN curve) defines the life of the material as a function of the amplitude of the applied stress. It is different for each material, and also depends on the surface condition. This curve is generally defined for a probability of rupture of 50%. It is divided into three parts:

- Oligocyclic fatigue (generally < 1000 cycles) where ductile instability phenomena mingle with fatigue phenomena
- Fatigue with a large number of cycles or conventional fatigue
- The endurance limit where for low applied stress amplitudes, there can be no fatigue failure

A compact heat exchanger used in aircraft is particularly exposed to fatigue problems due to high variations of temperatures and pressures leading to variations of stresses. This phenomenon reduces the endurance life of the compact heat exchanger. In the document “Compact Heat Exchangers, Analysis, Design and Optimization using FEM and CFD Approach” by C. Ranganayakulu and K. N. Seetharamu (Ranganayakulu, 2018), a coupled thermo-fluidic and thermo-mechanical analysis is performed to estimate the endurance life of a heat exchanger. Ideas (SIEMENS) software was used to generate the solid model, then HyperMesh (ALTAIR) has been employed to create the finite element model and finally the analyses were performed with the ANSYS software. First, CFD analysis was carried out to find out the temperature distribution of hot and cold fluid in the heat exchanger. Fluid temperature distribution for the hot and cold streams was obtained for the operating conditions. As the operating envelope is cyclic, having a maximum and a minimum condition, CFD analysis was carried out to obtain the fluid temperature distribution for both the conditions. Linear static analysis is performed using ANSYS software on the FE model for the maximum and minimum operating conditions, and the stress distribution on the separating sheet is obtained. The loads considered for analysis are differential pressure on separating sheet and thermal loads.

The heat exchanger is subjected to high pressure and high temperature in a cyclic manner to experimentally evaluate endurance life. It is found that the CHE has withstood 1100 cycles. The endurance life of compact heat exchanger using computational methods is found to be 1224 cycles and is in close agreement with the experimental results.

In this example, the endurance life of the compact heat exchanger (CHE) is estimated considering both fatigue and creep effects. Indeed, thermal fatigue effects are considered as the CHE is subjected to cyclic loads during its operation. Creep effects are considered as the operating temperature of heat exchanger is 30% of the melting temperature of the material, according to the document “Failure Analysis – A Practical guide for Manufacturers of Electronic Components and Systems” by Bazu and Bajenescu (Bazu, 2011). For fatigue life estimation, the Coffin-Manson equation is used. For creep life estimation, the Larson-Miller parameter is employed.

Once the fatigue life and creep life calculated, the endurance life of the compact heat exchanger is calculated thanks to the Miner-Robinson equation:

$$\frac{1}{\textit{Endurance life}} = \frac{1}{\textit{Fatigue life}} + \frac{1}{\textit{Creep life}}$$

In this kind of heat exchanger, the failure region is often located at the junction of hot air entry with cold air exit. In this region, the CHE experiences maximum metal temperature and maximum metal temperature gradient, which cause maximum stress. It was observed that creep plays a more important role in the failure of CHE than fatigue at higher temperatures.

Hereunder are plotted the fatigue life, the creep life and the endurance life of the compact heat exchanger:

Hereunder an example of brazed compact heat exchanger structure, before and after the brazing process. The third and fourth pictures represent a fatigue failure near the braze joint. The pictures are extracted from the thesis “Etude de l’endommagement en fatigue d’alliages d’Aluminium brasés pour échangeurs thermiques automobiles” by A. Buteri (Buteri, 2012).

i) Structural Topology Optimization Overview

Structural topology optimization is a mathematical method consisting in searching the ideal material distribution in a defined space (working volume or design space) subjected to mechanical constraints. This technique is based on the finite element method: a finite element model has to be created to perform a structural topology optimization.

Structural topology optimization can be used in pre-design phases or when it is necessary to challenge the conventional design. Indeed, the results of a structural topology optimization often lead to very particular designs which can be assimilated to organic geometries. These innovative designs are particularly interesting if they are combined with additive layer manufacturing, because it is often difficult (or impossible) to manufacture them with conventional techniques.

Searching the ideal material distribution leads to designs where all useless material is removed. The resulting geometries are therefore aerated and lighter. Topology optimization is a very interesting solution for weight savings.

An advantage of this technique, when used in pre-design phase, is the function integration. Indeed, mechanical systems conventionally composed of several parts for manufacturing reasons, can be reduced to only one or few part(s) thanks to the capabilities of additive layer manufacturing and topology optimization. The working volume has to integrate all the parts to merge, and the topology optimization finds an innovative design.

Several software editors propose optimization solutions. MSC Software with NASTRAN, Dassault Systèmes with Tosca and ALTAIR with OptiStruct are the most common solutions used in industry.

ii) Structural Topology Optimization Technics

For example, ALTAIR with its calculation code OptiStruct proposes several kinds of optimizations, including structural topology optimization. Topology optimization, with the free size and the topography ones are considered as conceptual optimizations because they have a direct impact on the geometry of the optimized solutions. Free shape, shape and size optimizations are considered as refined optimizations because they allow fine tunings of geometrical parameters.

To perform a topology optimization, the first step consists in defining the maximum allowable volume in which the topology optimization will search the ideal material distribution. This maximum allowable volume (or design volume) has to take into account the environment of the part or system to optimize (neighboring parts or systems) but also all the means for the mounting of the optimized part (tool accesses for example). Once the maximum design volume is defined, the finite element model has to be created: boundary conditions, loadings, material... Topology optimization parameters have also to be set up: an objective has to be defined to pilot the process and all constraints and variables have to be created to frame the solution. Hereunder is provided the process for a force loaded structural topology optimization.

The topology optimization objective consists in minimizing or maximizing a unique function “objective” while respecting constraint functions based on design variables. All finite element data can be optimized: compliance, mass, volume, displacements, force, energy, modal frequency...

Structural topology optimization terminology:

- Objective: response function of the system for which an extremum is searched. It has to be a function of the design variables. Only one objective per optimization.
- Design variable: system parameter that is allowed to change during the optimization process. In a topological optimization, it is the element density, varying from 0 to 1.
- Response functions: finite element data that need to be monitored (mass, volume, compliance, displacement, stress, strain, frequency, element force, temperature, ...).
- Constraint function: define bounds on response functions of the system that need to be satisfied for the design to be acceptable.
- Feasible design: satisfies all the constraints.

- Infeasible design: violates one or more constraint functions.
- Optimum design: set of design variables along with the minimized (or maximized) objective function and satisfy all the constraints.

In a structural force loaded or displacement loaded topology optimization, the compliance is often used to define the objective. The compliance of a part under a particular loading is the internal strain energy of the loaded part. According to the work principle, it is also the total work of external forces. Using the compliance of the system as objective for a topology optimization allows getting the stiffest solution according to the defined parameters and also the best stress repartition in the structure.

$$\text{Compliance} = E_{\text{int_strain}} = W_{\text{ext_force}}$$

Force loaded:

$$W_{\text{ext}} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot F \cdot u = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{F^2}{K}$$

Displacement loaded:

$$W_{\text{ext}} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot F \cdot u = \frac{1}{2} \cdot K \cdot u^2$$

Indeed: $F = K \cdot u$ with F the force, K the stiffness, u the displacement.

According to the kind of loading (force or displacement), maximizing the stiffness of a system is achieved by minimizing or maximizing its compliance.

Hereunder is presented a structural topology optimization of an Airbus A320 nacelle hinge bracket. This structural topology optimization was performed with ALTAIR software and allowed a weight saving of 64% while retaining the same characteristics in terms of stiffness and bolt loading and reducing the stresses in the part.

iii) Coupled Structural and Thermal Topology Optimization

Thermal and mechanical topology optimizations can be also combined to reach complex design solutions with optimized characteristics in both application areas. This concept is described in the

document “Structural and Thermal Performances of Topological Optimized Masonry Blocks” by Gieljan Vantoghema, Wouter De Corte, Veerle Boela and Marijke Steeman (Vantoghema, 2016). In this study, the topology optimization of the masonry block is driven by two main objectives: maximizing the structural stiffness and minimizing the thermal transmittance. These two objectives are antagonists in the way that increasing the structural stiffness leads to add material and thus degrade the insulating performance of the system.

Hereunder are provided results with different parameters of topology optimizations for a 2D cut of a masonry block:

Another example of coupled structural and thermal topology optimization is provided by the software editor ALTAIR. In this case, the objective is to minimize the thermal compliance of a bracket while respecting mechanical constraints:

- 1st normal mode
- Stress
- Mass
- Two symmetric planes

The process is very similar to conventional structural topology optimization. The first step is to define the maximum design volume and then to mesh it in order to create the finite element model. Parameters are then set up to define the objective and the constraints.

iv) Coupled Fluid and Structural Topology Optimization

In the thesis “Evolutionary Topology Optimization of Fluid-Structure Interaction Problems” by Renato Picelli Sanches (Sanches, 2015), the development of a computational tool for the design of structures considering fluid-structure interaction using topology optimization is discussed. A methodology of structural topology optimization is proposed in association with finite element formulations of fluid-structure coupled problems. The difficulties in designing fluid loaded structures arise due to the variation of location, direction and magnitude of the loads when the structural shape and topology change along the optimization procedure. Another difficulty lies in the fact that traditional topology optimization technics are density based methods with intermediate density elements. Thus the pressure loaded surfaces are not explicitly defined. To solve this problem, the BESO (Bi-directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization) method is employed.

$n = 0; V_n = 100\%$

$n = 9; V_n = 80\%$

$n = 21; V_n = 59\%$

$n = 37; V_n = 39\%$

$n = 55; V_n = 25\%$

$n = 69; V_n = 25\%$

v) *Lattice Topology Optimization*

Structural topology optimizations allow including in optimized designs lattice structures. Lattice structures consist in repetitive patterns of a particular cell shape or type. A lot of cell types exist, and the density of these cells in a design is based on purpose of the structure and its loading.

The figure below is extracted from the document “Design for Additive Manufacturing: Trends, Opportunities, Considerations and Constraints” by M. K. Thompsona, G. Moronib, T. Vanekerc, G. Fadeld, R. I. Campbelle, I. Gibsonf, A. Bernardg, J. Schulzh, P. Grafh, B. Ahujai and F. Martinaj (Thompsona, 2016). It provides different types of cell.

According to the document “Topology optimization of lightweight periodic lattices under simultaneous compressive and shear stiffness constraints” by A. Asadpoure and L. Valdevit (Asadpoure, 2015), metallic cellular materials possess unique combinations of low weight, high stiffness and strength, and enable substantial energy absorption at relatively low crushing stress. Moreover, due to the large network of structural members, the design exhibits better performance for stability.

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The picture below, extracted from Altair Enlighten, shows different 3D printed cells:

Hereunder an example of a hybrid design with lattice structure by ALTAIR:

ALTAIR software with OptiStruct but also SOLIDTHINKING with Inspire are able to implement to their structural topology optimization this concept of lattice structure:

Design Space

Optimized Shape

In this example (Inspire), the pattern is constructed with the nodes of the FEA model. The start and end sections of each beam are optimized according to the structure solicitations.

7.4 Example of Coupled Thermo-Fluidic and Thermo-Mechanical analysis

The aim of this section is to describe and illustrate the methodology used to combine thermo-fluidic analyses and thermo-mechanical analyses.

The first step is to create the design in CAD format of the heat exchanger to be studied. This design has to be exported in a format compatible with simulation software, like STEP format for example. Hereunder is provided a CAD model of a representative heat exchanger pattern created with CATIA V5:

This heat exchanger is an extended surface one with thin-sheets. It comprises one cold channel between two hot channels.

The second step consists in analyzing the thermo-fluidic behavior of this heat exchanger pattern. A finite element model has to be created with all necessary data in dedicated software:

- Material of the heat exchanger (thermal conductivity ...)
- Inlet temperatures of cold and hot flows
- Inlet pressures of cold and hot flows
- ...

Once the finite element model set up, the thermo-fluidic analysis can be run. The result is the temperature distribution in all the heat exchanger pattern structure as it is shown below:

This temperature distribution is one of the input data for the next step: the thermo-mechanical analysis.

The third and last step is to perform the thermo-mechanical analysis to characterize the mechanical behavior of the heat exchanger pattern. As for the previous step, a finite element model has to be created in dedicated simulation software: here HyperMesh. Once the CAD geometry imported, the mesh and all necessary data are created:

- Boundary conditions
- Material characteristics (E , ν , ρ , thermal expansion coefficient, reference temperature)
- Properties
- Loading (fluid pressure in channels, temperature mapping from the thermo-fluidic analysis)

All these data constitute the finite element model for the thermo-mechanical analysis:

Remark: material characteristics (E and yield strength particularly) are weighted by a knock down factor in order to take into account the temperature effects.

Once the finite element model set up, the thermo-mechanical analysis can be run (here with OptiStruct). The result is the stress distribution in all the heat exchanger pattern structure as it is shown below (here VonMises):

Contour Plot
Element Stresses (2D & 3D)(vonMises, Max)
Analysis system
8.413E+01
7.470E+01
6.544E+01
5.609E+01
4.675E+01
3.740E+01
2.806E+01
1.071E+01
9.368E+00
2.321E-02
No result
Max = 8.413E+01
2D 1056239
Min = 2.321E-02
2D 1192732

1: Model
Subcase 1 (THERMO-MECA) : Static Analysis : Frame 25

The displacements of the heat exchanger pattern can be also known:

Contour Plot
Displacement(Mag)
Analysis system
2.188E-01
1.945E-01
1.701E-01
1.458E-01
1.215E-01
9.729E-02
7.292E-02
4.861E-02
2.431E-02
0.000E+00
No result
Max = 2.188E-01
Grids 671
Min = 0.000E+00
Grids 5490

1: Model
Subcase 1 (THERMO-MECA) : Static Analysis : Frame 25

As it has been shown, the combination of thermo-fluidic and thermo-mechanical analyses is necessary to characterize the behavior of a heat exchanger.

7.5 Additive Manufacturing Simulation

As described earlier, thermal and thermomechanical analysis are usually done using the finite element method. The computation domain is then subdivided into small elements and the considered equations

are discretized and projected onto those elements. The values of interest (temperature, strain, stress, velocity ...) are computed at the nodes of the elements.

The thermal analysis allows to compute the temperature at all nodes following the heat transfer energy balance. (Megahed, 2016) (Denlinger I. M., 2014) (Hodge, 2014) (Papadakis, 2014)

$$\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \vec{q}(\vec{r}, t) + Q(\vec{r}, t)$$

with ρ, C_p the density and specific heat, \vec{r} is the spatial coordinate, Q is the heat source and \vec{q} is the heat flux vector, expressed as a pure conduction term using Fourier's Law

$$\vec{q} = -k\Delta T$$

where k is thermal conductivity. The radiation heat flux may be accounted using the Stefan-Boltzmann law

$$q_{rad} = \varepsilon \sigma_{rad} (T^4 - T_{amb}^4)$$

With $\varepsilon, \sigma_{rad}$ the emissivity and Stefan-Boltzmann constant, T_{amb} is the ambient temperature. The convection is given by

$$q_{conv} = h(T - T_{amb})$$

With h the heat transfer coefficient. It is usually neglected because small compared to the conduction term.

Schematic depiction of a thermal model (Papadakis, 2014).

The heat-source models the energy input by the laser or the electron beam. Several models are described in the literature such as the Goldak double ellipsoid model (Goldak, 1984) or the Gusarov Model. (Gusarov, Model of Radiation and Heat Transfer in Laser-Powder Interaction Zone at Selective Laser Melting, 2009) (Gusarov, Heat transfer modelling and stability analysis of selective laser melting, 2007) Typically, they follow a Gaussian distribution modulated by shape form factors and a global coefficient accounting for the laser absorption by the material.

These equations allow studying the scanning strategies by modulating the expression of $Q(\vec{r}, t)$ in space and time, mimicking the trajectories and the behavior of the actual heat source.

The phase changes must be accounted as they play an important role during additive manufacturing (melting and solidification of powder). Typically, the latent heat of fusion is considered by defining an equivalent specific heat which increases significantly at the fusion point. (Megahed, 2016)

Following the complexity of the model, one may also account for the powder bed porosity by defining porosity-dependent conductivity and absorptivity.

The mechanical analysis is used to compute the stress, strain and deformation in the workpiece during its manufacturing. This analysis is weakly coupled to the thermal model as it depends only on the thermal history. (Megahed, 2016)

Coupling between thermal and mechanical analysis. (Megahed, 2016)

The mechanical analysis is non-linear because the non-linearity of the material behavior.

The governing equations are: (Megahed, 2016) (Denlinger I. M., 2014) (Denlinger G. I., 2017)

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma + \vec{f}_{int} = 0.$$

With σ the stress tensor and \vec{f}_{int} the internal forces. The stress and strain tensors are linked following

$$\sigma = \mathbf{C} \epsilon^e.$$

Where \mathbf{C} is the material stiffness tensor and ϵ^e the elastic strain. Assuming a thermo-elasto-plastic behavior the total strain ϵ can be decomposed into a sum of plastic, elastic and thermal strain

$$\epsilon = \epsilon^e + \epsilon^p + \epsilon^{th}$$

With

$$\epsilon^e = \frac{1 + \nu}{E} \sigma - \frac{\nu}{E} tr(\sigma)$$

$$\epsilon^p = g(\sigma_Y)$$

$$\epsilon^{th} = \alpha(T - T_0)$$

Where E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's coefficient, σ_Y is the yield stress, α , T , T_0 are the thermal expansion coefficient, the temperature at the considered node and the initial temperature; $g(\sigma_Y)$ is a function representing the plastic behavior of the material.

The mechanical analysis allows to compute the strain, stress and thus the distortion of the workpiece as the layers build up. Knowing the distortion associated to nodes, one may extract a manufacturing criterion based on machine specifications and tolerances.

Distortions of a plate following two different scanning strategies. (Megahed, 2016)

This kind of model can be quite long to compute depending on the workpiece dimension. To reduce computation time, one may consider mesh coarsening algorithms to decrease the number of nodes while retaining the results accuracy.

Mesh coarsening algorithm where layers are fused to reduce computation time. (Denlinger I. M., 2014)

Supporting is essential during additive manufacturing process. It prevents the workpiece to shrink or even break in areas with little to no consolidated matter beneath.

To find the best support strategy, criteria-based search is usually used to find the parts that need supporting. Typically, those criteria include inclination angle and surface to support. (Megahed, 2016) (Calignano, 2014)

If the supports are already modelled, i.e. they are parts of the workpiece cad, their impacts are directly computed with mechanical model. (Papadakis, 2014) (Denlinger G. I., 2017)

Part orientation on the baseplate plays also on important role during manufacturing. Different orientation involves different supports (in shape, size and number) leading to material savings. Minimization algorithms may be used to find the orientations that minimizes the number of supports needed based on criteria (angle and area typically). (Calignano, 2014)

Flow chart for orientation and support optimization algorithm. (Calignano, 2014)

(Sabeur, 2018) deals with the numerical simulation of the SLM additive manufacturing process as a tool to better grasp the impact of SLM machine parameters on the residual constraints. The simulation of the printing process could also help to predict and reduce manufacturing defects and their influence on the part mechanical behavior.

The possibility to use multi-scale simulation allows bringing to light the different physical phenomenon taking place during the fusion and solidification process. The use of simulation reduces the need for experimentation reducing significantly the cost and time needed for the investigation.

At micro scale, the simulation of interaction laser/material allows studying the reflectivity and absorptivity impact of the powder to estimate the amount of absorbed energy.

Finite element method can be used to study particles distribution for each new powder layer. FEM allows investigating the presence of porosity during the layer deposition, these porosities causing default apparitions when the layer is solidified. The simulation of the molten pool and of the thermal input can achieve the study to give an overall view of the phenomenon occurring during AM process and their impact on the product quality.

(Farinia Group, 2016) also proposes a multiscale approach to improve the AM manufacturing process. The process is cut chronologically with five different phases: energy insertion, molten pool dynamics, microstructure evolution, residual stresses and distortion and finally Prediction of Material Properties.

For the energy insertion part, the modeling of the energy beam, molten pool cavity and energy absorption show that the energy flux is governed by the focal spot location, the energy distribution at the local spot and the convergence angle. It is important that the model of the energy beam is enough accurate to describe the physics and timing of the real system. A good temperature distribution is necessary to obtain the residual stresses fields and microstructural evolution. The choice of the model significantly impacts the result, a pulsed model being for example more precise than a Gaussian one. It is important to model the Marangoni effect which affects the melt pool geometry.

The numerical study of the melt pool dynamics can bring to light the relationship between process parameters and the melt pool geometry. The melt pool geometry strongly affects the microstructures during the solidification. Simulation allows studying key parameters like cross-sectional area and length to depth ratio and can be used to draw map curves as a support for engineers to choose process parameters.

On microstructural evolution, it is observable that the increase of beam power makes the microstructure more dendritic because of high temperature gradients. The nature of the microstructure is dependent of the spatial cooling rate variation. Simulation methods like Lattice-Boltzmann and cellular automata (CA) can be used to better understand dendritic growth to determine how to set every parameter which may influence energy density and consequently microstructure development.

Finite elements methods can help improving the thermal control during the AM process allowing to reduce residual stresses, these stresses being due to laser velocity and power. FEM can also help in mechanical properties prediction to optimize the process input parameter which grants to the part its mechanical properties.

8. Heat Exchangers Tests

8.1 Introduction

The book of J. E. Hesselgreaves (Hesselgreaves, 2001), original edition from 2001, presents a very complete review on the design of compact heat exchangers. It addresses the following topics:

Chapter n°1: Introduction

Chapter n°2: Industrial compact exchangers

An example of Plate-Fin Heat Exchanger (PFHE) for the aerospace industry is provided (figure below). This PFHE might be constructed in stainless steel, nickel, inconel in addition to aluminium.

Figure 2.4 Primary air-air heat exchanger, Airbus A320
(Courtesy Secan/Allied Signal)

Illustration of a PFHE

Chapter n°3: The heat exchanger as part of a system: exergetic (second law) analysis

Chapter n°4: Surface comparisons, size, shape and weight relationships

Chapter n°5: Surface types and correlations

Chapter n°6: Thermal design

Chapter n°7: Compact heat exchangers in practice.

The book includes a large database of physical properties of gases and saturated liquids.

The book of R. Shah (Shah S. , 2003) is a second reference book for heat exchangers design. It includes a complete overview of heat exchanger design methodology. Chapter 7 provides information for surface basic heat transfer and flow friction characteristics. It is obvious that the most important parameters describing a heat exchanger are the heat transfer coefficient and the friction factor. The thermal performance of the exchanger will depend on the accuracy of the measured heat transfer coefficient and pressure loss. The book finishes with a complete chapter on fouling and corrosion.

8.2 Test of Performance (Heat Transfer and Friction Characteristics)

The main characteristic of a heat exchanger are the heat transfer and the pressure loss. Two general articles are first described followed by more specific papers.

Methods to perform thermal performance tests and analyse the results of heat exchangers in industrial stream process are presented in the complete review made by T. Lestina (Lestina, 2001). The document is from 2001. It summarised industrial test practices and operating conditions, which are compared with experimental methods. A thorough review of sources of error and their contribution to overall tests uncertainty is described. Laboratory tests are usually expensive because of the high cost of temperature and flow instruments. The analysis includes methods to estimate the uncertainty of predicted performance based on test data measured at different operating conditions.

The second paper is the review of R. Cummings (Cummings, 2005). It addresses performance evaluation in controlled environment of components or system to qualify various heat exchangers used in the automotive industry. The paper focuses on air-conditioning system heat exchangers and present the following testing related to systems: A/C system calorimeter testing, refrigerant charge determination, wind tunnel testing and finally road testing.

B. Sahin (Sahin, 2008) presents experimental results obtained to enhance heat transfer by using perforated square fins. The experimental investigation was performed inside a wind tunnel (figure below). The overall heat transfer, the friction factor and the effect of the various design parameters on the heat transfer and friction factor equipped with square cross-sectional perforated pin fins are presented in the article.

Fig. 1. A schematic display of experimental set-up. (1) Effuser, (2) thermometer/anemometer, (3) differential pressure transducer, (4) test section, (5) heater unit, (6) triac, (7) variac, (8) diffuser, (9) fan, (10) multiplexer board, (11) computer, (12) inlet and outlet thermocouples.

Wind tunnel (Sahin, 2008)

Another test set-up used to investigate the air-side performance of fin-and-tube heat exchangers with various fin patterns is described by L.H. Tang (Tang, 2009). Five different types of fin configurations have been tested experimentally: crimped spiral fin, plain fin, slit fin, fin with delta-wing longitudinal vortex generators and mixed fin with front 6-rows vortex generator fin and rear 6-rows slit fin. The heat transfer and friction factor correlations for different types of heat exchangers were obtained with the Reynolds number ranging from 4000 to 10000. The experimental set-up is shown in figure below:

1-Entrance; 2-Transition section; 3-Contraction section; 4-Straightening section; 5-Test heat exchanger; 6-Flow metering duct; 7-Blower; 8-Boiler; 9-steam over-heater; 10-Inclined tube draft gauge; 11-Volumetric meter; 12-Digital voltmeter; 13-Thermocouples grid; 14-Ice bath; 15-U tube manometer; 16-valve

Experimental facility (Tang, 2009)

Another experimental test bench is described by W. Yan (Yan S. , 2003) to investigate the heat transfer and pressure drop of fin-and-tube exchangers with plate, wavy and louvered fin surfaces. These different fin patterns have been developed to improve the air-side heat transfer performance to reduce size and weight of heat exchangers. The results are presented as plots of friction factor f and Colburn j factor against Reynolds number. Various comparison methods were adopted to evaluate the air side performance of the plate, wavy and louver fin heat exchanger. The experimental test with a test section of 60*40 cm in cross section is represented in figure below. They performed tests on thirty-six samples.

Experimental test rig (Yan S. , 2003)

The master thesis of A. Pandey (Pandey, 2011) describes an experimental investigation to characterise a plate fin compact heat exchanger used to transfer heat between Helium at two different pressures. The heat exchanger is constructed for cryogenic application. The temperature range is between -189°C and 36°C . The experiments have been conducted under balanced condition, meaning that the mass flow rate for both sides of the fluid stream is the same.

A. Pandey (Pandey, 2011) presents a very complete review on plate fin heat exchanger, summarising in detailed the different types of plate fin compact heat exchangers. The main objective of his work was to evaluate the performance of a counter flow plate fin heat exchanger through hot/cold testing. The test rig is shown in figure below.

Experimental test rig (Pandey, 2011)

J. Dong (Dong, 2007) presents an experimental study on the air side heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics for 20 types of multi-louvered fin and flat tube heat exchangers. Multi-louvered fin and flat tube heat exchangers have a high degree of surface compactness and substantial heat transfer enhancement is obtained due to the periodic starting and development of the laminar boundary layer over the interrupted channels formed by the louvered fins and their dissipation in the fin wakes. Characteristics of the heat transfer and pressure drop for different geometry parameters are reported in terms of Colburn j -factor and Fanning friction f -factor as function of the Reynolds number. Figure below shows the wind tunnel apparatus for the study. The wind tunnel is a rectangular duct of 270 * 220 mm in cross section.

- | | |
|---|------------------------------------|
| 1, airinlet | 10, multiplenozzleplate |
| 2, honey cone straightener | 11, variableexhaust fan system |
| 3, T/C inlet temperature measuring station | 12, air outlet |
| 4, pressure tap(inlet) | 13, difference pressure tap nozzle |
| 5, testunit | 14, inlet temperature tap water |
| 6, pressure tap (outlet) | 15, outlet temperature tap water |
| 7, T/X outlet temperature measuring station | 16, dataacquisition system |
| 8, setting means | 17, hot water tank |
| 9, staticpressure tap | 18, water pump |

Schematic diagram of the wind tunnel test apparatus (Dong, 2007)

The paper of M. Kim (Kim, 2002) presents an experimental study on the air-side heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics for multi-louvered fin and flat tube heat exchangers. 45 different heat exchangers have been tested with different louver angles, fin pitches and flow depths. The heat transfer coefficient and pressure drop data for heat exchangers with different geometrical configurations were reported in terms of Colburn j -factor and Fanning friction factor f , as function of Reynolds number based on the louver pitch. The f correlation has indicated that the flow depth is one important parameter for the pressure drop.

The tests have been performed on the test set-up shown in figure below. The uncertainty in the heat transfer rate measurement is less than 3%, since accuracy of the temperature measurement is $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and accuracy on the air and water flow rates are $\pm 1\%$ and $\pm 2\%$ respectively.

Schematic diagram of the test apparatus (Kim, 2002)

8.3 Test of Leakage

Three different approaches can be found in the literature for the identification of leakages inside a heat exchanger.

The first one is a standard Helium leak test (Li, 2008). It has been used for a Printed Circuit Heat Exchanger (PCHE) developed for the next generation of nuclear reactors. Material selection is crucial as the compact heat exchanger needs to withstand high temperature exposure up to 60 years. Inconel alloy 617 is considered by the authors. A leak rate of $8.6E-9$ mbar/sec was measured during a Helium leak test. This value has exceeded the requirements of the diffusion bonded heat exchangers from the authors.

A second approach to detect leakages is the use of Infrared Thermography. A typical example in the use of thermal imaging is the US patent proposed (Avila, 2005) for air conditioning systems. The principle is to have a heated or cooled gas inside the heat exchanger and to measure the surface temperature to locate any leaks in the heat exchanger.

An efficient Fuzzy Model-based leak detection algorithm has been developed by H. Habbi (Habbi, 2009) for a pilot plant heat exchanger. The fuzzy model-based leak detection and diagnosis scheme is designed using experimental data collected from a pilot plant in normal operation mode. Different leaks have been introduced on the real heat exchangers and corresponding data sets are analysed for Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD) system design. The main advantage of the method is the use of a dynamic fuzzy model that can be trained from measurement data instead of applying complicated first-principle laws. With the integration of a suitable fuzzy reasoning on the design of FDD systems, the author claims that significant improvement could be made in safety and maintenance of industrial heat exchangers.

8.4 Other Tests (Vibration / Deformation)

The papers of Pettigrew (Pettigrew, Vibration analysis of shell-and-tube heat exchangers: an overview – Part 1: flow, damping, fluidelastic instability, 2003) and (Pettigrew, Vibration analysis of shell-and-tube heat exchangers: an overview – Part 2: vibration response, fretting-wear, guidelines, 2003)

present guidelines to prevent tube failures due to excessive flow-induced vibration in shell-and-tube heat exchangers. It's a very complete overview for shell-and-tube heat exchangers. The author presents an overview of vibration analysis procedures and design guidelines.

Generally a heat exchanger vibration analysis consist of the following steps: flow distribution calculations, dynamic parameter evaluation (damping, effective tube mass and dynamic stiffness, formulation of vibration excitation mechanisms, vibration response prediction and resulting damage assessment. These steps are to be used for a vibration analysis of any kind of heat exchanger.

Part 1 (Pettigrew, Vibration analysis of shell-and-tube heat exchangers: an overview – Part 1: flow, damping, fluidelastic instability, 2003) of the overview covers flow calculations, dynamic parameters and fluidelastic instability. Several vibration mechanisms are considered: fluidelastic instability – the most important mechanism -, periodic wake shedding, random excitation and acoustic resonance.

Part 2 (Pettigrew, Vibration analysis of shell-and-tube heat exchangers: an overview – Part 2: vibration response, fretting-wear, guidelines, 2003) of the paper covers forced vibration excitation mechanisms, vibration response prediction, resulting damage assessment and acceptance criteria.

Flow-induced vibration is usually considered as a detrimental factor causing heat exchange damages and is strictly prevented from its occurrence, but it can also have a positive effect and enhance the heat transfer. Cheng (Cheng, 2009) presents a novel approach to enhance the heat transfer by using the flow –induced vibration of a new designed heat transfer device. He studied the vibration and heat transfer numerically and experimentally, and a correlation of the shell-side convective heat transfer is obtained. He found that the new designed heat exchanger can significantly increase the convective heat transfer coefficient and decrease the fouling resistance. The flow-induced vibration does not require additional energy. Although the vibration may increase the flow friction coefficient, it seems that the heat transfer coefficient on the heat surface is less dependent on the flow velocity. Therefore, a low flow velocity could be used which would result in low energy consumption.

A similar work is presented by Yakut (Yakut, 2004). Flow-induced vibration characteristics of conical-ring turbulators used for heat transfer enhancement in heat exchangers are investigated. The vortex shedding frequencies and amplitude have been determined. The author observed an increase in vortex shedding frequencies when the pitch increases and the maximum amplitudes of the vortices are produced by conical-ring turbulators with small pitches. The maximum heat transfer is obtained for the smallest pitch arrangement.

8.5 Measurement of Temperature and Analysis of Thermal Stress

The paper of A. Herchang (Herchang, 2002) describes the use of an infrared camera to monitor temperature distribution over a plate-fin surface inside a plate finned tube heat exchanger. The differentiation of the temperature function is derived to determine the local convective heat transfer coefficients on a teste fin. With infrared thermography, A. Herchang was able to rapidly detect location and separation regions of the boundary layer over the whole surface of the tested models. Thanks to the comparison of the test results, it was for the author easier to understand and interpret the detailed dynamic phenomena of flow inside heat exchangers. With this experimental study, they demonstrate that the averaged heat transfer coefficient of staggered configuration is 14-32 % higher than that of in-line configuration.

The experimental set-up, used to investigate the local heat transfer performance of a plate consisted of a three-row plate-fin and tube heat exchanger is shown in the two figures below. A typical temperature map is shown in the second figure.

Test set-up (Herchang, 2002)

Temperature distribution on the plate fin surface (Herchang, 2002)

Thermal stress and deformation of the internally finned bayonet tube used for high temperature heat exchanger is presented in (Ma, 2012). Based on their analysis, the author proposed not to weld together the inner fin and inner tube so that they can expand freely. He compared the effect of gap between inner tube and inner fin on the stress and heat transfer performances.

8.6 Experimental Test Bench – Instruments

The following quantities need to be measured on an experimental test bench for the global thermal characterisation of a heat exchanger:

- Mass flow
- Temperature (inlet –outlet)

Different measurement techniques (diaphragm, Venturi...) can be used to measure the mass flow depending on the fluid inside the heat exchanger and the flow rate. Temperature measurements are usually performed with thermocouples.

For the pressure drop characterisation, the following quantity needs to be measured:

- Total pressure (inlet – outlet)

To characterize the pressure drop of a heat exchanger, the pressure measurements should be measurements of total pressure. However, depending on the inlet and outlet section, values of static pressure could be used.

Additional information on the flow field and temperature field will help to understand the physical phenomena responsible of the heat exchange. The following measurements should be considered when designing a test bench for heat exchangers.

- Velocity measurements – flow field analysis (PIV, LDV, hot wire)
- Local temperature measurements - thermal performance (thermocouple, liquid crystals)
- Heat transfer measurements – determination of the local h (temperature measurements)
- Vibration measurements - accelerometers
- Deformation measurements - strain gauges
- Leakage measurements – gas tracer

9. Conclusion

Heat exchanger is one of the most efficient device to transfer heat from one fluid to another. In this field considerable developments have driven in the past few years. As a result of which there are varieties of heat exchangers available in the market depending on the different use and different applications. The requirement in most heat transfer applications is to maximize the amount of heat transferred, subject to capital cost and pressure drop constraints. Both cost and heat transfer performance generally increase in proportion to exchange surface area.

The aim of this literature review is to serve for the preliminary choice and sizing of an innovative compact heat recovery unit. It is composed of eight parts that can be summarized as follows:

Various passive techniques of heat transfer enhancement are reviewed. Unlike active methods, passive techniques do not require direct input of external power. They largely use surface or geometrical modifications to the flow channel, or incorporate an insert, material, or additional device. Except for extended surfaces which increase the effective heat transfer area, these passive arrangements promote higher heat transfer coefficients by disturbing or altering the existing flow behavior. This, however, is accompanied by an increase in the pressure drop. The use of two or more techniques in combination constitutes compound enhancement. The effectiveness of any of these techniques is strongly dependent on the mode of heat transfer and type and process application of the heat exchanger.

The surface roughness has a significant impact on both heat transfer and pressure loss. Surface roughness is more desirable in the case of high Reynolds number application when the use of heat

transfer intensifications structures increase significantly the pressure drop. To take full advantage of the roughness a proper sizing is necessary with respect to the laminar sublayer thickness.

Moreover, the Additive Manufacturing (3D Printing, AM) seems to open the field to an orderly design of micro-structures, purposely designed in order to exploit at best the thermo-fluid dynamics boundary layers and thus achieve the highest heat transfer coefficient items.

Fluid maldistribution is a potential problem in any system of interconnected channels, and can significantly reduce the desired heat exchanger performance. Though, as discussed, this influence may be negligible in many cases, and the goal of uniform flow through the exchanger is met reasonably well for performance analysis and design purposes. Flow maldistribution can be induced by (1) heat exchanger geometry (mechanical design features such as the basic geometry, manufacturing imperfections, and tolerances), and (2) heat exchanger operating conditions (e.g., viscosity- or density-induced maldistribution and fouling phenomena). The most important flow maldistribution caused by operating conditions is viscosity-induced maldistribution and associated flow instability.

Compact heat exchangers with continuous-flow passages are highly susceptible to passage-to-passage flow maldistribution (irregular flow in neighboring flow passages) important in laminar flows. That is because the neighboring passages are geometrically never identical, due to imperfect manufacturing processes. By traditional manufacturing technologies, as subtractive (cutting and punching) and conjunctive (brazing) processes, it is especially difficult to control the passage size precisely when small dimensions are involved. The additive manufacturing can be the alternative to this problem. Moreover, the additive manufacturing processes, as compared to conventional manufacturing processes is its ability to make intricate 3-D geometries.

In general, CFD methods are used to understand the overall flow behavior of single/multi-component. CFD methods involves several steps like geometry modeling, computational mesh generation, and description of flow physics with turbulence, incorporating two-phase flow effects and visualization besides extending to multi-disciplinary areas like FSI and aero acoustics. CFD together with additive manufacturing design, enabled a high rate of both complex design iterations, and validation in meeting performance targets.

Compact heat exchangers used in aircraft are subjected to arduous operating conditions during flight. They experience high temperatures and are also subjected to thermal cycles during operation. Generally, Pressure and thermal stress calculations are performed to determine the thicknesses of critical parts in the exchangers, such as the fin, plate, tube, shell, etc.

10. Patents And Norms

This part of the bibliography consists in introducing an overview of all collected and relevant patents and norms in relation with heat exchangers.

10.1 Patents

i) Thermal expansion

Over the past years, the importance of heat exchangers has increased immensely from the viewpoint of energy conservation, conversion, recovery, and successful implementation of new energy sources. Its importance is also increasing from the standpoint of environmental concerns such as thermal pollution, air pollution, water pollution, and waste treatment. Heat exchangers are used in the process, power,

transportation, air-conditioning and refrigeration, cryogenic, heat recovery, alternate fuels, and manufacturing industries, as well as being key components of many industrial products available in the market.

Usually heat exchangers handle fluids of different temperatures, flow rates and thermal properties. Consequently, differential expansion of the metals can take place. When the terminal temperature difference between the fluids is significant these stresses can become severe, causing deformations and damages of different exchanger components.

Fixed heat exchanging elements (core or matrix where heat transfer takes place) “fixed design” are most susceptible to differential thermal expansion, because there is no inherent provision to absorb the stresses. One approach in common use is interconnecting different parts by a system that can absorb thermal expansion, for example an expansion joint.

Alternative approaches involve a design so that each component can independently expand and contract as needed: design allowing thermal expansion absorption.

A proper selection of the material and the method of bonding (such as brazing, welding, or tension winding) fins to plates or tubes is made depending on the operating temperatures, pressures, types of fluids used, fouling and corrosion potential, design life, and so on.

Patent numbers	Title	Pub. Date
KR20180016252 A	Heat exchanger element with thermal expansion feature	2018/02/14
US2017363369 A1	Reduced thermal expansion closure bars for a heat exchanger	2017/12/21
WO2013048922 A3	Brazed micro-channels heat exchanger with thermal expansion compensation	2013/05/23
US20130056176 A1	Heat exchanger with controlled coefficient of thermal expansion	2013/03/07
US20130299134 A1	Thermal expansion Joint and heat exchanger	2013/11/14
US6474408 B1	Heat exchanger with bypass seal allowing differential thermal expansion	2002/11/05
US20160377350 A1	Optimized plate fin heat exchanger for improved compliance to improve thermal life.	2016/12/29

ii) Fouling

The performance of heat exchangers usually deteriorates with time as a result of accumulation of deposits on heat transfer surfaces. The layer of deposits represents additional resistance to heat transfer, resulting in reduced the rate of heat transfer in a heat exchanger and often an increase in the pressure drop and pumping power as well. Both of these effects complement each other in degrading the performance of the heat exchanger.

In the present context, the term fouling is used to specifically refer to undesirable deposits on the heat exchanger surfaces.

Fouling represents heat exchanger operation-induced effect and should be considered for both the design of a new heat exchanger and operation of an existing exchange.

A lot of works have been done to reduce fouling formation and control of corrosion. In recent years, numerous methods have been developed to control fouling and corrosion. These methods can be classified as chemical means (inhibitor), mechanical means, changing the phases of the solution, electromagnetic fields, electrostatic fields, acoustic fields, ultraviolet light, radiation or catalytic treatment, surface treatment, green additives, fibre as a suspension, etc. If it is not possible to stop fouling, it becomes a practical matter to remove it. Surface cleaning can be done either online or offline. Furthermore, many different approaches are used to provide an allowance for fouling, and mainly using an excess surface area for heat transfer. These are described in the patent literature as follows:

Patent numbers	Title	Pub. Date
US2018051945 A1	Model-based method and system to detect heat exchanger fouling	2018/02/22
TW358869 B	Method for reducing the fouling of a heat exchanger surface of a heat exchanger, heat exchanger, and process for producing carbon blacks.	1999/05/21
WO2017088924 A1	Method and apparatus for preventing fouling of a heat exchanger element	2017/06/01
KR101557696 B1	Anti-fouling system of heat exchanger and its monitoring method	2015/10/06
US2014338867 A1	Shell and tube heat exchanger with improved anti-fouling properties	2014/11/20
US3842904 A	Heat exchanger	1974/10/22
US20030196781 A1	Heat exchanger with floating head	2003/10/23
US4007774 A	Heat exchanger apparatus and method of controlling fouling therein	1977/02/15
US8211548 B2	Silicon-containing steel composition with improved heat exchanger corrosion and fouling resistance	2012/07/03
US20160146511 A1	Heat exchanger assembly for aircraft ECS	2016/05/26
US20120255266 A1	Inertial filter for environmental control system heat exchanger applications	2012/10/11
FR2908505 A1	Heat exchanger e.g. air/air type heat exchanger for	2008/06/16

	internal combustion engine	
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iii) Design & Manufacturing

Usually, the manufacturing of heat exchangers entail a long and expensive progression of subtractive (cutting and punching) and conjunctive (brazing) processes. In addition, the brazing process usually requires a complex arrangement of fixtures that involves significant labor and time.

Opposed to brazing, additive manufacturing provides a means of achieving fine, planar structures and features, and boundaries, as well as complex internal fluid channels. The benefits of being able to build hollow structures with additive manufacturing may allow higher design complexity that may increase performance. These complex designs can be made with a favorable surface area, leading to the manufacturing of sophisticated heat exchangers.

Patent numbers	Title	Pub. Date
US20160108813 A1	Additive manufacturing ducted heat exchanger	2016/04/21
US20170205145 A1	Additive heat exchanger mixing chambers	2017/07/20
US20170336155 A1	Heat exchanger and fabrication	2017/11/23
US20170082372 A1	Integrated multi-chamber heat exchanger	2017/03/23
US5101890	Heat exchanger	1992/04/07
US20170131034 A1	Heat exchanger	2017/05/11
US20170089643 A1	Heat exchanger	2017/03/30
US20170023311 A1	Enhanced heat transfer in plate-fin heat exchangers	2017/01/26
US20170023312 A1	Enhanced heat transfer in printed circuit heat exchangers	2017/01/26
US20160114439 A1	Method of making a heat exchanger using additive manufacturing and heat exchanger	2016/04/28
EP2871433 A1	Heat exchangers and the production thereof	2015/05/13
WO2013163398 A1	Additive manufactured lattice heat exchanger	2013/10/31
US20080149299 A1	Method of using minimal surfaces and minimal skeletons to make heat exchanger components	2008/06/26
US20140116664 A1	Cross-flow heat exchanger having a graduated fin density	2014/05/01
US20030188850 A1	Tubular catalytic aircraft precooler	2003/10/09

US20150361922 A1	Heat exchanger design using variable geometries and configurations	2015/12/17
EP1429101 A2	Heat exchanger assembly with wedge-shaped tubes with balanced coolant flow	2004/06/16
US7866372B2	Method of making a heat exchanger core component	2011/01/11

iv) Icing

Aircrafts use cooling systems to manage thermal loads resulting from equipment operation. These cooling systems frequently include heat exchangers having separate hot and cold flow-paths. The heat exchanger transfers thermal energy from the hot flow-path air to the cold flow-path air, thereby cooling the air from the equipment compartment.

Air entering conventional heat exchangers from cooling turbines must be maintained at a temperature above a freezing temperature of water to prevent ice from accumulating on surfaces of the cold flow-path in the heat exchanger. If the temperature of the air entering the heat exchanger is below the freezing temperature of water, multiple layers of ice can accumulate on surfaces along the cold flow-path. These layers of ice deteriorate the heat exchanger by increasing power required to pump air through the heat exchanger and insufficiently cooling fluid in the hot flow-path. However, if colder air could be used in the heat exchanger without ice accumulating, then the air cycle machine efficiency could be increased and the heat exchanger size and weight could be reduced. Thus, there is a need for a heat exchanger that reduces the potential for ice accumulation.

Anti-icing systems are widely used for the prevention of ice gathering on leading edges of aircraft structures. Components such as wings, leading edge slats and spoilers, engine inlets, engine struts, radar domes, and vertical and horizontal stabilizers are fitted with anti-icing equipment and systems as appropriate for the particular aircraft.

A number of de-icing systems have been identified. These are described in the patent literature as follows:

Patent numbers	Title	Pub. Date
US2013140004 A1	Anti-icing heat exchanger	2013/06/06
CN104457396 A	Heat exchanger ant-freezing method and system	2015/03/25
US4246963	Heat exchanger	1981/01/27
US20150308731 A1	Heat Exchanger	2015/10/29
US20180093775 A1	Passive anti-frosting surface comprised of microscopic wettability patterns containing sacrificial ice	2018/04/05
WO2017070090 A1	Air-temperature conditioning system having a	2017/04/27

	frost resistant heat exchanger	
US9033030 B2	Apparatus and method for equalizing hot fluid exit plane plate temperatures in heat exchangers	2015/05/19
US20160122024 A1	Heat Exchanger	2016/05/05
US6442944 B1	Bleed air heat exchanger integral to a jet engine	2002/09/03

10.2 Norms

These collected norms are mainly from the aeronautical world and mostly deal with:

- Recommendations and requirements for design, material, manufacturing, inspection of several types of heat exchangers
- Manufacturing and assembly of conditioning system parts
- Methods and procedures to test and establish performance
- Qualification methods and tests
- Numerical analysis methods
- Maintenance procedures of heat exchangers
- Additive Layer Manufacturing methods, design and materials

Norms ISO 15547-1:2005, ISO 12212:2012, ISO 12211:2012, ISO 16812:2007, ISO 15547-2:2005 are recommendations and requirements for different types of heat exchanger designs: plate and frame heat exchangers, hairpin-type, spiral plate and shell and tubes heat exchangers for example. Mechanical design, materials selection, fabrication, inspection, testing, and preparation for shipment are discussed. Those norms will be helpful in the definition of an innovative heat exchanger.

Norms EN 1048:2014, EN 305:1997, EN 306:1997, EN 308:1997 define test procedures used in laboratories in order to establish the performance of heat exchangers. Temperature, pressure, temperature and/or pressure drops, capacity and how to measure them are discussed. All kinds of heat exchangers are treated, and related theory is developed.

Others norms like ADET0093, AIPI05-05-001, ASNA2141, ASNA2142, MTS075, NSA812001 deal with manufacturing process or assembly methods of conditioning system parts like composite piping and connection fittings. Various technics are also discussed like machining, welding, brazing and sealing of parts for conditioning lines.

Norms WD1602630, M20490, ISO / ASTM52910 – 17 or ISO 17296-2:2015 provide general information on Additive Layer Manufacturing (ALM) technology and general design rules to make a part compatible with 3D printing.

Other norms like AIMS03-27-000, AIMS02-08-001 or ASTM F3055 – 14a deal with materials specifications compatible with ALM technology (Inconel 718 ...).

To complete the selection of norms, some are focused on technical specifications of permanent connections of air conditioning systems, on the installation of thermoprobes, on analysis criteria of structures for system failures or for thermal-mechanical, on general conditions of use, on terminologies and generalities of heat exchangers and on operating and maintenance instructions.

All these standards are framed by the DO-160D, which specifies all the requirements that all equipment intended for flight must be checked in order to be qualified.

11. Annex

11.1 Annex - Correlations

i) NTU Correlations

The following table contains different $\epsilon = f(NTU)$ correlations:

<i>Flow configuration</i>	<i>Correlation</i>
Parallel flow heat exchanger	$\epsilon = \frac{1 - \exp[-NTU(1 + C_r)]}{1 + C_r}$
Counter-current flow heat exchanger	$\epsilon = \frac{1 - \exp[-NTU(1 - C_r)]}{1 - C_r \exp[-NTU(1 - C_r)]}$

(Ranganayakulu C. & Seetharamu) book gives several correlations between efficiency and NTU:

<i>Flow arrangement</i>	<i>Relation</i>
<i>Concentric tube</i>	
Parallel flow	$\epsilon = \frac{1 - \exp[-NTU(1 + C_r)]}{1 + C_r}$
Counter flow	$\epsilon = \frac{1 - \exp[-NTU(1 - C_r)]}{1 - C_r \exp[-NTU(1 - C_r)]} \quad (C_r < 1)$ $\epsilon = \frac{NTU}{1 + NTU} \quad (C_r = 1)$
<i>Shell and Tube</i>	
One shell pass	$\epsilon_1 = 2 \left\{ 1 + C_r + (1 + C_r^2)^{0.5} \right.$ $\left. \times \frac{1 + \exp[-(NTU)_1(1 + C_r^2)^{0.5}]}{1 - \exp[-(NTU)_1(1 + C_r^2)^{0.5}]} \right\}^{-1}$

N-shell pass (2n,4n,... tubes passes)	$\epsilon = \left[\left(\frac{1 - \epsilon_1 C_r}{1 - \epsilon_1} \right)^n - 1 \right] \left[\left(\frac{1 - \epsilon_1 C_r}{1 - \epsilon_1} \right)^n - C_r \right]^{-1}$
Cross flow (single pass)	
Both fluids unmixed	$\epsilon = 1 - \exp \left[\left(\frac{1}{C_r} \right) (NTU)^{0.22} \{ \exp[-C_r (NTU)^{0.78}] - 1 \} \right]$
$\frac{C_{max}(mixed)}{C_{max}(unmixed)}$	$\epsilon = \left(\frac{1}{C_r} \right) (1 - \exp\{-C_r [1 - \exp(-NTU)]\})$
$\frac{C_{min}(mixed)}{C_{min}(unmixed)}$	$\epsilon = 1 - \exp(-C_r^{-1} \{1 - \exp[-C_r (NTU)]\})$
All exchangers (Cr=0)	$\epsilon = 1 - \exp(-NTU)$
Multipass overall counter-flow, fluids mixed between passes	$\epsilon = \frac{\left(\frac{1 - \epsilon_p C^*}{1 - \epsilon_p} \right)^n - 1}{\left(\frac{1 - \epsilon_p C^*}{1 - \epsilon_p} \right)^n - C^*}$ <p>With n = number of identical passes (i.e each pass having the same ϵ_p)</p> <p>With ϵ_p = effectiveness of each pass as a function of $NTU_p = NTU/n$</p> <p>And $\epsilon_p = \frac{\left(\frac{1 - \epsilon C^*}{1 - \epsilon} \right)^{1/n} - 1}{\left(\frac{1 - \epsilon C^*}{1 - \epsilon} \right)^{1/n} - C^*}$</p> <p>(limiting value = $\epsilon_{counterflow}$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$)</p> <p>Multipass overall parallel flow fluids mixed between passes:</p> $\epsilon = \frac{1}{1 + C^*} [1 - \{1 - (1 + C^*)\epsilon_p\}^n]$

Flow arrangement	Relation
Concentric tube	
Parallel Flow	$NTU = - \frac{\ln[1 - \epsilon(1 + C_r)]}{1 + C_r}$
Counter Flow	$NTU = \frac{1}{C_r - 1} \ln \left(\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon C_r - 1} \right) (Cr < 1)$ $NTU = \frac{\epsilon}{1 - \epsilon} (C_r = 1)$
Shell and Tube	

One shell pass	$NTU_1 = -(1 + C_r^2)^{-0.5} \ln \left(\frac{E - 1}{E + 1} \right)$ $E = \frac{\frac{2}{\epsilon_1} - (1 + C_r)}{(1 + C_r^2)^{0.5}}$
N-shell pass (2n,4n,... tubes passes)	$\epsilon_1 = \frac{F - 1}{F - C_r} F = \left(\frac{\epsilon C_r - 1}{\epsilon - 1} \right)^{1/n} \quad NTU = n(NTU)_1$
<i>Cross-flow (single pass)</i>	
Cmax(mixed), Cmin(unmixed)	$NTU = -\ln \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{C_r} \right) \ln(1 - \epsilon C_r) \right]$
Cmin(mixed), Cmax(unmixed)	$NTU = -\left(\frac{1}{C_r} \right) \ln[\ln(1 - \epsilon) + 1]$
<i>All exchangers (Cr=0)</i>	$NTU = -\ln(1 - \epsilon)$

ii) **Forced Convection Correlations**

The following table from Handbook of Heat Transfer (Rohsenow et al.) gives correlations for forced convection:

- Laminar flow entrance length:

$$\frac{X/D}{Re_D} \approx 10^{-2} \quad (1.79)$$

- Skin friction coefficient definition:

$$C_{f,x} = \frac{\tau_w}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U^2} \quad (1.80)$$

- Laminar fully developed (Hagen–Poiseuille) flow between parallel plates with spacing D :

$$u(y) = \frac{3}{2}U \left[1 - \left(\frac{y}{D/2} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1.81)$$

with

$$U = \frac{D^2}{12\mu} \left(-\frac{dP}{dx} \right) \quad (1.82)$$

- Laminar fully developed (Hagen–Poiseuille) flow in a tube with diameter D :

$$u = 2U \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1.83)$$

with

$$U = \frac{r_0^2}{8\mu} \left(-\frac{dP}{dx} \right) \quad (1.84)$$

- Hydraulic radius and diameter:

$$r_h = \frac{A}{p} \text{ hydraulic radius} \quad (1.85)$$

$$D_h = \frac{4A}{p} \text{ hydraulic diameter} \quad (1.86)$$

- Friction factor:

$$f = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_w}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U^2} & (1.87) \end{cases}$$

$$f = \begin{cases} \frac{24}{Re_{Dh}} & D_h = 2D \text{ parallel plates } (D = \text{spacing}) \quad (1.88) \end{cases}$$

$$f = \begin{cases} \frac{16}{Re_{Dh}} & D_h = D \text{ round tube } (D = \text{diameter}) \quad (1.89) \end{cases}$$

$$\Delta P = f \frac{4L}{D_h} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho U^2 \right) \quad (1.90)$$

- Nusselt number:

$$Nu = \frac{hD}{k} = D \frac{\partial T / \partial r|_{r=r_0}}{T_0 - T_m} \quad (1.91)$$

- Laminar thermal entrance length:

$$X_T \approx 10^{-2} Pr D_h Re_{Dh} \quad (1.92)$$

- Thermally developing Hagen–Poiseuille flow ($Pr = \infty$):

- Round tube, isothermal wall:

$$Nu_x = \begin{cases} 1.077 x_*^{-1/3} - 0.70 & x_* \leq 0.01 \\ 3.657 + 6.874 (10^3 x_*)^{-0.488} e^{-57.2x_*} & x_* > 0.01 \end{cases} \quad (1.93)$$

$$Nu_{0-x} = \begin{cases} 1.615 x_*^{-1/3} - 0.70 & x_* \leq 0.05 \\ 1.615 x_*^{-1/3} - 0.20 & 0.005 < x_* \leq 0.03 \\ 3.657 + 0.0499/x_* & x_* > 0.03 \end{cases} \quad (1.94)$$

- Round tube, uniform heat flux:

$$Nu_x = \begin{cases} 3.302 x_*^{-1/3} - 1.0 & x_* \leq 0.00005 \\ 1.302 x_*^{-1/3} - 0.5 & 0.0005 < x_* \leq 0.0015 \\ 4.364 + 8.68 (10^3 x_*)^{-0.506} e^{-41x_*} & x_* > 0.001 \end{cases} \quad (1.95)$$

$$Nu_{0-x} = \begin{cases} 1.953 x_*^{-1/3} & x_* \leq 0.03 \\ 4.364 + 0.0722/x_* & x_* > 0.03 \end{cases} \quad (1.96)$$

- Parallel plates, isothermal surfaces:

$$Nu_{0-x} = \begin{cases} 1.233 x_*^{-1/3} + 0.40 & x_* \leq 0.001 \\ 7.541 + 6.874 (10^3 x_*)^{-0.488} e^{-245x_*} & x_* > 0.01 \end{cases} \quad (1.97)$$

$$Nu_{0-x} = \begin{cases} 1.849 x_*^{-1/3} & x_* \leq 0.00005 \\ 1.849 x_*^{-1/3} & 0.0005 < x_* \leq 0.006 \\ 7.541 + 0.0235/x_* & x_* > 0.006 \end{cases} \quad (1.98)$$

iii) Continuous Fins Correlations

For a continuous fin, the following correlations can be used for a channel factor α :

(Laminar flow)

$$f = \frac{24}{\text{Re}_{D_h}} (1 - 1,3553\alpha + 1,9467\alpha^2 - 1,07012\alpha^3 + 0,9564\alpha^4 - 0,2537\alpha^5)$$

$$j = \frac{7,541}{\text{Re}_{D_h} \text{Pr}^{1/3}} (1 - 2,61\alpha + 4,97\alpha^2 - 5,119\alpha^3 + 2,702\alpha^4 - 0,548\alpha^5)$$

(turbulent flow)

$$f = \frac{0,3164}{4\text{Re}_{D_h}^{1/4}}$$

$$j = \frac{0,023}{\text{Re}_{D_h}^{0,2}}$$

iv) OSF Correlations

Using the following parameters:

- w largeur de l'ailette ou pas de serration
- l_s longueur de serration
- h_s hauteur de l'ailette
- e épaisseur de l'ailette

The hydraulic diameter can be written as $D_h = \frac{2wh}{w+h}$

The friction and colburn factor are then given as:

$\text{Re} < 1000$:

$$f = 7,661 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,384} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,092} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,712}$$

$$j = 0,483 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,162} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,184} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,536}$$

Re > 1000:

$$f = 1,136 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,781} \left(\frac{e}{D_H} \right)^{0,534} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,198}$$

$$j = 0,242 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,322} \left(\frac{e}{D_H} \right)^{0,089} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,368}$$

Joshi & Webb 1987 gave other correlations with their physical parameters range:

$$7,518 \leq D_H \leq 13,487 \text{ (mm)}$$

$$0,112 \leq w/h \leq 0,246$$

$$0,001 \leq e/l_s \leq 0,064$$

$$0,087 \leq e/w \leq 0,191$$

They calculate the transition Reynolds with the following correlation:

$$\text{Re}^* = 257 \left(\frac{l_s}{w} \right)^{1,23} \left(\frac{e}{l_s} \right)^{0,58} D_H \left[e + 1,328 \left(\frac{\text{Re}_{D_H}}{l_s D_H} \right)^{-0,5} \right]^{-1}$$

For Re < Re*

$$f = 8,12 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,41} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,02} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,74} \quad j = 0,53 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,15} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{0,14} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,5}$$

For Re > Re* + 1000

$$f = 1,12 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,65} \left(\frac{e}{D_H} \right)^{0,17} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,36} \quad j = 0,21 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,24} \left(\frac{e}{D_H} \right)^{0,02} \text{Re}_{D_H}^{-0,4}$$

Mochizuki et al, 1987 gave the following correlations:

For $Re < 2000$:

$$f = 5,55 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,32} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,092} Re_{D_H}^{-0,67}$$

$$j = 1,37 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} \right)^{-0,25} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,184} Re_{D_H}^{-0,67}$$

For $Re > 2000$:

$$f = 0,83 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} + 0,33 \right)^{-0,5} \left(\frac{e}{D_H} \right)^{0,534} Re_{D_H}^{-0,20}$$

$$j = 1,17 \left(\frac{l_s}{D_H} + 3,75 \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{e}{D_H} \right)^{0,089} Re_{D_H}^{-0,36}$$

Manglik & Bergles, 1995, propose a correlation that can be used no matter the flow regime.

The physical parameters range has to be in the following specifications:

$$0,646 \leq D_H \leq 3,414 \text{ (mm)}$$

$$0,135 \leq w/h \leq 1,034$$

$$0,012 \leq e/l_s \leq 0,060$$

$$0,038 \leq e/w \leq 0,132$$

$$D_H = \frac{4whl_s}{2(wl_s + hl_s + eh) + ew}$$

With a $300 < Re < 10000$ range:

$$f = 9,6243 Re_{D_H}^{-0,7422} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,1856} \left(\frac{e}{l_s} \right)^{0,3053} \left(\frac{e}{w} \right)^{-0,2659} \times \left[1 + 7,669 \times 10^{-8} Re_{D_H}^{4,429} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-4,429} \left(\frac{e}{l_s} \right)^{3,767} \left(\frac{e}{w} \right)^{-0,236} \right]^{0,1}$$

$$j = 0,6522 Re_{D_H}^{-0,5403} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,1541} \left(\frac{e}{l_s} \right)^{0,1499} \left(\frac{e}{w} \right)^{-0,0678} \times \left[1 + 5,269 \times 10^{-5} Re_{D_H}^{1,340} \left(\frac{w}{h} \right)^{-0,504} \left(\frac{e}{l_s} \right)^{0,456} \left(\frac{e}{w} \right)^{-1,055} \right]$$

v) Wavy Fin Correlations

(Wang & jang, 1998) work gave correlation for heat transfer and friction for wavy fin in the case of wavy fin and tube heat exchangers. For the core friction of the heat exchanger, they use the pressure drop equation gave by Kays and London. The correlation for the Fanning friction factor that includes the entrance and exit pressure loss is written below:

$$f = \frac{A_c \rho_1}{A_0 \rho_m} \left[\frac{2\Delta P}{G_c^2 \rho_1} - (1 + \sigma^2) \left(\frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} - 1 \right) \right]$$

Where A_0 and A_c are respectively the total surface area and the flow cross-sectional area. Sigma is the ratio of the minimum flow area to frontal area.

For the Colburn factor j , they found the following correlation:

$$j = 0.324 Re_{D_c}^{J_1} \left(\frac{F_p}{P_1}\right)^{J_2} (\tan\theta)^{J_3} \left(\frac{P_1}{P_t}\right)^{J_4} N^{0.428}$$

Where:

$$J_1 = -0.229 + 0.115 \left(\frac{F_p}{D_c}\right)^{0.6} \left(\frac{P_1}{D_h}\right)^{0.54} \times N^{-0.284} \log_e(0.5 \tan\theta)$$

$$J_2 = -0.251 + \frac{0.232 N^{1.37}}{[\log_e(Re_{D_c}) - 2.303]}$$

$$J_3 = -0.439 \left(\frac{F_p}{D_h}\right)^{0.09} \left(\frac{P_1}{P_t}\right) N^{-0.93}$$

$$J_4 = 0.502(\log_e(Re_{D_c}) - 2.54)$$

They proposed the following friction factor correlation:

$$f = 0.01915 Re_{D_c}^{F_1} (\tan\theta)^{F_2} \left(\frac{F_p}{P_1}\right)^{F_3} \left(\log_e\left(\frac{A_0}{A_t}\right)\right)^{-5.35} \times \left(\frac{D_h}{D_c}\right)^{1.3796} N^{-0.0916}$$

Where:

$$F_1 = 0.4604 + 0.01336 \left(\frac{F_p}{P_1}\right)^{0.58} \log_e\left(\frac{A_0}{A_t}\right) (\tan\theta)^{-1.5}$$

$$F_2 = 3.247 \left(\frac{F_p}{P_t}\right)^{0.1458} \log_e\left(\frac{A_0}{A_t}\right)$$

$$F_3 = \frac{-20.113}{\log_e(Re_{D_c})}$$

They noticed the j factor correlation can describe 95.1% of the j factors within +/- 15% and f can correlate 97.3% of the friction factors within +/-15%.

(Khoshvaght Ailabadi, Hormozi, & Rad Hosseini, 2012) gave correlations for wavy plate-fin heat exchangers and considered different working fluids.

In cases from literature, correlation proposed for WPs do not consider all geometric parameters. For example, wave amplitude and length have significant effects on the performance of WPF heat exchangers. The impact of the fin thickness was also added.

Using Taguchi method, they performed a reduced number of simulations and from 250 simulated data points of 25 WPF models they extracted the following correlations for air as working flow:

- Laminar flow ($Re < 1900$):

$$j_{Air} = 0.2951 Re^{-0.1908} \left(\frac{F_p}{D_e}\right)^{0.7356} \left(\frac{F_h}{D_e}\right)^{0.1378} \left(\frac{L}{D_e}\right)^{-0.3171} \left(\frac{t}{D_e}\right)^{0.0485} \left(\frac{2A}{D_e}\right)^{0.2467} \times \left(\frac{L_d}{D_e}\right)^{-0.4976}$$

$$f_{Air} = 38.7488Re^{-0.3840} \left(\frac{F_p}{D_e}\right)^{-1.4790} \left(\frac{F_h}{D_e}\right)^{-0.3696} \left(\frac{L}{D_e}\right)^{-1.4542} \left(\frac{t}{D_e}\right)^{0.1016} \left(\frac{2A}{D_e}\right)^{1.0903} \\ \times \left(\frac{L_d}{D_e}\right)^{-0.1549}$$

- Turbulent flow (Re>1900):

$$j_{Air} = 0.7293Re^{-0.3637} \left(\frac{F_p}{D_e}\right)^{0.7966} \left(\frac{F_h}{D_e}\right)^{0.2398} \left(\frac{L}{D_e}\right)^{-0.4979} \left(\frac{t}{D_e}\right)^{0.0402} \left(\frac{2A}{D_e}\right)^{0.2012} \\ \times \left(\frac{L_d}{D_e}\right)^{-0.3026}$$

$$f_{Air} = 52.2375Re^{-0.3524} \left(\frac{F_p}{D_e}\right)^{-1.6277} \left(\frac{F_h}{D_e}\right)^{-0.3529} \left(\frac{L}{D_e}\right)^{-1.7484} \left(\frac{t}{D_e}\right)^{0.1034} \left(\frac{2A}{D_e}\right)^{1.2294} \\ \times \left(\frac{L_d}{D_e}\right)^{-0.2371}$$

The hydraulic diameter was used as a reference parameter for dimensionless number. 95% of the data are correlated within +/-12%. Other correlations for water and ethylene glycol are given.

Previously, the following correlations and work were presented in literature. They don't take into account as much parameters as (Khoshvaght Ailabadi, Hormozi, & Rad Hosseini, 2012) correlations and should be used carefully.

Zhang et al. (2003) investigated the enhanced heat transfer performed by 3D sinusoidal wavy channels. J and f factors were decreasing with increasing the cross-section aspect ratio Fp/Fh. These factors values increase with the increase of the spacing ratio Fp/2A.

Manglik et al. (2005) worked on 3D steady forced convection for wavy fin with low Re. No more information is given from this study.

Muley & al. (2006) presented experimental and computational studies for the sinusoidal wavy channels. J and f measurements were given for flow rates in Re range from 500 to 5000. For Re range from 100 to 1000 they obtain computational results with a j and f prediction in agreement with experimental measurements.

Junqi & al. (2007) studied thermal and hydraulic performance of wavy fin-and-flat tube heat exchangers with 11 models. They investigate all geometric parameters effects except wave length and amplitude. Two correlations were developed in their work:

$$j = 0.0836Re^{0.2309} \left(\frac{F_p}{F_h}\right)^{0.1284} \left(\frac{F_p}{2A}\right)^{-0.153} \left(\frac{L_d}{L}\right)^{-0.326}$$

$$f = 1.160Re^{-0.309} \left(\frac{F_p}{F_h}\right)^{0.3703} \left(\frac{F_p}{2A}\right)^{-0.25} \left(\frac{L_d}{L}\right)^{-0.1152}$$

Junqui & al. correlations cannot correctly describe heat transfer and pressure drop in a wide range of wave amplitude (especially in high wave amplitudes).

Naphon (2009) investigated temperature and flow distributions in a wavy channel with finite element method. He demonstrated that sharp edges of the wavy plate have significant impact on the flow structure and heat transfer enhancement.

Khoshvagt Aliabadi et al. (2011) use 3D-CFD simulation to estimate j and f factors in the case of wavy fin-and-flat tube heat exchangers.

For Re between 600 and 7000:

$$j = 0.0482 Re^{-0.2372} \left(\frac{F_p}{F_h}\right)^{0.1230} \left(\frac{L_d}{L}\right)^{-0.2183}$$

$$f = 1.160 Re^{-0.309} \left(\frac{F_p}{F_h}\right)^{-0.0988} \left(\frac{L_d}{L}\right)^{-0.0752}$$

The deviation on j and f factors are respectively of 3.22% and 3.68%.

vi) *Louvered Fins Correlations*

Ailette

pas de serration w
hauteur h_s
épaisseur e

Persienne

Longueur l_s
hauteur ouverte l_h
largeur l_t
angle θ

Davenport (1983)

$70 < Re < 900$:

$$f = 5,47 Re_{is}^{-0,72} \left(\frac{l_t}{h_s}\right)^{0,89} l_s^{0,2} l_h^{0,37} h_s^{0,23}$$

$1000 < Re < 4000$:

$$f = 0,494 \operatorname{Re}_{ls}^{-0,39} \left(\frac{l_h}{h_s} \right)^{0,33} \left(\frac{l_l}{h_s} \right)^{1,1} h_s^{0,46}$$

$300 < \operatorname{Re} < 4000$:

$$j = 0,249 \operatorname{Re}_{ls}^{-0,42} l_h^{0,33} \left(\frac{l_l}{h_s} \right)^{1,1} h_s^{0,26}$$

Achaichia & Cowell (1988)

$$f = 0,895 f_a^{1,07} w^{-0,22} l_s^{0,25} e^{0,26} (2l_h)^{0,33} \quad f_a = 596 \operatorname{Re}_{ls}^{(0,318 \operatorname{Log}(\operatorname{Re}_{ls}) - 2,25)}$$

$$j = 1,54 \operatorname{Pr}_{air}^{2/3} \operatorname{Re}_{ls}^{-0,57} \left(\frac{w}{l_s} \right)^{-0,19} \left(\frac{e}{l_s} \right)^{-0,11} \left(\frac{2l_h}{l_s} \right)^{0,15}$$

Sunden & Svantesson (1992)

$100 < \operatorname{Re} < 800$:

$$f = 9,2 \operatorname{Re}_{ls}^{-0,540} \left(\frac{w}{l_s} \right)^{-0,022} \left(\frac{h_s}{l_s} \right)^{-1,085} \left(\frac{l_h}{l_s} \right)^{0,067} \left(\frac{L}{l_s} \right)^{0,310}$$

$$j = \text{St} \cdot \text{Pr}^{2/3} = 3,67 \text{Re}_{l_s}^{-0,591} \left(\frac{w}{l_s}\right)^{0,0206} \left(\frac{h_s}{l_s}\right)^{-0,285} \left(\frac{l_h}{l_s}\right)^{0,0671} \left(\frac{L}{l_s}\right)^{-0,243} \text{Pr}_{\text{air}}^{2/3}$$

Chang & Wang (1996) (Louvered fins inside rectangular duct)

$$\epsilon = \frac{\text{Total heat transfer area (tubes and fins)}}{\text{External tubes surfaces}}$$

$$\epsilon_1 = \frac{\text{Louvered surface}}{\text{Total heat transfer area}}$$

For Re between 100 and 1000:

$$f = 0,862 \text{Re}_{l_s}^{-0,488} \epsilon^{0,706} \epsilon_1^{1,04}$$

$$j = 0,436 \text{Re}_{l_s}^{-0,559} \epsilon^{0,192} \epsilon_1^{0,0956}$$

vii) *Woven Textiles Correlations*

Woven textile allows an easy calculation of their properties, the following correlations can be used to calculate the density, the porosity and the area density of woven textile.

The number of pore per unit length N is defined as $N = \frac{1}{d+w}$ where d is the wire diameter and w the width of square pore. The screen layer thickness will be noted t and is equal to $2d$.

The density of the woven textile cores will be expressed as

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_s} = \frac{\pi N d^2}{2t} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{d}{d+w}\right)^2}$$

The porosity *epsilon* is given by the relationship, it can be noted that the flow resistance will usually decrease with an increasing porosity excepting for specific sample:

$$\epsilon = 1 - \bar{\rho}$$

The surface area density α_{s_f} can be calculated using $\alpha_{s_f} = \frac{\pi}{w+d} = \pi N$

A large surface area density is desirable for enhance thermal transport in compact heat exchanger. The value of α_{s_f} can be calculated to exceed 2000m²/m³ when $N > 18$ pores per inch which is comparable to the corresponding value of commercially available metal foams with similar pore size.

A friction factor is proposed by (Lu, Xu, & Wen). Defining A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 as the cross sectional areas of the flow before at and after the orifice, and associating them with P_1 , P_2 , P_3 pressure values and u_1 , u_2 , u_3 velocity values, it is possible to give a friction factor using Bernoulli equation and Momentum equation.

The friction factor k_{cell} , based on unit cell length dp , is defined as follow. R_{open} being the ratio $A2/A3$ and dp being equal to $d+w$ for orientation A and $2d$ for orientation B (see previous pictures for orientation). f_h is the friction factor based on channel height:

$$k_{cell} = \frac{P_1 - P_3}{\rho u_1^2 / 2} = \frac{\Delta P}{L} d_p \frac{1}{\rho u_1^2 / 2} = \left(\frac{1 - R_{open}}{R_{open}} \right)^2$$

$$f_H = \frac{\Delta P}{L} H \frac{1}{\rho U_m^2 / 2} = \left(\frac{1 - R_{open}}{R_{open}} \right)^2 \frac{H}{d_p}$$

For heat transfer calculation it is possible to use Chang correlation to calculate the effective thermal conductivity, this relation is based on combined series and parallel conduction:

$$k_e = \frac{k_f}{(1+A)^2} \left\{ \alpha^2 A \left[\frac{\alpha A}{\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\pi B \left(1 - \frac{k_f}{k_s}\right)} + \frac{2[1+A(1-\alpha)]}{\alpha - \frac{1}{4}\pi B \left(1 - \frac{k_f}{k_s}\right)} \right] + [1+A(1-\alpha)]^2 \right\}$$

With $A=d/w$ and $B=d/t$. α is a constant to take into account the effects of mesh size and is given by $\frac{\pi d}{2t} \leq \alpha \leq 1 + \frac{w}{d}$ when the base of the cross section is chosen as the wire radius $\alpha = 0.5$ and when the base is the wire diameter α is equal to 1. If the cross section is a square, α becomes $\sqrt{\pi}/2$.

It is possible to give a thermal conductivity correlation depending of directions:

$$\frac{k_{ez}}{k_f} = (1 - \gamma_{ay})(1 - \gamma_{ax}) + \frac{\gamma_{ax} + \gamma_{ay} - 2\gamma_{ax}\gamma_{ay}}{\gamma_{bz}(\lambda - 1) + 1} + \frac{\gamma_{ax}\gamma_{ay}(1 - \gamma_c^2)}{2\gamma_{bz}(\lambda - 1) + 1} + \frac{\gamma_c^2 \gamma_{ax}\gamma_{ay}}{\lambda}$$

$$\frac{k_{ex}}{k_f} = [1 - \gamma_{ay}\gamma_{bz} - \gamma_{bz} - \gamma_{ay}\gamma_c(1 - 2\gamma_{bz})] + \frac{\gamma_{ay}\gamma_{bz}}{\lambda}$$

$$+ \frac{\gamma_{bz}}{\gamma_{ax}(\lambda - 1) + 1} + \frac{\gamma_{ay}\gamma_c(1 - 2\gamma_{bz})}{\gamma_{ax}\gamma_c(\lambda - 1) + 1}$$

$$\gamma_{ay} = \gamma_{ax} = d/(d + w), \gamma_{bz} = \pi B, \gamma_c = c/d, \lambda = k_f/k_s.$$

The bulk volumetric heat transfer coefficient is given by the relation:

$$h_v(x) = \frac{Q}{V} \frac{1}{\Delta T(x)} \quad \text{and} \quad h_v = h \frac{A}{V} \quad (4.30)$$

where $\Delta T(x) = T_w(x) - \left(T_f(x) + \frac{\dot{Q}}{\dot{m}c_p} \frac{x}{L} \right)$, which is derived from the energy balance equation, h_v is the volumetric heat transfer coefficient, V is the volume of the tested sample, A is the area of the substrate and h is the heat transfer coefficient based on this area.

viii) *Miscellaneous Correlations for Heat Transfer and Friction Factor*

- DUCTS

Nusselt number for duct in laminar flow (fully-developed) extracted from (Hesselgreaves, Law, & Reay, 2016):

Table 6.1 Laminar flow parameters for ducts

Geometry	Nu_{H1}	Nu_T	k (fRe)	$\frac{j_{H,0}}{f}$	$\sqrt{\frac{Nu_T}{k}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{Nu_{H1}}{k}}$	K_{∞}	L^+	$\sqrt{\frac{Nu_T^3}{k}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{Nu_{H1}^3}{k}}$
Sine	3.014	2.390	12.630	0.269	0.435	0.489	1.739	0.040	1.040	1.472
Triang	3.111	2.470	13.333	0.263	0.430	0.483	1.818	0.040	1.063	1.503
Square	3.608	2.976	14.227	0.286	0.457	0.504	1.433	0.090	1.361	1.817
Hex	4.002	3.340	15.054	0.299	0.471	0.516	1.335	0.086	1.573	2.063
Rect2	4.123	3.391	15.548	0.299	0.467	0.515	1.281	0.085	1.584	2.123
Circ	4.364	3.657	16.000	0.307	0.478	0.522	1.250	0.056	1.748	2.279
Rect4	5.331	4.439	18.233	0.329	0.493	0.541	1.001	0.078	2.190	2.883
Rect6	6.049	5.137	19.702	0.346	0.511	0.554	0.885	0.070	2.623	3.352
Rect8	6.490	5.597	20.585	0.355	0.521	0.561	0.825	0.063	2.918	3.644
Parallel	8.235	7.541	24.000	0.386	0.561	0.586	0.674	0.011	4.227	4.824
Parallel, one side ins.	5.385	4.861	24.000	0.253	0.450	0.474	0.674	0.011	2.188	2.551
Semicirc	4.089		15.780	0.292		0.509	1.440	0.090		2.081

Duct shape	Hydraulic diameter	Friction factors and Nusselt numbers
	Circular $d_k = 2a$	$fRe = k = 16$ $Nu_T = 3.657$ $Nu_{H1} = 4.3636$
	Rectangular $d_k = \frac{4ab}{a+b}$ $a^* = 2b/2a$	$fRe = 24(1 - 1.3553\alpha^* + 1.9467\alpha^{*2} - 1.7012\alpha^{*3} + 0.9564\alpha^{*4} - 0.2537\alpha^{*5})$ $Nu_T = 7.541(1 - 2.61\alpha^* + 4.97\alpha^{*2} - 5.119\alpha^{*3} + 2.702\alpha^{*4} - 0.548\alpha^{*5})$ $Nu_{H1} = 8.235(1 - 2.0421\alpha^* + 3.0853\alpha^{*2} - 2.4765\alpha^{*3} + 1.0578\alpha^{*4} - 0.1861\alpha^{*5})$ $Nu_{H2} = 8.235(1 - 10.6044\alpha^* + 61.1755\alpha^{*2} - 155.18\alpha^{*3} + 176.92\alpha^{*4} - 72.9236\alpha^{*5})$
	Triangular (equilateral) $d_k = \frac{4b}{3}, a = \frac{2b}{\sqrt{3}}$	$fRe = 40/3 = 13.3333$ $Nu_T = 2.49$ $Nu_{H1} = 28/9 = 3.1111$ $Nu_{H2} = 1.892$
	Triangular (isosceles)	The most common geometry is that for $0 \leq \alpha^* \leq \infty$, giving the following relationships: $fRe = 12 \left(\alpha^{*3} + 0.2592\alpha^{*2} - 0.2046\alpha^* + 0.0552 \right) / \alpha^{*3}$ $Nu_T = 0.943 \left(\alpha^{*5} + 5.3586\alpha^{*4} - 9.2517\alpha^{*3} - 11.9314\alpha^{*2} + 9.8035\alpha^* - 3.3754 \right) / \alpha^{*5}$ $Nu_{H1} = 2.059 \left(\alpha^{*5} + 1.2489\alpha^{*4} - 1.0559\alpha^{*3} + 0.2515\alpha^{*2} + 0.1520\alpha^* - 0.0901 \right) / \alpha^{*5}$ $Nu_{H2} = 0.912 \left(\alpha^{*3} - 13.3739\alpha^{*2} + 78.9211\alpha^* - 46.6239 \right) / \alpha^{*3}$ for $1 < \alpha^* < 8$

Duct shape	Hydraulic diameter	Friction factors and Nusselt numbers
	Sine $d_h = \frac{4ab}{a + \sqrt{a^2 + 4b^2}}$	The geometric data and fully-developed flow data for sine ducts are given in Tables 6.3 and 6.4 respectively. For $0 \leq \alpha^* \leq 2$ the data can be approximated by: $fRe = 9.5687(1 + 0.8772\alpha^* + 0.8619\alpha^{*2} - 0.8314\alpha^{*3} + 0.2907\alpha^{*4} - 0.338\alpha^{*5})$ $Nu_T = 1.1791(1 + 2.7701\alpha^* - 3.1901\alpha^{*2} - 1.995\alpha^{*3} - 0.4966\alpha^{*4})$ $Nu_{HT1} = 1.9030(1 + 0.4556\alpha^* - 1.2111\alpha^{*2} - 1.6805\alpha^{*3} + 0.7724\alpha^{*4} - 0.1228\alpha^{*5})$ $Nu_{HT2} = -0.0202(1 - 30.0594\alpha^* - 216.1635\alpha^{*2} + 244.3812\alpha^{*3} - 82.4951\alpha^{*4} + 7.6733\alpha^{*5})$

(Hydraulic diameter is defined within 1% by

$$d_h/2a = (1.0542 - 0.4670\alpha - 0.1180\alpha^2 + 0.1794\alpha^3 - 0.0436\alpha^4)\alpha^*$$
)

	Regular polygon $d_h = \frac{4ab}{a + \sqrt{a^2 + 4b^2}}$
--	--

$d_h = 2a \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right)$ where a is the radius of the circumscribed circle

$$fRe = \left(\frac{n^2}{0.44 + n^2}\right)^4$$

n = number of nodes: $n = \infty$ for circular, 3 for triangular

$$fRe = \left(\frac{2Nu_{HT1} - 0.1908 \left(1 + 7.9489n - 1.1383n^2 + 0.0712n^3 - 0.0016n^4\right)}{0.44 + n^2}\right)^4$$

$$Nu_{HT2} = -2.2578 \left(\frac{1 - 0.8051n + 0.0586n^2 - 0.0007n^3 - 0.0002n^4}{+0.000003n^5}\right)$$

	Semicircular segment $d_h = \frac{4ab}{a + \sqrt{a^2 + 4b^2}}$
--	---

$Re = 15.78$
 $Re = 15.78$
 $Re = 15.78$
 $Nu_{HT2} = 2.96$

$$d_h = \frac{d}{(1 + 2/\pi)}$$

Duct shape Hydraulic diameter Friction factors and Nusselt numbers

Circular segment ducts

This is the more general case of the above semicircular segment duct, and is characterised by the included angle, which for the above is 180 degrees. The graphical solutions are as shown in the figure:

Figure modified from Kakac S., Shah R.K., Aung W., 1987. Handbook of Single-Phase Convective Heat Transfer. Wiley, New York.

Trapezoidal duct

$$d_h = \frac{4ab}{a + \sqrt{a^2 + 4b^2}}$$

Provided that the included angle of the sides is greater than about 60 degrees, and the ratio of short side to height is about unity, the following approximations can be used:

- $fRe = 14.2$
- $Nu_{H1} = 3.4$
- $Nu_{H2} = 2.2, 2.8$ and 3.0 for $\phi = 60, 75$ and 85 degrees, respectively

$$d_h = \frac{4b(a+c)}{a+c + \sqrt{(c-a)^2 + 4b^2}}$$

Table 6.3 Geometric data and fully-developed flow characteristics for sine duct

$\frac{2b}{2a}$	$\frac{P}{2a}$	$\frac{D_h}{2a}$	$\frac{y}{2a}$	$\frac{y_{max}}{2a}$	$\frac{\mu_{max}}{\mu_m}$
∞	—	—	—	—	3.825
2	5.1898	0.77074	0.75000	0.46494	2.288
$\frac{3}{2}$	4.2315	0.70897	0.56250	0.40964	2.239
1	3.3049	0.60516	0.37500	0.33390	2.197
$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$	3.0667	0.56479	0.32476	0.30773	2.191
$\frac{3}{4}$	2.8663	0.52332	0.28125	0.28205	2.190
$\frac{1}{2}$	2.4637	0.40589	0.18750	0.21347	2.211
$\frac{1}{4}$	2.1398	0.23366	0.09375	0.11926	2.291
$\frac{1}{8}$	2.0375	0.12270	0.04688	0.06173	2.357
0	2.0000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	2.400

Data from Bhatti, M.S., Shah, R.K., 1987. Turbulent and transition flow forced convective heat transfer in ducts. In: Kakac, S. (Ed.), Handbook of Single Phase Convective Heat Transfer. Wiley, New York. Copyright© John Wiley & Sons, Inc., by permission of John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Table 6.4 Fully-developed flow and heat transfer characteristics for sine duct

$\frac{2b}{2a}$	$K(\infty)$	L_{hy}^+	fRe	Nu_T	Nu_{H1}	Nu_{H2}	$T_{w,max}^*$	$T_{w,min}^*$
∞	3.218	0.1701	15.303	0.739	2.521	0	–	–
2	1.884	0.0403	14.553	–	3.311	0.95	2.92	0.002
$\frac{3}{2}$	1.806	0.0394	14.022	2.60	3.267	1.38	2.93	0.257
1	1.744	0.0400	13.023	2.45	3.102	1.55	2.17	0.398
$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$	1.739	0.0408	12.630	–	3.014	1.47	2.58	0.396
$\frac{3}{4}$	1.744	0.0419	12.234	2.33	2.916	1.34	2.93	0.379
$\frac{1}{2}$	1.810	0.0464	11.207	2.12	2.617	0.90	3.65	0.266
$\frac{1}{4}$	2.013	0.0553	10.123	1.80	2.213	0.33	4.16	0.099
$\frac{1}{8}$	2.173	0.0612	9.743	–	2.017	0.095	4.31	0.030
0	2.271	0.0648	9.600	1.178	1.920	0	–	–

For turbulent flow in duct, (Hesselgreaves, Law, & Reay, 2016) gave the following correlations:

- **Fully-Developed and Developing Flow in Smooth Duct (Techo et al):**

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f}} = 1.7372 \ln \left[\frac{Re}{1.964 \ln(Re) - 3.8215} \right]$$

Recommended for $10^4 < Re < 10^7$.

- **Fully-Developed and Developing Flow in Rough Duct (Chen):**

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f}} = 3.48 - 1.7372 \ln \left[\frac{\epsilon}{a} - \frac{16.2426}{Re} \ln(A_1) \right]$$

With epsilon the roughness and a the radius of the duct.

$$A_1 = \frac{\left(\frac{\epsilon}{a}\right)^{1.1098}}{6.0983} + \left(\frac{7.149}{Re}\right)^{0.8981}$$

Recommended for $4000 < Re < 10^8$.

- **Nusselt for a smooth tube (Gnielinski 1983):**

$$Nu = \frac{\left(\frac{f}{2}\right) (Re - 1000) Pr}{1 + 12.7 \left(\frac{f}{2}\right)^{0.5} \left(P_r^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1\right)} \left[1 + \left(\frac{d_h}{L}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \right]$$

Recommended for $2000 < Re < 5 \cdot 10^4$ and $0.5 < Pr < 2000$.

$$N_u = 0.0214(R_e^{0.8} - 100)P_r^{0.4} \left[1 + \left(\frac{d_h}{L}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \right]$$

Recommended for $10^4 < R_e < 5 \cdot 10^6$ and $0.5 < Pr < 1.5$.

$$N_u = 0.012(R_e^{0.87} - 280)P_r^{0.4} \left[1 + \left(\frac{d_h}{L}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \right]$$

Recommended for $3 \cdot 10^3 < R_e < 10^6$ and $1.5 < Pr < 500$.

- **Nusselt for a rough tube (Bhatti and Shah 1987):**

$$N_u = \frac{R_e P_r \left(\frac{f}{2}\right)}{1 + \sqrt{\frac{f}{2}} (4.5 R_{e_t}^{0.2} P_r^{0.5} - 8.48)}$$

Recommended for $R_e > 10^5$ and $0.5 < Pr < 10$, $0.002 < \epsilon/d_h < 0.05$.

$$N_u = \frac{(R_e - 1000) P_r \left(\frac{f}{2}\right)}{1 + \sqrt{\frac{f}{2}} [(17.42 - 13.77 P_{r_t}^{0.8}) R_{e_t}^{0.5} - 8.48]}$$

Recommended for $R_e > 2300$ and $0.5 < Pr < 5000$, $0.001 < \epsilon/d_h < 0.05$ with

$$P_{r_t} = 1.01 - 0.09 P_r^{0.36} \text{ for } 1 < Pr < 145$$

$$P_{r_t} = 1.01 - 0.11 \cdot \ln(P_r) \text{ for } 145 < Pr < 1800$$

$$P_{r_t} = 0.99 - 0.29 \cdot (\ln(P_r))^{0.5} \text{ for } 1800 < Pr < 12500$$

- Miscellaneous surfaces:

Correlations developed for heat transfer and friction factor for different heat transfer enhancement techniques used in CHEs.

Author	Types of roughness	Range of parameters	Correlations	Heat transfer coefficient
			Friction factor	
Prasad and Saini [109]	Small diameter transverse wires on top plate	$e/D: 0.020-0.033$ $p/e: 10-20$ $Re: 5000-50,000$	$\bar{f} = \frac{(0.020\beta + 0.05)}{2.0W/H}$ $f_r = \frac{0.95 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.53} + 2.5 \ln \left(\frac{e}{D}\right) - 3.75}{2}$ $R(H^+) = \left(\frac{f}{8}\right)^{-0.5}$ $+ 2.5 \ln \left[\left(\frac{2H}{D_c}\right) \left(\frac{2A}{A+B}\right) \right] + 2.5$ $R = 3.31 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.53}$ for the solid-type rib $R = 5.15 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.53}$ for the perforated rib	$\bar{St} = \frac{7.2}{1 + \sqrt{7.2} \left[4.5(e^+)^{0.28} p^{0.57} - 0.95 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.53} \right]}$ $G(H^+, Pr) = \left(\frac{f}{8}\right)^{-0.5} / St$ $+ 2.5 \ln \left[\left(\frac{2H}{D_c}\right) \left(\frac{2A}{A+B}\right) \right] + 2.5$ $G = 3.72(H^+)^{0.35} \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.08}$ for the solid-type rib $G = 2.25(H^+)^{0.35} \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.08}$ for the perforated rib $H^+ = \frac{h}{D_c} Re \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.5}$
Hwang and Liou [110]	Staggered parallel rectangular ribs on top and bottom plates	2A: 160 mm 2B: 40 mm Rib angle-of-attack: 90° PR: 5-20 H/De: 0.081, 0.162 H/2B: 0.13, 0.26 Open-area ratio of the perforated rib: 50% Re: 10,000-50,000	$f = 5.979 Re^{-0.363}$	$\bar{Nu}_p = 0.364 Re^{0.604}$
Liou and Wang [111]	Detached square ribs near bottom plate	Duct width: 160 mm Duct height: 40 mm Aspect ratio: 4 Rib height: 5.2 mm Rib width: 5.2 mm Rib angle-of-attack: 90° The ratio of rib pitch to height: 10 The rib to duct height ratio: 0.13 The non-dimensional clearance Between rib and wall: 0.58 Re: 5000-50,000	$f = 0.1911 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.196} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{-0.093}$ $\times Re^{-0.165} e^{-0.993(1-u/w)^2}$	$h = 0.0024 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.001} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{-0.06}$ $\times Re^{0.084} e^{-0.04(1-u/w)^2} \left(\frac{k}{D}\right)$ for $e^+ < 35$ $h = 0.0071 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.24} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{-0.028}$ $\times Re^{0.88} e^{-0.475(1-u/w)^2} \left(\frac{k}{D}\right)$ for $e^+ \geq 35$
C Gupta et al. [112]	Angled circular ribs on top plate	Test length: 1500 mm W: 200 mm H: 19 mm e/D: 0.023-0.05 p/e: 7.5&10 α : 30-90° Re: 4000-18,000	$f_c = 0.79 Re_c^{-0.77} \left(\frac{h}{B}\right)^{1.58} \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^{-0.79}$	$Nu_c = 0.55 Re_c^{0.23} \left(\frac{h}{B}\right)^{0.77} \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^{0.24}$
Leung et al. [113]	Rectangular ribs on bottom plate	Duct width: 202 mm Duct height: 120 mm Rib angle-of-attack: 90° Rib length: 200 mm B: 6.35 mm Spacing between ribs: 6.35 mm L/B: 3, 4 H/B: 6, 8, 10 Re: 510-2050	$f = 0.815 Re^{-0.361} \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.266} \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^{-0.190} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{0.591}$	$Nu = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} Re^{1.22} \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.625} \left(\frac{S}{10e}\right)^{2.22}$ $\times e^{-1.25 \left[\ln \left(\frac{S}{10e}\right) \right]^2} \left(\frac{L}{10e}\right)^{2.66} e^{-0.824 \left[\ln \left(\frac{L}{10e}\right) \right]^2}$
Saini and Saini [114]	Expanded wire mesh on top plate	Test length: 1000 mm W: 405 mm H: 35 mm e/D: 0.012-0.039 L/e: 25.00-71.87 S/e: 15.62-46.87 Re: 1900-13,000		
Author	Types of roughness	Range of parameters	Correlations	Heat transfer coefficient
			Friction factor	
Tsai and Hwang [115]	Alternate attached-detached ribs near bottom plate	2W: 160 mm 2B: 40 mm W/B: 4 h: 8 mm Rib width: 8 mm Rib angle-of-attack: 90° Detached rib clearance: 4 mm P/h: 10-30 h/2B: 0.2 The ratio of the rib clearance to h: 0.5 Re: 12,000-70,000	$R(H^+) = \left(\frac{f}{8}\right)^{-0.5}$ $+ 2.5 \ln \left[\left(\frac{2h}{D_c}\right) \left(\frac{2W}{W+B}\right) \right] + 2.5$ $R = 2.9 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.53}$	$G(H^+, Pr) = \left(\frac{f}{8}\right)^{-0.5} / St$ $+ 2.5 \ln \left[\left(\frac{2h}{D_c}\right) \left(\frac{2W}{W+B}\right) \right] + 2.5$ $G = 2.9(H^+)^{0.28} \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.07}$ $H^+ = \frac{h}{D_c} Re \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{0.5}$
Karwa et al. [116]	Rectangular and chamfered repeated ribs on bottom plate	W: 150 mm H: 12.5-30 mm W/H: 4.8-12 Test length to D_h ratio: 32, 66 e/D _h : 0.014-0.032 p/e: 4.5-8.5 Φ : -15° to 18° Re: 3000-20,000	$R = \sqrt{f} + 2.5 \ln \left(\frac{2e}{D_h}\right) + 3.75$ $R = 1.66 e^{-0.0078p} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{-0.4} \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^{-2.695}$ for $5 \leq e^+ < 20$ $e^{-0.762 \ln \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^2} (e^+)^{-0.075}$ for $20 \leq e^+ \leq 60$ $R = 1.325 e^{-0.0078p} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{-0.4} \times \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^{-2.695} e^{-0.762 \ln \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^2}$ for $20 \leq e^+ \leq 60$ For $W/H > 7.75$ use $W/H - 7.75$ in equations $e^+ = \sqrt{f} Re \frac{e}{D_h}$ $f_r = 0.245 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{-0.206} \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^{0.243} Re^{-1.25}$	$g = \left(\frac{f}{8} - 1\right) \sqrt{f} + R$ $g = 103.77 e^{-0.006p} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^{-2.56}$ for $7 \leq e^+ < 20$ $0.7343 \ln \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^2 (e^+)^{-0.31}$ for $20 \leq e^+ \leq 60$ $g = 32.26 e^{-0.006p} \left(\frac{W}{H}\right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^{-2.56} \times 0.7343 \ln \left(\frac{p}{e}\right)^2 (e^+)^{0.08}$ for $20 \leq e^+ \leq 60$ when $W/H > 10$ use $W/H - 10$ in equations for $e^+ \leq 24$ $Nu_t = 0.08596 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{-0.054} \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^{0.072} Re^{0.723}$ for $e^+ > 24$ $Nu_t = 0.02954 \left(\frac{e}{D}\right)^{-0.016} \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^{0.021} Re^{0.802}$ $e^+ = \frac{h}{D} \sqrt{f} Re$ $Nu_t = 0.067 Re^{0.888} \left(\frac{e}{D_h}\right)^{0.424} \times \left(\frac{\alpha}{60}\right)^{-0.077} e^{-0.782 \ln \left(\frac{\alpha}{60}\right)^2}$
Verma and Prasad [117]	Circular ribs on top plate	e/D: 0.01-0.03 p/e: 10-40 Re: 5000-20,000 e ⁺ : 8-42		
Momin et al. [118]	V-shaped wire ribs on top plate (downward)	Test length: 1.5 m Duct width: 0.2 m Aspect ratio: 10.15 e/D _h : 0.02-0.034 The ratio of rib pitch to height: 10 α : 30-90° Re: 2500-18,000	$f_r = 6.266 Re^{-0.425} \left(\frac{e}{D_h}\right)^{0.565} \left(\frac{\alpha}{60}\right)^{-0.093}$ $\times e^{-0.719 \ln \left(\frac{\alpha}{60}\right)^2}$	$Nu_t = 0.067 Re^{0.888} \left(\frac{e}{D_h}\right)^{0.424} \times \left(\frac{\alpha}{60}\right)^{-0.077} e^{-0.782 \ln \left(\frac{\alpha}{60}\right)^2}$

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11.2 Annex - Non Compact Heat Exchangers

i) *Plate and Shell Heat Exchangers*

Plate and shell heat exchangers combine shell and tube advantage with those of plate heat exchangers.

Plate and shell features an outer shell enclosing the circular plates welded into pairs. As a plate is more thermally efficient than a tube, this achieves a significantly higher level of heat transfer.

The maximum operating temperature is 900°C, and the maximum pressure is 100 bar. Plate and shell heat exchangers can work with aggressive media and acids which cannot be handled by conventional gasketed plate heat exchangers. They can also withstand extreme temperature shocks and pressures due to their rigid and compact construction.

For an equivalent area and capacity, plate and shell designs are smaller than shell and tubes heat exchanger due to the higher ratio of heat transfer area and specific volume. Plate and shell heat exchanger will occupy only 20 to 30% of the footprint of equivalent capacity shell and tube HX. The maximum operating pressure is also higher.

ii) *Spiral Heat Exchangers*

The classical design of a spiral heat exchanger uses two metal strips rolled around a central core to two concentric spiral channels. The channels are welded. Spiral heat exchangers tend to be self-cleaning. The smooth curved channels results in low fouling tendency. Each fluid having only one channel, a localized fouling will result in a reduction in the channel cross sectional area and lead to a velocity increase to scour the fouling layer. This self-cleaning effect results in reduced operating costs.

The typical limit in temperature is 400°C set by the limits of gaskets material. Special design without gaskets can operate with temperature up to 850°C. Maximum pressure is around 15 up to 30 bar.

Advantages are an optimum flow conditions on both sides of the heat exchanger, an even velocity distribution with no dead-spots and an even temperature distribution with no hot or cold spot. The HX is more thermally efficient with higher heat transfer coefficients and small hold up times and volumes. Removal of one cover exposes the total surface area of one channel providing easy inspection and cleaning.

For the same application, the spiral heat exchanger heat transfer area would be 90m² compared to 60m² for a plate and frame design or 125m² for a shell and tubes design.

iii) Shell and Tube Heat Exchangers

The most commonly used heat exchanger is the shell and tube type, it is principally used in industrial process heat transfer. As the use of other types of heat exchangers is increasing, the shell and tube heat exchanger popularity remains important principally because of its versatility.

A tube and shell heat exchanger is compound of tubes, baffles, shells, a front and rear head, tube sheets and nozzles. The selection criteria for each components depends of the operating pressures, temperatures, thermal stresses, corrosion characteristics of fluids, fouling and cost.

Straight-tube heat exchanger (one pass tube-side)

- Tubes

Tube diameters are very variable, smaller tubes allow high heat transfer coefficient and result in a compact heat exchanger when larger diameter tubes are easier to clean and allow lower pressure drop.

Different tube pattern are used:

To increase the surface provided by the tube, fins or others types of extended surfaces are common depending on the requirements (low pressure drop, etc.). The following tables illustrate some shapes taken by the finned surface:

The choice of tube pitch is, like for the tube diameter, a compromise between a close pitch (for increased shell-side heat transfer and compactness) and a large pitch (for a decreased shell-side pressure drop and fouling).

- **Baffle**

The transverse baffle can be of two types plate baffle (segmental, disk and doughnut, orifice baffle) and rod baffles.

In plate baffle category, segmental baffles are circular disks having a segment removed. A large number of shell and tube HX employ segmental baffles. Pressure drop and heat transfer are strongly affected by baffle cuts. The baffle cuts vary from 20 to 49%, commonly being 20-25%. 20% baffle cut gives the highest heat transfer for a given pressure drop.

The practical range for single segmental baffle spacing is $1/5$ to 1 shell diameter.

Segmental baffles have a tendency to create poor flow distribution. A common practice consists to use multiple segmental baffles to afford larger fluid flow on the shell side and create multiple streams inside the heat exchanger. Multiple baffles and resulting streams are illustrated in the following figure:

Next type of plate baffle is the disk and doughnut baffle. This type of baffle consists in an alternate disk and doughnut. This baffle design provides a lower pressure drop.

Rod baffles design uses alternate sets of rod grids instead of plate baffles. Tubes can be supported at shorter intervals without resulting in a high pressure drop. The flow is essentially parallel to tube axis. The longitudinal flow has low pressure drop to heat transfer conversion characteristics. The following schematic describes a rod baffle design.

Shell and tube heat exchangers can handle high vacuum to ultrahigh fluid pressures generally limited to 30 MPa on shell side and 140 MPa on tube side. The temperature range is limited by the materials choice only. However, the temperature difference is limited to 50°C due to the thermal expansion depending of the design.

iv) Plate and Frame Heat Exchangers

The plate and frame heat exchanger is currently second to the shell and tube heat exchanger in terms of market share.

The most common variant of the plate and frame heat exchanger consists of a number of pressed, corrugated metal plates compressed together into a frame. These plates are provided with gaskets, partly to seal the spaces between adjacent plates and partly to distribute the media between the flow channels. The most common plate material is stainless steel.

One advantage of the plate and frame heat exchangers is the ability to access plate surfaces for cleaning.

All manufacturers follow the same basic construction method, the difference in performance results in the patterns on the plates and the choice of materials.

The heat transfer surface consists of a number of thin corrugated plates pressed out of a high grade metal. The pressed pattern of each plate surface induces turbulence and minimizes stagnant areas and fouling. Due to the cost of manufacturing equipment, there is a limited range of plate design. Variation in the trough angle, flow path or flow gap are used to modify the NTU of the heat exchanger. When the trough angle is 90° , the troughs run vertically, the flow passage resemble a collection of vertical tube with low NTU. With the reduction of this angle, the path gains in tortuosity, the hydrodynamic resistance and the NTU are increased.

It is preferable to use this type of exchanger with a counter-flow single pass configuration to reach and extremely efficient performance. Two passes are common.

The operating limits of plate and frame are typically between minus 35°C and $+200^\circ\text{C}$. Design pressures up to 25 bar are tolerated.

These types of exchangers have a heat transfer areas range from 0.02m^2 to 4.45m^2 with flow rate up to $3500\text{m}^3/\text{h}$.

The good mixing and turbulence induced by the surface pattern offers to this type of exchanger a low propensity for fouling (fouling resistance observed are 25% those of shell and tubes HX). Wide gaps between plates are used when fouling is a concern, for example a 13mm gap.

The weight of this exchanger is usually lower than a shell and tubes HX.

Partially welded plate and frame heat exchangers exist allowing to reduce some limitations.

v) ***Brazed Plate Heat Exchanger***

The heat exchanger uses a pack of pressed plates brazed together, that eliminates the use of gaskets. The frame can also be omitted. These types of exchanger have heat transfer capabilities up to 600 kW.

For copper brazed units, temperature limitation goes up to 225°C with a max pressure of 30 bar. Nickel brazed units are used to reach temperatures up to 400°C with a max operating pressure of 16 bar only.

A brazed plate heat exchanger is about 20%-30% the weight of a shell and tube heat exchanger for the same application.

(Ranganayakulu C. & Seetharamu) detail the construction process.

The heat exchanger is assembled from a series of flat sheets/separating sheets and corrugated fins in a sandwich construction. Tube plates provide the primary heat transfer surface. Parting sheets are positioned alternately with the layers of fins in the stack to provide containment between individual layers. These elements are built into a complete core and then vacuum brazed to form an integral unit.

The heat transfer fins provide the secondary heating surface for heat transfer. Fin types, densities and heights can be varied to ensure that exchangers are tailor-made to meet individual customer requirements in terms of heat transfer performance versus pressure drop. Distributor fins collect and distribute the heat transfer fluid from the header tank to the heat transfer fins at the inlet and reverse the process at the outlet. Distribution fins are taken from the same range as the heat transfer fins, but tend to be less dense.

The heat exchanger core is then encased in a welded structure that incorporates headers, support plates and feed/discharge pipes. Most plate-fin heat exchangers are made of aluminum, with a vacuum-brazed core. Corrosion-resistant and heat-resistant brazing alloys can be used; for example, plate-fin heat exchangers can also be assembled in stainless steel, a variety of nickel-based alloys, and some other special alloys.

11.3 Annex - Simulation

i) Global Presentation

Simulation can be used to simulate heat exchangers thermal and fluidic behavior. Due to their complex design, heat exchangers can be simulated using CFD (Computational Fluids Dynamic) or FEA (Finite Element Analysis) software. Several CFD commercial or open software can be cited: STARCCM+, ANSYS-FLUENT, Openfoam.

These software use finite volume method or finite element method to solve thermal and fluidic equations.

To simulate a complex system several steps are required:

- A part created with a CAD software
- Meshing
- CFD Calculation

Usually the heat exchanger is designed on a CAO software (such as CATIA, Solidworks, Rhinoceros, etc.) to create a part.

To be able to calculate on this part, an image based meshing has to be done. CAD based meshing consist in an automatic process which transform a 3D image data to a computer model for computational fluid dynamic. The computer begins to create a surface meshing splitting the external surface of the CAD volume in several geometric simple 2D elements (triangle, square, etc).

Example of a tetrahedral and hexahedral meshing on two geometries

The next step consists in the volume meshing, creating volume 3D elements like tetrahedron, hexahedron, etc. to divide the internal volume in cells.

The cell size is defined to size the smallest elements of the CAD and to keep the mesh shape close to the initial geometry shape. Each cell of the volume has its own properties (temperature, velocity, density, etc).

Once the meshing is finished, the cells surfaces which are located on the external surface of the part mesh are grouped into “patches”. These patches will become different boundary conditions depending on the nature of each patch (inlet, outlet, wall, heat source, etc.). All CFD problems are defined in terms of initial and boundary conditions.

For example for a flow simulation in a tube, the surface of the mesh at each end of the tubes will be assigned to inlet or outlet boundary conditions and will receive respectively a specified velocity and a specified pressure. The other surfaces of the tube will receive a wall boundary condition (velocity equal to 0) to indicate no fluid can pass through it.

Cells affected by boundary conditions will have one or several of their properties fixed. For the tube example, each cells of the inlet will receive the velocity specified in the boundary condition, no matter the simulation progress.

Using the boundaries, the software will solve several equations iteratively. For each iteration, the solver will apply corrections on cells properties values in the volume mesh. From the initial state of the system, the value of each cells property will be corrected and calculated until they reach a constant value corresponding to the equilibrium in accordance with specified boundaries limits.

(Ranganayakulu C. & Seetharamu) illustrate that any fundamental fluid dynamics problem is governed by the Navier-Stockes equations. CFD solves these three equations which represent respectively mass, momemtum and energy conservation.

- Continuity equation

$$\frac{\delta \rho}{\delta t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho V) = 0$$

The following figure shows the application of the mass conservation on a square cell of a mesh:

- Momentum Equation

$$\frac{\delta(\rho V)}{\delta t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho V V) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \Sigma + \rho g$$

Application of the momentum equation on each cell:

- Energy equation

$$\frac{\delta(\rho E)}{\delta t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho E V) = \nabla \cdot (P \cdot V) + \rho g \cdot V + \nabla \cdot q + \nabla \cdot q_R$$

For the conduction, the program solver will solve the Fourier equation:

$$\frac{\delta T}{\delta t} + D \nabla^2 T = \frac{S}{\rho C p}$$

Others equations can also be taken into account to include phenomenon such as turbulence, phase change, etc.

The simulated case can finally be post-treated to extract velocity, temperature and others properties distribution inside the volume meshed. Mass flow and heat transfer can be evaluated.

Due to computer and time resources needed for the simulation of an entire heat exchanger, a common approach consists to combine CFD and usual design methods. Usual design methods are used to determine the required heat transfer coefficient. Then only one element of the heat exchanger is simulated, for example one tube or a sample of the heat exchanger. This element needs less resource to be simulated and can be modified easily to observe the impact of the physical parameters on the heat transfer rate. It allows testing complex design modifications. The heat transfer coefficient of the single element can then be determined and the number of total elements needed in the final heat exchanger can be evaluated.

ii) Transient / Steady

A simulation can be run differently depending on the study criterion, to take into account the time variable.

Usual heat exchangers are designed for a steady state meaning the time variable is not taken into account. The CFD software will iteratively go from the initial solution to the final solution which corresponds to an equilibrium state. This equilibrium is reached when the conservative quantities balance reach 0. For example, a simulation will be considered as ended when the conservative value like balance of mass flow, heat transfer, etc... will reach 0 and when the others values (temperatures, etc...) will reach a constant value on each cell. At each iteration, the CFD software provides residual values which are the difference of the cells values between two iterations. These residuals tend to a fixed constant value and have to be as small as possible.

A steady state simulation will give the heat exchanger state a long time after the system start, when it reach the operating state specified by boundary condition.

However, to observe the temperature of the heat exchanger during the starting phase of the system, or to track the response of the system to a flow or flux variation over time, it is necessary to simulate the heat exchanger in a transient simulation. A transient simulation is time consuming and resources consuming. The CFD software will calculate iteratively several successive states spaced by a time step. If this time step is too high, numerical errors on the values (Temperature, Velocity, etc...) appear and spread over time and complicate the convergence.

To find the best balance, the choice of the time step is done to allow the fluid particle to range 1 to 10 cells, which corresponds to a Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy number (also called CFL) between 1 and 10.

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